

Lectures on Modules Theory

Prof. Dr. Areej Tawfeeq Hameed

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Education for Girls,

University of Kufa, Najaf , Iraq.

areej.tawfeeq@uokufa.edu.iq and areej238@gmail.com

(Review)

Ring, Subring and Ideal

0.1. RINGS

DEFINITION 0.1.1.

The mathematics system $(R, +, \cdot)$ is called a **ring** if a nonempty set (R) with two operations addition $(+)$ and multiplication (\cdot) satisfying the following requirements:

$$\forall a, b, c \in R,$$

1- $(R, +)$ is binary operation, that mean

$$a- \text{ Closure under addition } a, b \in R \Rightarrow a+b \in R, \text{ and}$$

$$b- \text{ Well-define: } a=a_1 \wedge b=b_1 \Rightarrow a+b = a_1+b_1, \forall a, b, a_1, b_1 \in R.$$

2- Associative: $(a+b)+c=a+(b+c)$.

3- Identity: $\exists 0 \in R \exists a+0=0+a=a$.

4- Inverse: $\forall a \in R \exists -a \in R \exists a+(-a)=(-a)+a=0$.

5- Commutative: $a+b = b+a$.

6- R is closure under multiplication, $a, b \in R \Rightarrow a \cdot b \in R$.

7- Associative: $(a \cdot b) \cdot c = a \cdot (b \cdot c)$.

8- The operation (\cdot) is distributive over the operation $(+)$:

$$a \cdot (b+c) = a \cdot b + a \cdot c \wedge (a+b) \cdot c = a \cdot c + b \cdot c.$$

DEFINITION 0.1.2.

A nonempty set R with two operation $(+)$ addition and (\cdot) multiplication is called **ring** if and only if,

1- $(R, +)$ is commutative group,

2- (R, \cdot) is semi group,

3- The semi group operation (\cdot) is distributive over the group operation $(+)$.

REMARK 0.1.3. Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring then:-

1- $(R, +, \cdot)$ is called commutative ring if (\cdot) commutative.

$2-(R,+, \cdot)$ is called ring with identity (unity) if it has an identity (denoted by (1))with respect to $(w \cdot r \cdot t)(\cdot)$, then (1) is called an unit element.

PROPOSITION 0.1.4.

Let $(M, *)$ be an commutative group and let $\text{Hom}(M)=\{f | f: M \rightarrow M \text{ is a group homomorphism} \}$.

Define $(+)$ and (\cdot) on $\text{Hom}(M)$ such that

$(f+g)(m) = f(m) * g(m)$ and $(f \cdot g)(m) = (f \circ g)(m) = f(g(m)) \forall f, g \in \text{Hom}(M), \forall m \in M$. Then

$(\text{Hom}(M), +, \cdot)$ is a ring.

PROPOSITION 0.1.5. Prove that $(Z_n, +_n, \cdot_n)$ is commutative ring with identity.

DEFINITION 1.1.6. In any ring $(R, +, \cdot)$, $\forall a, b \in R$, then **the difference** of a and b is denoted by $a-b$ define as: $a-b=a+(-b)$

THEOREM 0.1.7.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, then for any $a, b \in R$,

1- $a \cdot 0 = 0$, $0 \cdot a = 0$. 2- $a \cdot (-b) = -(a \cdot b) = (-a) \cdot b$. 3- $(-a) \cdot (-b) = a \cdot b$. 4- $(-a) = -a$.

5- $(-1) \cdot a = -a \wedge (-1) \cdot (-1) = 1$, if R has unity (1).

THEOREM 0.1.8.

1- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring with identity ,then the pair (R^*, \cdot) forms a group, known as the group of invertible elements (i.e., For all $a \in R^*, \exists a^{-1} \in R$).

2- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring with identity such that $R \neq \{0\}$. Then the elements 0 and 1 are distinct ($0 \neq 1$).

THEOREM 0.1.9.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, then $\forall a, b, c \in R$,

1- $-(a-b) = -a+b$ 2- $a \cdot (b-c) = a \cdot b - a \cdot c$ & $(a-b) \cdot c = a \cdot c - b \cdot c$

PROPOSITION 0.1.10.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring. $(R, +, \cdot)$ is commutative ring if and only if,

$(a+b) \cdot (a-b) = a^2 - b^2, \forall a, b \in \mathcal{R}$.

DEFINITION 0.1.11.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and $a \in R$. a is called **idempotent element** $\Leftrightarrow a^2 = a$

DEFINITION 0.1.12.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring with unity. R is called **Boolean ring** $\Leftrightarrow x^2 = x, \forall x \in R$. (i.e) every element of R is idempotent element).

DEFINITION 0.1.13.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, if $\exists n$ is positive integer (n) such that $n \cdot a = 0$, $\forall a \in R$, then the least positive integer (n) this property is called the **Characteristic of the ring**.

If no such positive integer exists (that is $n \cdot a = 0 \forall a \in R \Rightarrow n = 0$), then we say that $(R, +, \cdot)$ has Characteristic zero.

THEOREM 0.1.14.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring with unity (1). Then $(R, +, \cdot)$ has $\text{Char}(R) = n$ ($n > 0$) $\Leftrightarrow n$ is the least positive integer $\exists n \cdot 1 = 0$

0.2. SUBRING OF A RING

DEFINITION 0.2.1.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and $\emptyset \neq W \subseteq R$. $(W, +, \cdot)$ is called a **subring** of $(R, +, \cdot) \Leftrightarrow (W, +, \cdot)$ is a ring.

REMARK 0.2.2.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring $R \neq \{0\}$, then R has at least two subrings which are $(R, +, \cdot)$, $(\{0\}, +, \cdot)$

THEOREM 0.2.3.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and $\emptyset \neq W \subseteq R$, then $(W, +, \cdot)$ is a subring of $(R, +, \cdot)$ if and only if,
 $1 - a - b \in W$, $2 - a \cdot b \in W$, $\forall a, b \in W$

THEOREM 0.2.4.

- 1- Every subring of commutative ring is commutative.
- 2- Intersection of two subrings of a ring R is a subring of R .
- 3- Let S and T be subrings of R . Then $S \cup T$ is a subring of $R \Leftrightarrow S \subseteq T$ or $T \subseteq S$.

DEFINITION 0.2.5.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring. The set $\{x : x \in R \wedge x \cdot y = y \cdot x, \forall y \in R\}$ is called the **center of R** and denoted by $\text{cent}(R)$.

PROPOSITION 0.2.6.

- 1- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, then $(\text{cent}(R), +, \cdot)$ is subring of $(R, +, \cdot)$.
- 2- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be commutative ring, then $\text{cent}(R) = R$.

0.3. IDEALS OF RING

DEFINITION 0.3.1.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be a nonempty subring of R ($\emptyset \neq I \subseteq R$). I is called **ideal** if and only if, $r \cdot a \in I$ & $a \cdot r \in I, \forall r \in R, a \in I$.

REMARK 0.3.2.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be a subring of R and $\emptyset \neq I \subseteq R$,

1- I is called **left ideal** if and only if, $r \cdot a \in I, \forall r \in R, a \in I$.

2- I is called **right ideal** if and only if, $a \cdot r \in I, \forall r \in R, a \in I$.

3- I is called (**two sided ideal**) **ideal** if and only if, $r \cdot a \in I$ & $a \cdot r \in I, \forall r \in R, a \in I$.

THEOREM 1.3.3.

Let $(R; +, \cdot)$ be a ring and $\emptyset \neq I \subseteq R$, then $(I, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$ if and only if, $\forall a, b \in I, 1- a-b \in I. 2- r \cdot a \in I, a \cdot r \in I, \forall r \in R$.

REMARK 0.3.4.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring, let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be a subring of R . I is called **ideal of ring R** if and only if, $r \cdot a \in I, \forall r \in R, a \in I$.

REMARK 0.3.5.

1- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, $R \neq \{0\}$, then R has at least two ideals which are $(R, +, \cdot)$ and $(\{0\}, +, \cdot)$.

2- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, $R \neq \{0\}$. Let I ideal of $R, \emptyset \neq I \subseteq R$ such that $I \neq R$, then I is a proper ideal of R .

DEFINITION 0.3.6.

A ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ such that $R \neq \{0\}$, which contains no ideals except these two ideals $(R, +, \cdot)$ and $(\{0\}, +, \cdot)$. R is said to be **simple ring**.

PROPOSTION 0.3.9.

1- If $(\mathcal{R}, +, \cdot)$ is real number, then $(\mathcal{R}, +, \cdot)$ is simple ring.

2- Every ideal of ring R is a subring of R .

3- Every subrings of $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of \mathbb{Z} .

4- Every subring of $(\mathbb{Z}_n, +_n, \cdot_n)$ is an ideal of \mathbb{Z}_n .

PROPOSITION 0.3.10.

If $(I, +, \cdot)$ is a proper ideal of ring $(R, +, \cdot)$, then no element $a \in I$ has inverse of R , (i.e. $I \cap R^* \neq \emptyset$) . [the pair (R^*, \cdot) forms a group, known as the group of invertible elements (i.e., For all $a \in R^*, \exists a^{-1} \in R$)]

THEOREM 0.3.11.

- 1- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring with unity 1. Let I be an ideal of R such that $1 \in I$, then $I=R$.
- 2- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring with unity 1. Let I be an ideal of R such that $\exists a \in I, a \neq 0, a$ has multiplication inverse, then $I=R$.

THEOREM 0.3.12.

- 1- Any field F has only two ideals, which that F and $\{0\}$.
- 2- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a field, then R has no proper ideal.
- 3- Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with unity 1 and $a \in R$. If $I = \{x \mid x = r.a, r \in R\}$, then $(I, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of R & containing a .

DEFINITION 0.3.13.

Let R be a ring, and $I \subseteq R$, the set $T = \bigcap_{i \in W} \{I_i \mid I_i \text{ is an ideal of } R, I_i \supseteq I\}$

T is called **ideal of R generated by I** denoted $\langle I \rangle$, or (I) .

DEFINITION 0.3.14.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with identity and $a \in R$, then the ideal I is called **the principle ideal of R generated by (a)** and denoted by $\langle a \rangle$ or (a) where

$$I = \langle a \rangle = \{x \mid x = r.a, r \in R\}.$$

PROPOSITION 0.3.15.

For any ideal $(I, +, \cdot)$ of ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. Defined the set $C(I) = \{r \in R, r.a - a.r \in I, \forall a \in R\}$, then $(C(I), +, \cdot)$ is a subring of R .

PROPOSITION 0.3.16.

Let $(I_1, +, \cdot)$ and $(I_2, +, \cdot)$ are two ideals of $(R, +, \cdot)$. Define $I_1 + I_2 = \{a+b : a \in I_1 \wedge b \in I_2\}$, and $I_1 \cdot I_2 = \{\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cdot b_i : a_i \in I_1 \wedge b_i \in I_2\}$, for all $a, b, a_i, b_i \in R, n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Show that $I_1 + I_2, I_1 \cdot I_2$ are ideals of R . (Note that : In general $I_1 + I_2 \subseteq I_1 \cdot I_2$).

THEOREM 0.3.17. (Theorem of Division Algorithm).

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with unity, let $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ be two non zero polynomial ring in $F[x]$ such that if $g(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + \dots + a_n x^n; n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$,

$a_i \in R, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, is a_n inverse element. Then $\exists! q(x), r(x) \in F[x]$ such that $f(x) = q(x) \cdot$

$g(x) + r(x)$. where $r(x) = 0$ or $\deg(r(x)) < \deg(g(x))$.

THEOREM 0.3.18.

- 1- Any ideal in $(Z, +, \cdot)$ is principle ideal of a ring Z .
- 2- Any ideal in $(Z_n, +_n, \cdot_n)$ is principle ideal of Z_n .

DEFINITION 0.3.19.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with identity . R is called **principle ideal ring** (p.I.R) , if every ideal principle ideal of ring.

PROPOSITION 0.3.20.

If $(I_1, +, \cdot)$ and $(I_2, +, \cdot)$ are ideals of a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ $\ni I_1 \cap I_2 = \{0\}$. Prove that $a \cdot b = 0 \quad \forall a \in I_1, b \in I_2$.

DEFINITION 0.3.21.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n be ideals of R , then

$\langle I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n \rangle = I_1 + I_2 + \dots + I_n = \{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n : x_i \in I_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$, is an ideal of R .

DEFINITION 0.3.21. Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$, $a \in R$, then

The set $a+I = \{ a+i | i \in I \}$ is called **a left coset of I in R** .

The set $I+a = \{ i+a | i \in I \}$ is called **a right coset of I in R** .

Since $(+)$ is commutative with ring R , then clearly $a+I = I+a$, for all $a \in R$.

PROPOSITION 3.1.42. Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$, $a, b \in R$, then

$a+I = b+I$ if and only if, $a-b \in I$.

PROPOSITION 3.1.43.

Let F be any field , then $F[x]$ is a principle ideal ring (p.I.R) .

0.4. QUOTIENT RINGS:

DEFINITION 0.4.1.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be any ring and $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of R , $(I, +)$ is subgroup of group $(R, +)$. So $(I, +) \triangleleft (R, +)$, since any subgroup of commutative group is **normal**. Then the system

$(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is called **the quotient ring of R by I**, where define

\oplus, \odot on R/I by $(a+I) \oplus (b+I) = (a+b) + I$ and $(a+I) \odot (b+I) = (a \cdot b) + I$.

REMARK 0.4.2.

The zero element of $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is the cost $0+I = I$, while $-(a+I) = (-a) + I$.

THEOREM 0.4.3.

Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$, then $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.

THEOREM 0.4.4.

Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. If R is a commutative ring with unity 1, then $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a commutative ring with unity $(1+I)$.

THEOREM 0.4.5.

Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. If $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a commutative ring, then $a \cdot b = b \cdot a \in I$, where $\forall a, b \in R$.

REMARK 0.4.6.

Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. Then prove or disprove the following

- 1- If $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring has unity $(1+I)$, then $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a ring has unity 1.
- 2- If $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a ring has char zero, then $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring has char zero.
- 3- If $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a ring has $\text{char}(R) = n, n \neq 0$, then $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring has $\text{char}(R/I) = n, n \neq 0$.
- 4- If $(R, +, \cdot)$ is an integer domain, then $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is an integer domain.
- 5- If $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is an integer domain, then $(R, +, \cdot)$ is an integer domain.

6- Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be an ideal of the ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. Then the following

- a- $(R/R, \oplus, \odot) = \{0\}$ is a trivial ring.
- b- $(R/\{0\}, \oplus, \odot) = R$.

PROPOSITION 0.4.7.

In the ring $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ of integers, $I = \langle n \rangle$ where n is fixed positive integer, then $(\mathbb{Z}/\langle n \rangle, \oplus, \odot) = (\mathbb{Z}_n, +_n, \cdot_n)$.

0.5. ANNIHILATER OF IDEAL ON RING .

DEFINITION 0.5.1.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and I be an ideal of R . **The annihilator of R** is denoted by $(\text{ann } I)$, it is defined to the set $\text{ann } I = \{a \in R : r \cdot a = 0, \forall r \in I\}$

PROPOSITION 0.5.2. Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and I be an ideal of R . $\text{ann } I$ is an ideal in R .

PROPOSITION 0.5.3. Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with unity 1 and $a \in R$.

If $I = \{a \mid r \cdot a = 0, r \in R\}$, then $(I, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of R & containing a .

REMARK 0.5.4.

If $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a ring, then $\text{ann } I$ is an ideal of $R \Rightarrow R/\text{ann } I$ is a ring.

DEFINITION 0.5.5. A ring R is called **faithful** if and only if, $\text{ann } I = \langle 0 \rangle$.

PROPOSITION 0.5.6.

1- Let R be a ring and I be an ideal of R which contained I in $\text{ann } I$. (i.e., $I \subseteq \text{ann } I$). Then $(R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.

2- If $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a ring, then $(R/\text{ann } I, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.

0.6. HOMOMORPHISM OF RING

DEFINITION 0.6.1.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ and $(R', +', \cdot')$ be two rings and the function $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ such that $f(a + b) = f(a) +' f(b)$ and $f(a \cdot b) = f(a) \cdot' f(b), \forall a, b \in R$.

$\therefore f$ is **ring homomorphism**.

DEFINITION 0.6.2.

If f is a ring homomorphism from $(R, +, \cdot)$ into $(R', +', \cdot')$, then **the kernal of f** is the set $\ker f = \{a \in R: f(a) = 0'\}$.

THEOREM 0.6.3.

1- Let f be a ring homomorphism from $(R, +, \cdot)$ into $(R', +', \cdot')$,

f is 1-1 $\Leftrightarrow \ker f = \{0\}$.

2- If f is ring homomorphism from $(R, +, \cdot)$ into $(R', +', \cdot')$. Then the triple $(\ker f, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of R .

DEFINITION 0.6.4.

Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ and $(R', +', \cdot')$ be two any rings. R is said to be **isomorphic** to R'

$(R \cong R') \Leftrightarrow \exists f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot') \exists f$ is 1-1, onto and ring homomorphism.

REMARK 0.6.5.

Let $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be any homomorphism ring.

1) f is called **ring monomorphism** $\Leftrightarrow f$ is 1 - 1.

2) f is called **ring epimorphism** $\Leftrightarrow f$ is onto.

3) f is called **ring isomorphism** $\Leftrightarrow f$ is 1 - 1 and onto.

THEOREM 0.6.6. Let $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be a ring homomorphism. Then

1) $f(0) = 0'$ 2) $f(-a) = -f(a)$

3) If S is a subring of $R \Rightarrow f(S)$ is subring of R' .

4) If I is an ideal of $R \Rightarrow f(I)$ is Ideal of R' .

5) If H is a subring of $R \Rightarrow f^{-1}(H)$ is subring of R .

6) If K is an ideal of $R \Rightarrow f^{-1}(K)$ is ideal of R .

DEFINITION 0.6.7. Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring and I be an ideal of R . Then mapping

$f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R/I, \oplus, \odot)$ which is defined by $f(a) = a + I, \forall a \in R$ is called **natural projection on R/I** , (denoted by nat_I or π).

The First Fundamental Theorem

THEOREM 0.6.8. (Fundamental theorem of homomorphism ring)

Let $f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (R', +', \cdot')$ be a ring homomorphism and onto, then

$$(R/\ker f, \oplus, \odot) \cong (R', +', \cdot')$$

COROLLARY 0.6.9.

Let M, N be to two rings such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +', \cdot')$ be a ring epimorphism. Then $(M/\ker f, \oplus, \odot) \cong (N, +', \cdot')$.

The Second Fundamental Theorem

THEOREM 0.6.10. Let K, L be to two ideals of rings R and N respectively such that

$f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +, \cdot)$ be a ring homomorphism. Then

$$(K/(K \cap L), \oplus, \odot) \cong ((K \cap L) / L, +, \cdot).$$

The Third Fundamental Theorem

THEOREM 0.6.11. Let K, L be to two ideals of rings R and N respectively such that

$f: (R, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +, \cdot)$ be a ring homomorphism such that $K \subseteq L$. Then

$$(R/K / L/K, \oplus, \odot) \cong (R / L, +, \cdot).$$

Chapter One

MODULES

DEFINITION 1.1.1.

Let R be a ring. A left R -module or a left module over R is a set M together with
 (1) a binary operation $+$ on M under which M is an abelian group, and
 (2) a mapping $R \times M \rightarrow M$ (is called a module multiplication) denoted by $r.m \in M$, for all $r \in R$ and for all $m \in M$ which satisfies:-

- (a) $(r + s).m = r.m + s.m$, for all $r, s \in R, m \in M$,
- (b) $(r.s).m = r.(s.m)$, for all $r, s \in R, m \in M$, and
- (c) $r.(m + n) = r.m + r.n$, for all $r \in R, m, n \in M$.

If the ring R has an identity element 1_R and

- (d) $1.m = m$, for all $m \in M$, then M is said to be a unitary left R -module.

REMARK 1.1.2.

The descriptor "left" in the above definition indicates that the ring elements appear on the left. A right R -modules can be defined analogously as follows.

DEFINITION 1.1.3.

Let R be a ring. A right R -module or a right module over R is a set M together with
 (1) a binary operation $+$ on M under which M is an abelian group, and
 (2) a mapping $M \times R \rightarrow M$ (is called a module multiplication) denoted by $m.r \in M$, for all $r \in R$ and for all $m \in M$ which satisfies

- (a) $m.(r + s) = m.r + m.s$, for all $r, s \in R, m \in M$,
- (b) $m.(r.s) = (m.r).s$, for all $r, s \in R, m \in M$, and
- (c) $(m + n).r = m.r + n.r$, for all $r \in R, m, n \in M$.

If the ring R has an identity element 1_R and

- (d) $m.1 = m$, for all $m \in M$, then M is said to be a unitary right R -module.

REMARK 1.1.4.

- 1- The notation ${}_R M$ (resp. M_R) denotes to left (resp. right) R -module M .
- 2- If the ring R is commutative, then a module M is left R -module if and only if it is a right R -module.

DEFINITION 1.1.5.

Let R be a commutative ring with unity. A nonempty set M with two binary operation addition $(+)$ defined on m and scalar multiplication $(.)$. Is called a left R -module (or a right module over R) if and only if, the following are true :-

- 1- $(M,+)$ is an abelian group .
- 2- $(.)$ is a mapping from $R \times M \rightarrow M$ such that $\forall r \in R$ and $r. m \in M$ satisfying
 - i- $(r_1 + r_2) . m = r_1.m + r_2.m, \forall r_1, r_2 \in R, \forall m \in M.$
 - ii- $(r_1 . r_2) . m = r_1.(r_2.m) \quad \forall r_1, r_2 \in R, \forall m \in M.$
 - iii- $r. (m_1 + m_2) = r.m_1 + r.m_2 \quad \forall r \in R, \forall m_1, m_2 \in M.$

REMARK 1.1.6.

- 1- If in addition. $1.m = m, \forall m \in M$, Then M is called a until left R -module .
- 2- If in addition. $m.1 = m, \forall m \in M$, Then M is called a until right R -module .

DEFINITION 1.1.7.

That is an abelian group. $(M, +)$ is called a left R -module $\Leftrightarrow \exists$ a mapping $X: R \times M \rightarrow M$ such that $(r,m) \mapsto r.m, \forall r \in R, \forall m \in M$ satisfying :- $\forall r, r_1, r_2 \in R, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M$

- i- $(r_1 + r_2, m) = (r_1, m) + (r_2, m)$
- ii- $(r_1.r_2, m) = (r_1, (r_2.m))$
- iii- $(r, m_1 + m_2) = (r, m_1) + (r, m_2)$
- iv- $(1, m) = m$

REMARK 1.1.8.

1. The right R -modules are defined similarity.
2. Every properties which hold for left modules are also hold for right modules.
3. Every left R -modules can be consider a right R -module if the ring are commutative .

LEMMA 1.1.9.

Let R be a ring with 1, M be a left R -module and $r, s \in R, m, n \in M$. Then:

- (1) $r . 0_M = 0_M$;
- (2) $0_R . m = 0_M$;
- (3) $(-1).m = -m$;
- (4) $-(r . m) = (-r) . m = r . (-m)$;
- (5) $(r - s) . m = r.m - s.m$;
- (6) $r . (m - n) = r.m - r . n$.

Proof.

- (1) $r . 0_M = r . (0_M + 0_M) = r . 0_M + r . 0_M \Rightarrow r . 0_M + (- (r . 0_M)) = r . 0_M + r . 0_M + (- (r . 0_M)) \Rightarrow 0_M = r . 0_M.$
- (2) $0_R . m = (0_R + 0_R) . m = 0_R . m + 0_R . m \Rightarrow 0_R . m + (- (0_R . m)) = 0_R . m + 0_R . m + (- (0_R . m)) \Rightarrow 0_M = 0_R . m.$
- (3) $0_M = 0_R . m$ (by (2)) = $(1 + (-1)) . m = m + (-1) . m$. Thus $(-1) . m = -m$.
- (4) $-(r . m) = (-1)(r . m)$ (by 3) = $((-1) . r) . m = (-r) . m$. Also, $r . (-m) = r . ((-1) . m)$ (by 3) = $(r . (-1)) . m = (-r) . m$. Thus $-(r . m) = (-r) . m = r . (-m)$.
- (5) $(r - s) . m = (r + (-s)) . m = r . m + (-s) . m = r . m + (- (s . m))$ (by 4) = $r . m - s . m$.
- (6) $r . (m - n) = r . (m + (-n)) = r . m + r . (-n) = r . m + (- (r . n))$ (by 4) = $r . m - r . n$.

EXAMPLES 1.1.10.

1. Every abelian group $(M,+)$ is a module over the ring N (the ring of all integers) .
 - (every abelian group is a N -module) . Define $\alpha : N \times M \rightarrow M$ such that

$$\alpha(n, m) = \underbrace{m + m + \dots + m}_{n \text{ times}} = n.m \in M.$$

Proof :- For all $n, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$, and $m, m_1, m_2 \in M$, such that $\alpha(n, m) = n.m$.

i- $(n_1 + n_2, m) = (n_1 + n_2).m$
 $= m + m + \dots + m + m + m + \dots + m = n_1.m + n_2.m$
 $= (n_1, m) + (n_2, m)$

ii- $(n_1 n_2, m) = (n_1 .n_2).m$ by define of α
 $= m + m + \dots + m = (m + m + \dots + m)$
 $= (m + \dots + m) + \dots + (m + \dots + m)$
 $= n_1 .(m + m + \dots + m)$
 $= n_1 .(n_2 .m)$
 $= (n_1 , n_2 .m)$
 $= (n_1 , (n_2 , m))$

iii- $(n, m_1 + m_2) = n.(m_1 + m_2)$
 $= (m_1 + m_2) + (m_1 + m_2) + \dots + (m_1 + m_2)$ by define of α
 $= m_1 + m_1 + m_1 + \dots + m_1 + m_2 + m_2 + \dots + m_2 = n.m_1 + n.m_2.$
 $= (n .m_1) + (n.m_2) = (n, m) + (n, m).$

iv- $\forall m \in M, (1, m) = 1.m = m.$

$\therefore M$ is until N -module

- $(R, +)$ is an abelian group is a Z -module) Since $(Z, +)$ is an abelian group and define $\alpha : Z \times R \rightarrow R \ni (a, b) = a.b \in R, \forall a, a_1, a_2 \in Z, b, b_1, b_2 \in R.$
 i: $(a_1 + a_2, b) = (a_1 + a_2).b = a_1.b + a_2.b = (a_1, b) + (a_2, b).$
 ii: $(a_1 a_2, b) = (a_1 + a_2).b = a_1.(a_2.b) = (a_1, a_2 b) = (a_1, (a_2, b)).$
 iii : $(a, b_1 + b_2) = a.(b_1 + b_2) = a.b_1 + a.b_2 = (a, b_1) + (a, b_2).$
 $\therefore R$ is a Z -module .
- $(Q, +)$ is abelian group $\Rightarrow Q$ is a Z -module .

EXAMPLES 1.1.11.

Let $M_{2 \times 2} = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}, a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{R} \right\}$ is a module over R , then $M_{2 \times 2}$ is a \mathbb{R} -module since :-

1- $(M_{2 \times 2}, +)$ is an abelian group . $(r, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) \mapsto r. \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in M_{2 \times 2}$

2- \exists a mapping $\alpha: \mathbb{R} \times M_{2 \times 2} \rightarrow M_{2 \times 2}$ such that $(r, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) \mapsto r. \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in M_{2 \times 2}, \forall \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix} \in M_{2 \times 2}, \forall r, r_1, r_2 \in \mathbb{R},$

i- $(r_1 + r_2, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) = (r_1 + r_2). \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = r_1. \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} + r_2. \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = (r_1, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) + (r_2, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}).$

ii- $(r_1.r_2, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) = (r_1.r_2). \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = r_1. (r_2. \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}). = (r_1, (r_2, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix})).$

iii- $(r, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) + (r, \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix}) = r. \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} + r. \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix} = (r, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) + (r, \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix}).$

$$\text{iv- } (1, \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) = 1 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}.$$

$\therefore M_{2 \times 2}$ is a until \mathbb{R} -module.

EXAMPLES 1.1.12.

1- Let $(\mathbb{R}, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring, let $(\mathbb{R}, +) = (M, +) \therefore \mathbb{R}$ is a \mathbb{R} -module.

2- Let $M_{2 \times 2}(\mathbb{Z}) = M$, $(M, +, \cdot)$ is a \mathbb{Z} -module of matrix.

Solution:-

Since $(M, +)$ is an abelian group and define $\alpha : Z \times M \rightarrow M$.

Let $r_1, r_2 \in Z$, $A, B \in M$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i- } (r_1 + r_2) \cdot A &= (r_1 + r_2) \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (r_1 + r_2) \cdot a & (r_1 + r_2) \cdot b \\ (r_1 + r_2) \cdot c & (r_1 + r_2) \cdot d \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot a & r_1 \cdot b \\ r_1 \cdot c & r_1 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} r_2 \cdot a & r_2 \cdot b \\ r_2 \cdot c & r_2 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} = \left(r_1 \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \right) + \left(r_2 \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \right) \\ &= r_1 \cdot A + r_2 \cdot A. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii- } (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot A &= (r_1 \cdot r_2) \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot a & (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot b \\ (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot c & (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot d \end{pmatrix} \\ &= r_1 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} r_2 \cdot a & r_2 \cdot b \\ r_2 \cdot c & r_2 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}) = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot A). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{iii- } r_1 \cdot (A + B) &= r_1 \cdot \left(\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot (a + e) & r_1 \cdot (b + f) \\ r_1 \cdot (c + g) & r_1 \cdot (d + h) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot a & r_1 \cdot b \\ r_1 \cdot c & r_1 \cdot d \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \cdot e & r_1 \cdot f \\ r_1 \cdot g & r_1 \cdot h \end{pmatrix} = \left(r_1 \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \right) + \left(r_1 \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix} \right) \\ &= r_1 \cdot A + r_1 \cdot B. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{iv- If has unity 1, then } 1 \cdot A = A, \quad 1 \cdot A = 1 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = A.$$

$\therefore M_{2 \times 2}$ is a until \mathbb{R} -module.

3- Is $(\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{2}], +, \cdot)$ a until \mathbb{Z} -module?

Solution:-

Since $(\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{2}], +)$ is an abelian group and define $\alpha : Z \times Z[\sqrt{2}] \rightarrow Z[\sqrt{2}]$.

$r_1, r_2 \in Z$, $x = a + b\sqrt{2}$, $y = c + d\sqrt{2}$, $x, y \in Z[\sqrt{2}]$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i- } (r_1 + r_2) \cdot x &= (r_1 + r_2) (a + b\sqrt{2}) = (r_1 + r_2) a + (r_1 + r_2) b\sqrt{2} \\ &= ((r_1 \cdot a) + (r_2 \cdot a)) + ((r_1 \cdot b) + (r_2 \cdot b) \sqrt{2}) = ((r_1 \cdot a) + (r_1 \cdot b) \sqrt{2}) + ((r_2 \cdot a) + (r_2 \cdot b) \sqrt{2}) \\ &= (r_1 \cdot (a + b\sqrt{2})) + (r_2 \cdot (a + b\sqrt{2})) = r_1 \cdot x + r_2 \cdot x. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii- } (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot x &= (r_1 \cdot r_2) (a + b\sqrt{2}) = (r_1 \cdot r_2) a + (r_1 \cdot r_2) b\sqrt{2} \\ &= r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot a) + r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot b) \sqrt{2} = r_1 \cdot ((r_2 \cdot a) + (r_2 \cdot b) \sqrt{2}) \\ &= r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot (a + b\sqrt{2})) = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot x). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{iii- } r_1 \cdot (x + y) &= r_1 \cdot ((a + b\sqrt{2}) + (c + d\sqrt{2})) \\ &= r_1 \cdot (a + b\sqrt{2}) + r_1 \cdot (c + d\sqrt{2}) = r_1 \cdot x + r_1 \cdot y. \end{aligned}$$

iv- If has unity 1, then $1 \cdot x = x$ and $x \cdot 1 = x$,

$$1 \cdot x = 1. (a + b \sqrt{2}) = (1.a + 1.b \sqrt{2}) = (a + b \sqrt{2}) = x, \text{ and}$$

$$x \cdot 1 = (a + b \sqrt{2}) . 1 = (a.1 + b.1 \sqrt{2}) = (a + b \sqrt{2}) = x.$$

$\therefore (Z[\sqrt{2}], +, \cdot)$ is a until Z -module.

4- Is $(Z[\sqrt{2}], +, \cdot)$ a until $Z[\sqrt{2}]$ -module ?

EXAMPLES 1.1.13.

For each positive integer n , Z_n is a Z -module.

Proof :- since $(Z_n, +_n)$ is an abelian group

$$\alpha : Z \times Z_n \rightarrow Z_n \ni (n, a) \mapsto n \cdot_n a \quad \forall n, n_1, n_2 \in Z, \forall a, a_1, a_2 \in Z_n$$

$$\text{i- } (n_1 + n_2, a) = (n_1 + n_2) \cdot_n a = n_{1 \cdot n} a + n_{2 \cdot n} a = (n_1, a) + (n_2, a) .$$

$$\text{ii- } (n_1 n_2, a) = (n_1 \cdot n_2) \cdot_n a = n_1(n_2 \cdot_n a) = (n_1, n_2 \cdot_n a) = (n_1, (n_2, a)) .$$

$$\text{iii- } (n, a_1 +_n a_2) = n \cdot_n (a_1 +_n a_2) = (n \cdot_n a_1) +_n (n \cdot_n a_2) = (n, a_1) +_n (n, a_2) \in Z_n .$$

$\therefore Z_n$ is a Z -module .

EXAMPLES 1.1.14.

Let $K = \text{Map}(X) = \{f \mid f \text{ is a mapping from } X \text{ into } M\}$, where $\emptyset \neq X \subseteq M$, X and M are rings . Define $(+)$ and (\cdot) on K such that $(f+g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ and $(f \cdot g)(m) = f(m) \cdot g(m)$, $\forall f, g \in K, \forall m \in X$.

Then $(K, +, \cdot)$ is a until X -module

Proof:- Let $f, g, h \in K, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in X$ and e is unity of X .

Closure, Since $f : X \rightarrow M$ and $g : X \rightarrow M \Rightarrow f + g : X \rightarrow M$,

Well-defined, $f = f_1$ and $g = g_1, (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = f_1(m) + g_1(m) = (f_1 + g_1)(m)$.

Assuasive, $[(f + g) + h](m) = (f + g)(m) + h(m) = (f(m) + g(m)) + h(m) = f(m) + (g(m) + h(m)) = f(m) + (g + h)(m) = [f + (g + h)](m)$.

Identity, $f(m) = e, (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = e + g(m) = g(m) = g(m) + e = g(m) + f(m) = (g + f)(m)$.

Inverse, $f(m) + f(-m) = f(m - m) = f(e) = e . f(-m) + f(m) = f(-m + m) = f(e) = e . \therefore (-f(m)) = f(-m)$.

Commutative, $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = g(m) + f(m) = (g + f)(m) . \therefore +$ is commutative.

$(K, +)$ is commutative group.

Define $\alpha : X \times H \rightarrow H$ such that $(f, m) \mapsto f(m) \quad \forall f, g \in K, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in X$.

i- $(f + g, m) = (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ by define of $+$ on K . $= (f, m) + (g, m)$ by define of α .

ii- $(f \cdot g, m) = (f \cdot g)(m)$, by define α . $= f(m) \cdot g(m)$, by define of (\cdot) on K . $= (f, m) \cdot (g, m)$

iii- $(f, m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) + f(m_2) = (f, m_1) + (f, m_2)$.

iv- mI is the identity mapping of K and $(mI, m) = mI(m) = m, \forall m \in X$.

$\therefore (K, +, \cdot)$ is a until X -module.

EXAMPLES 1.1.15.

Let $M^* = \text{Map}(M) = \{f \mid f \text{ is a mapping from } M \text{ into } R\}$, where $\emptyset \neq M \subseteq R$, R and M are rings .

Define $(+)$ and (\cdot) on K such that $(f+g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ and $(f \cdot g)(m) = f(m) \cdot g(m)$, $\forall f, g \in K, \forall m \in X$. Then $(M^*, +, \cdot)$ is a until M -module

Proof:- Let $f, g, h \in M^*, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M$ and e is unity of M .

Closure, Since $f : M \rightarrow R$ and $g : M \rightarrow R \Rightarrow f + g : M \rightarrow R$,

Well-defined, $f = f_1$ and $g = g_1, (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = f_1(m) + g_1(m) = (f_1 + g_1)(m)$.

Assuasive , $[(f + g) + h](m) = (f + g)(m) + h(m) = (f(m) + g(m)) + h(m) = f(m) + (g(m) + h(m))$
 $= f(m) + (g + h)(m) = [f + (g + h)](m)$.

Identity , $f(m) = e$, $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = e + g(m) = g(m) = g(m) + e = g(m) + f(m) = (g + f)(m)$.

Inverse , $f(m) + f(-m) = f(m - m) = f(e) = e$. $f(-m) + f(m) = f(-m + m) = f(e) = e$. $\therefore (-f)(m) = f(-m)$.

Commutative , $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = g(m) + f(m) = (g + f)(m)$. $\therefore +$ is commutative.

$(M^*, +)$ is commutative group.

Define α : $M \times M^* \rightarrow M^*$ such that $(f, m) \mapsto f(m) \quad \forall f, g \in M^*, \quad \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M$.

i- $(f + g, m) = (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ by define of $+$ on M^* . $= (f, m) + (g, m)$ by define of α .

ii- $(f \cdot g, m) = (f \cdot g)(m)$, by define α . $= f(m) \cdot g(m)$, by define of (\cdot) on M^* . $= (f, m) \cdot (g, m)$

iii- $(f, m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) + f(m_2) = (f, m_1) + (f, m_2)$.

iv- mI is the identity mapping of M^* and $(mI, m) = mI(m) = m, \quad \forall m \in M$.

$\therefore (M^*, +, \cdot)$ is a until M -module.

EXAMPLES 1.1.16.

Let $(M, +)$ be an commutative group and let $H = \text{Hom}(M) = \{f \mid f: M \rightarrow M \text{ is a group homomorphism}\}$.

Define $(+)$ and (\circ) on H such that $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ and $f \circ g(m) = f(g(m)) \quad \forall f, g \in H,$
 $\forall m \in M$. Then $(H, +, \circ)$ is an until M -module.

Proof:- Let $f, g, h \in H, \quad \forall m, m_1, m_2, m^{-1} \in M$ and e is unity of M .

Closure, Since $f: M \rightarrow M$ is homomorphism and $g: M \rightarrow M$ is homomorphism $f + g: M \rightarrow M$ homomorphism, where $(f + g)(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1 + m_2) + g(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) + f(m_2) + g(m_1) + g(m_2)$
 $= f(m_1) + g(m_1) + f(m_2) + g(m_2) = (f + g)(m_1) + (f + g)(m_2)$. $\therefore f + g: M \rightarrow M$ is homomorphism.

Well-defined, $f = f_1$ and $g = g_1$, $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = f_1(m) + g_1(m) = (f_1 + g_1)(m)$.

Assuasive , $[(f + g) + h](m) = (f + g)(m) + h(m) = (f(m) + g(m)) + h(m) = f(m) + (g(m) + h(m))$
 $= f(m) + (g + h)(m) = (f + (g + h))(m)$.

Identity , $f(m) = e$, $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = e + g(m) = g(m)$ and
 $g(m) = g(m) + e = g(m) + f(m) = (g + f)(m)$.

Inverse, $f(m) + f(m^{-1}) = f(m + m^{-1}) = f(e) = e$. $f(m^{-1}) + f(m) = f(m^{-1} + m) = f(e) = e$. $\therefore (f(m))^{-1} = f(m^{-1})$.

Commutative, $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = g(m) + f(m)$, since $(M, +)$ is commutative group
 $= (g + f)(m)$. $\therefore +$ is commutative.

$(H, +)$ is commutative group.

Define α : $M \times H \rightarrow H$ such that $(f, m) \mapsto f(m)$. $\forall f, g \in H, \quad \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M$.

i- $(f + g, m) = (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ by define of $+$ on H . $= (f, m) + (g, m)$ by define of α .

ii- $(f \circ g, m) = (f \circ g)(m)$ by define α . $= f(g(m))$ by define of $+$ on H . $= (f, g(m)) = (f, (g, m))$

iii- $(f, m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) + f(m_2) = (f, m_1) + (f, m_2)$

iv- mI is the identity mapping of H and $(mI, m) = mI(m) = m, \quad \forall m \in M$.

$\therefore (H, +, \cdot)$ is a until M -module .

EXAMPLES 1.1.17.

Let $(M, *)$ be an commutative group and let $H = \text{Hom}(M, N) = \{f \mid f: M \rightarrow N \text{ is a group homomorphism}\}$. Define $(+)$ and (\circ) on H such that $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ and

$f \circ g(m) = f(g(m)) \forall f, g \in H, \forall m \in M$. Then $(H, +, \circ)$ is an until M -module.

Proof:- Let $f, g, h \in H, \forall m, m_1, m_2, m^{-1} \in M$ and e is unity of M .

Closure, Since $f: M \rightarrow N$ is homomorphism and $g: M \rightarrow N$ is homomorphism

$f + g: M \rightarrow N$ homomorphism, where

$$(f + g)(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1 + m_2) + g(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) + f(m_2) + g(m_1) + g(m_2) \\ = f(m_1) + g(m_1) + f(m_2) + g(m_2) = (f + g)(m_1) + (f + g)(m_2). \therefore f + g: M \rightarrow N \text{ is homomorphism.}$$

Well-defined, $f = f_1$ and $g = g_1, (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = f_1(m) + g_1(m) = (f_1 + g_1)(m)$.

Assuasive, $((f + g) + h)(m) = (f + g)(m) + h(m) = (f(m) + g(m)) + h(m) = f(m) + (g(m) + h(m)) \\ = f(m) + (g + h)(m) = (f + (g + h))(m).$

Identity, $f(m) = e, (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = e + g(m) = g(m)$ and $g(m) = g(m) + e = g(m) + f(m) = (g + f)(m).$

Inverse, $f(m) + f(m^{-1}) = f(m + m^{-1}) = f(e) = e. f(m^{-1}) + f(m) = f(m^{-1} + m) = f(e) = e. \therefore (f(m))^{-1} = f(m^{-1}).$

Commutative, $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = g(m) + f(m)$, since $(M, +)$ is commutative group $= (g + f)(m). \therefore +$ is commutative.

$(H, +)$ is commutative group.

Define $\alpha: M \times H \rightarrow H$ such that $(f, m) \mapsto f(m). \forall f, g \in H, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M.$

i- $(f + g, m) = (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ by define of $+$ on $H. = (f, m) + (g, m)$ by define of $\alpha.$

ii- $(f \circ g, m) = (f \circ g)(m)$ by define $\alpha. = f(g(m))$ by define of $+$ on $H. = (f, g(m)) = (f, (g, m))$

iii- $(f, m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) * f(m_2) = (f, m_1) + (f, m_2)$

iv- $M I$ is the identity mapping of H and $(M I, m) = M I(m) = m, \forall m \in M.$

$\therefore (H, +, \cdot)$ is a until M -module.

PROPOSITION 1.1.18.

Every left ideal $(I, +, \cdot)$ of a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a left unite R -module.

Proof:- Let $r, r_1, r_2 \in R$ and $a, a_1, a_2 \in I$. Since $(I, +)$ is an abelian group and $r \cdot a \in I, \forall r \in R, \forall a \in I,$

Define $\alpha: R \times I \rightarrow I \ni (r, a) \rightarrow r \cdot a \in I \forall r \in R, \forall a \in I,$ satisfying :-

i- $(r_1 + r_2, a) = (r_1 + r_2) \cdot a = r_1 \cdot a + r_2 \cdot a = (r_1, a) + (r_2, a).$

ii- $(r_1 r_2, a) = (r_1 r_2) \cdot a = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot a) = (r_1, a) \cdot (r_2, a) = (r_1, (r_2, a)).$

iii- $(r, a_1 + a_2) = r \cdot (a_1 + a_2) = r \cdot a_1 + r \cdot a_2 = (r, a_1) + (r, a_2).$

iv- $(1, a) = 1 \cdot a = a.$

$\therefore I$ is an unite R -module.

REMARK 1.1.19.

Every right ideal $(I, +, \cdot)$ of a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a right unite R -module.

Proof. (H.W).

PROPOSITION 1.1.20.

Every ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a left and right R -module.

Proof.

Since $(R, +, \cdot)$ is an ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$ it follows that $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a left and right ideal of $(R, +, \cdot)$. R is a left and right R -module.

PROPOSITION 1.1.21.

Let I be a left ideal in a ring R and let $R/I = \{a+I : a \in R\}$. R/I is an unital R -module.

Proof:- Let $r, r_1, r_2 \in R, a+I, b+I \in R/I$.

Since $(R/I, \oplus)$ is an abelian group, where \oplus is defined on R/I by :

$(a+I) \oplus (b+I) = (a+b)+I, \forall a, b \in R$. Define $\alpha: R \times (R/I) \rightarrow R/I$ such that $(r, a+I) \rightarrow r.a+I$

i: $(r_1+r_2, a+I) = (r_1+r_2).a+I = (r_1.a+r_2.a)+I = (r_1.a+I) \oplus (r_2.a+I)$.

ii: $(r_1 r_2, a+I) = (r_1 r_2).a+I = r_1.(r_2.a)+I = (r_1, r_2.a+I) = (r_1, (r_2.a+I))$.

iii : $(r, (a+I) \oplus (b+I)) = (r, (a+b)+I)$ by define of \oplus . $= r.(a+b)+I$ by define of α .

$= (r.a+r.b)+I = r.a+I \oplus r.b+I = (r, a+I) \oplus (r, b+I) \in R/I$.

iv: $(1, a+I) = 1.a+I = a+I$. Hence R/I is an unital R -module.

REMARK 1.1.22.

For each positive integer $n, Z/(n) \cong Z_n$ is Z -module $Z/(2) \cong Z_2, Z/(3) \cong Z_3$.

Example: Let $(Z, +, \cdot)$ be a ring, and $(n) = \{n.k : k \in Z\}$ be an ideal of Z , then $Z/(n) \cong Z_n$.

PROPOSITION 1.1.23.

Every left R -module can be considered as a right R -module (that mean $(r, m) = (m, r)$).

Proof:-

Let M be an abelian group and \exists a mapping $\alpha: R \times M \rightarrow M \ni (r, m) \rightarrow r.m, \forall r \in R, \forall m \in M$ and

(i)-(iv) are true. $\forall r, r_1, r_2 \in R$ and $m, m_1, m_2 \in M$. Define $\beta: M \times R \rightarrow M$ such that $(m, r) \rightarrow r.m = (r, m)$

i- $(m_1+m_2, r) = r.(m_1+m_2) = r.m_1+r.m_2$, since M is a left R -module. $= (m_1, r) + (m_2, r)$

ii- $(m, r_1 r_2) \stackrel{?}{=} ((m, r_1), r_2)$

$(r_1 r_2).m = (r_2 r_1).m$, since R is commutative. $= r_2.(r_1.m)$, since M is a left R -module.

$= (r_1.m, r_2) = ((m, r_1), r_2)$.

iii- $(m, r_1+r_2) = (r_1+r_2).m = r_1.m + r_2.m$

$\therefore M$ is a right R -module.

PROPOSITION 1.1.24.

Let R and S be two rings and let $f: S \rightarrow R$ be a ring homomorphism. If M is an unital S -module the M can be considered as an unital R -module.

Proof:-

Since M is an S -module, then $(M, +)$ is an abelian group and \exists a map. $\alpha: S \times M \rightarrow M$ satisfying (i-iv).

$\forall r, r_1, r_2 \in R$, and $m, m_1, m_2 \in M$. Define $\beta: R \times M \rightarrow M$ such that $(r, m) \rightarrow f(r).m \in M$, since

$f(r) \in S$ and M is an unital S -module. $\forall r, r_1, r_2 \in R, m, m_1, m_2 \in M$

i: $(r_1+r_2, m) = f(r_1+r_2).m = (f(r_1)+f(r_2)).m = f(r_1).m + f(r_2).m = (r_1, m) + (r_2, m)$.

ii: $(r_1 r_2, m) = (f(r_1 r_2)).m = f(r_1).(f(r_2).m) = (r_1, f(r_2).m) = (r_1, (r_2, m))$.

iii: $(r, m_1+m_2) = f(r).(m_1+m_2) = f(r).m_1 + f(r).m_2 = (r, m_1) + (r, m_2)$, since f is homomorphism.

iv: $(1, m) = f(1).m = 1.m = m$.

$\therefore M$ is an unital R -module

PROPOSITION 1.1.25.

Every vector space is a module over a field that is if V is a vector space over a field F , then V is an unital F -module (since every field is a ring)

Proof. Since

1- $(V, +)$ is an abelian group .

2- \exists a mapping $\alpha : F \times V \rightarrow V$ such that $(a, v) \rightarrow a.v \in V$ and $a, a_1, a_2 \in F, \forall v, v_1, v_2 \in V,$

i: $(a_1 + a_2).v = (a_1 + a_2).v = a_1.v + a_2.v = (a_1.v) + (a_2.v).$

ii: $(a_1 a_2).v = (a_1 a_2).v = a_1.(a_2.v) = (a_1.(a_2.v)).$

iii: $(a, v_1 + v_2) = a.(v_1 + v_2) = a.v_1 + a.v_2 = (a.v_1) + (a.v_2).$

iv: $(1, v) = 1.v = v.$

$\therefore V$ is an until F -module

LEMMA 1.1.26.

A- Modules over a field F is the same modules.

Proof. By the definition of modules over a field F . (H.W).

B- Every ring R can be considered as a left module over itself (that is R is a R -module).

Proof. (H.W).

PROPOSITION 1.1.25.

If M is a unitary left \mathcal{R} -module and S is a subring of \mathcal{R} with $s1 = r1$, then M is a unitary left S -module as well. For instance the field \mathcal{R} is, a Z -module, a Q -module and a \mathcal{R} -module.

Proof.

Since M is a unitary left \mathcal{R} -module, $(M, +)$ is an abelian group and there is a module multiplication $\bullet : \mathcal{R} \times M \rightarrow M$ with $r1 \bullet m = m$. Define $* : S \times M \rightarrow M$ by $s * m = s \bullet m$, for all $s \in S$ and $m \in M$.

It is clear that $*$ is a module multiplication. Thus M is a left S -module. Since $s1 = r1$ it follows that $s1 * m = r1 \bullet m = m$ and hence M is a unitary left S -module.

REMARK 1.1.26.

Every abelian group of Z is Z -module.

Proof.

Let M be any abelian group, let $a \in M$ and let $n \in Z$. Define the multiplication $\pi : Z \times M \rightarrow M$ such that $\pi(a) = n.a, a \in M$ as follows:

If $n > 0$, then $n.a = \underbrace{a + a + \dots + a}_{n \text{ times}};$

If $n = 0$, then $na = 0$;

If $n < 0$, then $na = -((-n)a) = \underbrace{-a - a - \dots - a}_{|n| \text{ times}}.$

Let $n, m \in Z$ and let $a \in M$, thus

$$(n+m)a = \underbrace{a + a + \dots + a}_{n+m \text{ times}} = \underbrace{a + a + \dots + a}_{n \text{ times}} + \underbrace{a + a + \dots + a}_{m \text{ times}} = n.a + m.a.$$

Also, $(nm)a = \underbrace{a + a + \dots + a}_{nm \text{ times}}$

$$= \underbrace{a + a + \dots + a}_{m \text{ times}} + \underbrace{a + a + \dots + a}_{m \text{ times}} + \dots + \underbrace{a + a + \dots + a}_{m \text{ times}}$$

$$\xrightarrow{\hspace{10em} n \text{ time} \hspace{10em}}$$

$$= \underbrace{m.a + m.a + \dots + m.a}_{n \text{ times}} = n.(m.a).$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } n \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ and let } a, b \in M, \text{ thus } n.(a+b) &= \underbrace{(a+b) + (a+b) + \dots + (a+b)}_{n \text{ times}} \\ &= \underbrace{a+a+\dots+a}_{n \text{ times}} + \underbrace{b+b+\dots+b}_{n \text{ times}} = n.a + n.b. \end{aligned}$$

Thus M is a \mathbb{Z} -module. Since $1.a = a$, it follows that M is a unitary \mathbb{Z} -module.

EXAMPLE 1.1.27.

Let R be a ring with unite 1 and let $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Define

$R_1 \times \dots \times R_n = R^n = \{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \mid a_i \in R, \text{ for all } i\}$. Make R^n into a left R -module by componentwise addition and multiplication by elements of R as follows:

$$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) + (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n) = (a_1 + b_1, a_2 + b_2, \dots, a_n + b_n) \text{ and}$$

$$r.(a_1, \dots, a_n) = (r.a_1, \dots, r.a_n), \text{ for all } r \in R \text{ and } (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n), (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n) \in R^n.$$

Proof. H.W.

EXAMPLE 1.1.28.

If $M_n(R)$ is the set of $n \times n$ matrices over a ring R , then $M_n(R)$ is an additive abelian group under matrix addition. If $A = (a_{ij})_{n \times n} \in M_n(R)$ and $r \in R$, then the operation $r.A = r.(a_{ij})_{n \times n} = (r.a_{ij})_{n \times n}$ makes $M_n(R)$ into a left R -module. $M_n(R)$ is also a right R -module under the operation

$$A.r = (a_{ij})_{n \times n}.r = (a_{ij}.r)_{n \times n}.$$

Proof. H.W.

DEFINITION 1.1.29.

Let M be a R -module, the annihilator of M in R is denoted by $\text{ann}_R(M)$ (or $\text{ann}(M)$) it is defined to the set $\text{ann}_R(M) = \{r \in R \mid r.m = 0_M, \forall m \in M\}$.

EXAMPLES 1.1.30.

1- Prove that $\text{ann}_R(M)$ is an ideal in R .

Proof :- $\text{ann}_R(M) \neq \emptyset$ since $\exists 0_R \in R$ and $0_R.m = 0_M$, and $\text{ann}_R(M) \subseteq R$.

1) Let $r_1, r_2 \in \text{ann}_R(M)$, to proof $r_1 - r_2 \in \text{ann}_R(M)$, to proof $(r_1 - r_2).m = 0_M, \forall m \in M$.

$$(r_1 - r_2).m = (r_1 + (-r_2)).m = r_1.m + (-r_2).m = r_1.m + r_2.(-m) = 0_M + 0_M = 0_M.$$

$$\Rightarrow (r_1 - r_2).m = 0_M, \forall m \in M. \therefore r_1 - r_2 \in \text{ann}_R(M)$$

2) Let $r \in R$ and $r_1 \in \text{ann}_R(M)$, to proof $r.r_1 \in \text{ann}_R(M), \forall r \in R, \forall r_1 \in \text{ann}_R(M)$, to proof

$$((r.r_1).m) = 0_M, \text{ and } (m.(r.r_1)) = 0_M \forall m \in M.$$

$$(r.r_1).m = r.(r_1.m) = r.0_M = 0_M \Rightarrow (r.r_1).m = 0_M \Rightarrow r.r_1 \in \text{ann}_R(M)$$

$$m.(r.r_1) = (m.r_1).r = 0_M.r = 0_M \Rightarrow m.(r.r_1) = 0_M \Rightarrow r.r_1 \in \text{ann}_R(M). \therefore \text{ann}_R(M) \text{ is an ideal in } R.$$

2- Prove that $\text{ann}_R(M)$ is an until R -module.

Proof :- Since

1- $(\text{ann}_R(M), +)$ is an abelian group .

2- \exists a mapping $\alpha : R \times \text{ann}_R(M) \rightarrow \text{ann}_R(M)$ such that $(a, r) \rightarrow a.r \in \text{ann}_R(M)$ and $a, a_1, a_2 \in R$,

$$\forall r, r_1, r_2 \in \text{ann}_R(M),$$

$$\text{i: } (a_1 + a_2).r = (a_1 + a_2).r = a_1.r + a_2.r = (a_1.r) + (a_2.r).$$

$$\text{ii: } (a_1 a_2).r = (a_1 a_2).r = a_1.(a_2.r) = (a_1.(a_2.r)).$$

$$\text{iii: } (a, r_1 + r_2) = a.(r_1 + r_2) = a.r_1 + a.r_2 = (a.r_1) + (a.r_2).$$

$$iv: (1, r) = 1 \cdot r = r.$$

$\therefore \text{ann}_R(M)$ is an until R -module

REMARK 1.1.31.

If M is a R -module and since $\text{ann}(M)$ is ideal $\Rightarrow \text{ann}(M)$ is a R -module by (1.1.30(1))
 $\Rightarrow R/\text{ann}(M)$ is a R -module by proposition (1.1.20).

DEFINITION 1.1.32.

A R -module M is called faithful R -module M if and only if, $\text{ann}_R(M) = \langle 0 \rangle$.

EXAMPLES 1.1.33.

1- Let Z be a ring, let $\langle 5 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z \Rightarrow (Z/\langle 5 \rangle, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.

$\Rightarrow (Z/\langle 5 \rangle, \oplus)$ is commutative group and $Z/\langle 5 \rangle \cong Z_5$.

From (1.1.30) $\Rightarrow Z_5$ is an Z -module and $\text{ann}_Z(Z_5) = \{n \in Z: n \cdot m = z_5 0, \forall m \in Z_5\} = \langle 5 \rangle = \{5k : k \in Z\}$.

$\Rightarrow \langle 5 \rangle$ is not faithful.

In general, $\text{ann}_Z(Z_n) = \langle n \rangle = \{n \in Z: n \cdot m = z_n 0, \forall m \in Z_n\} = \langle n \rangle = \{nk : k \in Z\} \Rightarrow \langle n \rangle$ is not faithful.

2- Let Z be a ring, let $\langle 2 \rangle$ be an ideal of $Z \Rightarrow (Z/\langle 2 \rangle, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring.

$\Rightarrow (Z/\langle 2 \rangle, \oplus)$ is commutative group and $Z/\langle 2 \rangle \cong Z_2$.

From (1.1.30) $\Rightarrow Z_2$ is an Z -module and $\text{ann}_Z(\langle 2 \rangle) = \langle 2 \rangle = \{n \in Z: n \cdot m = z_2 0, \forall m \in \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 0 \rangle$

$\Rightarrow \langle 2 \rangle$ is a faithful.

PROPOSITION 1.1.34.

Let M be a R -module and I be an ideal of R which contained I in $\text{ann}(M)$ (i.e., $I \subseteq \text{ann}(M)$). Then M is an unite R/I -module.

Proof :- the answer by first step :-

Since M is a R -module $\Rightarrow (M, +)$ is an abelian group and \exists a map $\alpha : R \times M \rightarrow M$ such that $(r, m) \rightarrow r \cdot m \in M, \forall r \in R$ and $\forall m \in M$.

Define $\beta: R/I \times M \rightarrow M$ such that $(r+I, m) \rightarrow r \cdot m \in M, \forall r \in R, \forall m \in M$.

To proof β is a mapping, we have to show that β is a well-defined

Let $(r_1+I, m_1) = (r_2+I, m_2) \therefore r_1+I = r_2+I$ and $m_1 = m_2 \Rightarrow r_1 - r_2 \in I$. But $I \subseteq \text{ann}(M)$

$\Rightarrow r_1 - r_2 \in \text{ann}(M) \therefore (r_1 - r_2) \cdot m = 0_M, \forall m \in M$ (by define of $\text{ann}(M)$)

$\therefore r_1 m - r_2 m = 0_M$ (since $r_1, r_2 \in R, m \in M$ and M is a R -module)

$\therefore \beta(r_1+I, m) = \beta(r_2+I, m)$

Satisfying (i) - (iv), on $\beta, \forall r, r_1, r_2 \in R$ and $\forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M$

$$i: (r_1+I \oplus r_2+I, m) = ((r_1+r_2)+I, m) = (r_1+r_2) \cdot m = r_1 \cdot m + r_2 \cdot m = (r_1+I, m) + (r_2+I, m)$$

$$ii: (r_1 r_2+I, m) = (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot m = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot m) = (r_1+I, r_2 \cdot m) = (r_1+I, (r_2+I, m))$$

$$iii: (r+I, m_1 + m_2) = r \cdot (m_1 + m_2) = r \cdot m_1 + r \cdot m_2 = (r+I, m_1) + (r+I, m_2)$$

$$iv: (1+I, m) = (1) \cdot m = m.$$

$\therefore M$ is an unite R/I -module.

COROLLARY 1.1.35.

If M is a R -module, then M is an unite $R/\text{ann}(M)$ -module

Proof:- $I=\text{ann}(M)$, since $\text{ann}(M)$ is an ideal in R . Defined $\beta: (R/\text{ann}(M)) \times M \rightarrow M$ such that $(r+\text{ann}(M), m) \rightarrow r.m \Rightarrow M$ is an unite $R/\text{ann}(M)$ -module .

SUBMODULES

DEFINITION 1.2.1.

Let M and N be R -modules such that $N \subseteq M$. N is called a **R-submodule of M** (or a **submodule of M**) .

DEFINITION 1.2.2.

Let R be a ring and let M be a left R -module. A **left R-submodule of M** is a subgroup N of M such that $r \bullet n \in N$, for all $r \in R$, and for all $n \in N$, where \bullet is the module multiplication defined on M . We will use $N \hookrightarrow M$ to denote that N is a submodule of M .

REMARK 1.2.3.

A right R -modules can be defined analogously as follows.

DEFINITION 1.2.4.

Let R be a commutative ring and let M be a R -module. A **R-submodule of M** is a subgroup N of M such that $r \bullet n \in N$, for all $r \in R$, and for all $n \in N$, where \bullet is the module multiplication defined on M . We will use $N \hookrightarrow M$ to denote that N is a submodule of M .

REMARK 1.2.5.

If the ring R is commutative, then a module M is left R -submodule if and only if it is a right R -submodule.

EQUIVALENT 1.2.6.

If M is a R -module and $\emptyset \neq N \subseteq M$, then N is a submodule of M if and only if ,

- 1) $(N, +)$ is a subgroup of $(M, +)$.
- 2) $r.n \in N, \forall r \in R$ (i.e. $r.n \in N, \forall r \in R, \forall n \in N$).

EQUIVALENT 1.2.7.

If M is a R -module and $\emptyset \neq N \subseteq M$, then N is a submodule of M if and only if ,

- 1) $a - b \in N, \forall a, b \in N$.
- 2) $r.a \in N, \forall r \in R, \forall a \in N$.

THEOREM 1.2.8.

The definition (1.2.1) and the equivalents ((1.2.6) , (1.2.7)) are equivalently.

Proof:-

- 1- The definition (1.2.1) \Leftrightarrow the definition (1.2.6) ,
a- definition (1.2.1) \Rightarrow the equivalent (1.2.6) ,

From definition (1.2.1) $\Rightarrow M$ is a R -module and $\emptyset \neq N \subseteq M$, since N is itself a R -module with respect of the operations for $M \Rightarrow (N, +)$ is an abelian group.

$\therefore N \subseteq M \Rightarrow (n, +)$ is a subgroup of $(M, +)$. and \exists a map $\beta: R \times N \rightarrow N \ni (r, n) = r.n, \forall r \in R, \forall n \in N$.
(i.e. $r.N \subseteq N, \forall r \in R$). \therefore the equivalent (1.2.6) is true.

b- The equivalent (1.2.6) \Rightarrow definition (1.2.1) .

From definition (1.2.1) $\Rightarrow M$ is a R -module and $\emptyset \neq N \subseteq M$. To proof N is R -submodule of M .

i. e. To proof N is itself R -module with respect of the operations for M .

From (1) of equivalent (1.2.6), $(N, +)$ is subgroup of $(M, +) \Rightarrow (N, +)$ is an abelian group (since $(M, +)$ is an abelian group).

From (2) of equivalent (1.2.6), since $r.N \subseteq N, \forall r \in R$, so we can define $\alpha : R \times N \rightarrow N$ such that $(r, n) \rightarrow r.n, \forall r \in R, \forall n \in N$.

To proof α satisfying (i)-(iv)

i - Let $r_1, r_2 \in R, n \in N$,

$$\begin{aligned} (r_1 + r_2, n) &= (r_1 + r_2).n \text{ (by define of } \alpha \text{)} \\ &= r_1.n + r_2.n \text{ (since } r_1, r_2 \in R, n \in N \subseteq M \Rightarrow n \in M \text{ and } M \text{ is a } R\text{-module)} \\ &= (r_1, n) + (r_2, n) \end{aligned}$$

ii- Let $r_1, r_2 \in R, n \in N$,

$$\begin{aligned} (r_1.r_2, n) &= (r_1.r_2).n \text{ (by define of } \alpha \text{)} \\ &= r_1.(r_2.n) \text{ (since } r_1 + r_2 \in R, n \in N \subseteq M \Rightarrow n \in M \text{ and } M \text{ is a } R\text{-module)} \\ &= (r_1, r_2.n) \\ &= (r_1, (r_2, n)) \end{aligned}$$

iii- Let $r \in R, n_1, n_2 \in N$,

$$\begin{aligned} (r, n_1 + n_2) &= r.(n_1 + n_2) \text{ (by define of } \alpha \text{)} \\ &= r.n_1 + r.n_2 \text{ (since } r \in R, n_1, n_2 \in N \subseteq M \Rightarrow n_1, n_2 \in M \text{ and } M \text{ is a } R\text{-module)} \\ &= (r, n_1) + (r, n_2) \end{aligned}$$

iv- Let 1 be an identity element of $R \Rightarrow \forall n \in N \Rightarrow (1, n) = 1.n = n \therefore N$ is a unital R -module.

$\therefore N$ is an unital R -submodule of M .

2- The definition (1.2.6) \Leftrightarrow the definition (1.2.7) ,

The equivalent (1.2.6) \Rightarrow the equivalent (1.2.7) ,

(\Rightarrow) Suppose define (1.2.6) , to proof define (1.2.7)

From equivalent (1.2.6) \Rightarrow Let M be a R -module and $\emptyset \neq N \subseteq M$.

From (1) of equivalent (1.2.6), $\therefore (N, +)$ is subgroup of $(M, +) \Rightarrow (N, +)$ is a group $\Rightarrow +$ is closed on N .

(i.e. $a - b \in N, \forall a, b \in N \dots \dots (1)$)

From (2) of equivalent (1.2.6), $\therefore r.a \in N, \forall r \in R, \forall a \in N \Rightarrow r.N \subseteq N \dots \dots (2)$

From (1) and (2) \Rightarrow the equivalent (1.2.7) is hold.

The equivalent (1.2.7) \Rightarrow the equivalent (1.2.6) ,

From equivalent (1.2.7), let M is a R -module and $\emptyset \neq N \subseteq M$.

To proof $(N, +)$ is a subgroup of $(M, +)$, i.e. to proof $a + b \in N, \forall a, b \in N$ and $\forall a \in N \exists -a \in N$ such that $a + (-a) = 0$

From (1) of equivalent (1.2.7) $\Rightarrow a + b \in N, \forall a, b \in N$.

From (2) of equivalent (1.2.7), $-1 \in R \Rightarrow (-1) \cdot a \in N, \forall a \in N \Rightarrow (-1) \cdot a = 1 \cdot (-a) = -a \in N$

$\therefore a + (-a) = 0 \Rightarrow -a$ is an additive inverse of a . $\therefore \forall a \in N, \exists -a \in N$ such that $a + (-a) = 0$.

$\therefore (N, +)$ is a subgroup of $(M, +)$ (1).

From (2) of equivalent (1.2.7), $r \cdot a \in N, \forall r \in R, \forall a \in N \Rightarrow r \cdot N \subseteq N, \forall r \in R$ (2).

From (1) and (2) \Rightarrow equivalent (1.2.6) hold .

EXAMPLES 1.2.9.

1) For any R -module M , there is at least two submodules since $\{0\}$ is a submodule of M and M is a submodule of M . $\{0\}$ and M are called **the trivial submodules of M** .

2) If there is any other submodule N of M such that $\{0\} \subsetneq N \subsetneq M$, then N is called a **proper submodules of M** .

3) For each positive integer n , $n\mathbb{Z}$ is a submodules of \mathbb{Z} as a \mathbb{Z} -modules.

4) If R is a ring , consider R as a R -module , the submodules of R are just the ideals of R .

EXAMPLE 1.2.10.

Every left R -module M contains at least two submodules are $M \hookrightarrow M$ and $\{0\} \hookrightarrow M$.

Proof. H.W.

PROPOSITION 1.2.11.

Let R be a ring, let M be a left R -module and let N be a nonempty subset of M . Then the following statements are equivalent:

(1) N is a left submodule of M ;

(2) For all $a, b \in N$ and for all $r \in R$ we have that:

(i) $a - b \in N$ and

(ii) $r \cdot a \in N$, where \cdot is the module multiplication defined on M ;

(3) $r \cdot a - s \cdot b \in N$, for all $a, b \in N$ and for all $r, s \in R$.

Proof. H.W.

PROPOSITION 1.2.12.

Let R be a ring, let M be a left R -module and let N be a subset of M . Then N is a left submodule of M if and only if $(N, +)$ is a left R -module with the same addition and module multiplication on M .

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that N is a left submodule of M . Thus (by Definition 1.2.1) we have that N is a subgroup of $(M, +)$ such that $r \cdot n \in N$, for all $r \in R, n \in N$, where \cdot is the module multiplication defined $*: R \times N \rightarrow N$ by $r * n = r \cdot n$, for all $r \in R, n \in N$. It is **easy to check that** $*$ is a module multiplication (**H.W.**).

Thus $(N, +)$ is a left R -module with the same addition and module multiplication on M .

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that $(N, +)$ is a left R -module with the same addition and module multiplication on M . Thus $(N, +)$ is an abelian group and the multiplication $*: R \times N \rightarrow N$ defined by $r * n = r \cdot n$, for all $r \in R, n \in N$ is a module multiplication. Since N is a subset of M it follows that $(N, +)$ is a subgroup of $(M, +)$.

Let $r \in R$ and let $n \in N$, thus $r \cdot n = r * n \in N$. By definition (1.2.1), N is a left submodule of M .

PROPOSITION 1.2.13.

Let R be a ring with unit 1 . Then the left submodules of R as a left R -module are exactly the left ideals of a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$.

Proof.

Let $(I, +, \cdot)$ be a left ideal of a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$. By Proposition (1.1.16), I is a left R -module with the same addition and module multiplication on ${}_R R$. Since I is a subset of R it follows from Proposition (1.2.12), that I is a left submodule of a left R -module. Hence every left ideal of a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a submodules of R as a left R -module.

Suppose that N is a left submodules of R as a left R -module. By Proposition (1.2.11), we have that $a - b \in N$ and $r \cdot a \in N$ for all $a, b \in N$ and for all $r \in R$, where \cdot is the module multiplication defined on R . Thus N is a left ideal of a ring R . Therefore, the left submodules of R as a left R -module are exactly the left ideals of a ring $(R, +, \cdot)$.

EXERCISE 1.2.14.

Find all left submodules of the following left R -modules:

- (1) ${}_Z Z$; (2) ${}_F F$, where F is a field; (3) ${}_R R$; (4) Z_p as a left Z_p -module, where p is a prime number; (5) Z_6 as a left Z_6 -module.

PROPOSITION 1.2.15.

Let F be a field and let M be a left F -module. Then the left submodules of a left F -module are exactly the subspaces of a F -vector space.

Proof.

Since F is a field it follows from the definitions of submodules and subspaces that there is no difference between subspaces and submodules of a left F -module.

PROPOSITION 1.2.16.

Let M be a left Z -module. Then the left submodules of a left Z -module are exactly the subgroups of an abelian group.

Proof.

Let N be a subgroup of an abelian group M , thus N is an abelian group with the same addition of a group M . By Remark (1.1.28), N is a Z -module with the same module multiplication on M and hence by Proposition (1.2.12), we have that N is a left submodules of a left Z -module M . Thus every subgroups of an abelian group M is a left submodules of a left Z -module M .

Let K be a left submodule of a left Z -module M . By Proposition (1.2.12), K is a left Z -module and hence $(K, +)$ is a group. Since K is a subset of M it follows that K is a subgroup of M . Hence the left submodules of a left Z -module M are exactly the subgroups of an abelian group M .

DEFINITION 1.2.17.

a non-zero R -module M is called **simple R -module M** if M has no proper submodules .

EXAMPLES 1.2.18.

- 1- For each prime number p , Z_p is a simple Z -module.
- 2- As Z_3 is a simple Z -module and Z_4 is not simple Z -module.

PROPOSITION 1.2.19.

Let M be a left R -module and let N_1 and N_2 be two left submodules of M .

Define $N_1 + N_2 = \{y \in M \mid y = a + b \text{ with } a \in N_1 \text{ and } b \in N_2\}$. Then $N_1 + N_2$ is left submodule of M .

Proof.

We will prove that $N_1 + N_2$ is a submodule of M . Since N_1 and N_2 are subgroups of an abelian group M it follows that N_1 and N_2 contain 0 and hence $0 = 0 + 0 \in N_1 + N_2$.

Thus $N_1 + N_2$ is a nonempty subset of M .

Let $x, y \in N_1 + N_2$ and let $r \in R$. Thus $x = a_1 + b_1$ and $y = a_2 + b_2$, where $a_1, a_2 \in N_1$ and $b_1, b_2 \in N_2$. Thus $x - y = a_1 + b_1 - a_2 - b_2 = a_1 - a_2 + b_1 - b_2$ and $r \cdot x = r \cdot (a_1 + b_1) = r \cdot a_1 + r \cdot b_1$.

Since $N_1 \hookrightarrow M$ and $N_2 \hookrightarrow M$ it follows from Proposition (1.2.10), that $a_1 - a_2, r \cdot a_1 \in N_1$ and $b_1 - b_2, r \cdot b_1 \in N_2$ and this implies that $x - y, r \cdot x \in N_1 + N_2$. By Proposition (1.2.10), $N_1 + N_2$ is a submodule of M .

PROPOSITION 1.2.20.

The intersection of two submodules of a R -module is also a submodule of M .

Proof:-

Let N, K are two submodules of a R -module $N \subseteq M$ and $K \subseteq M \Rightarrow N \cap K \subseteq M, N \cap K \neq \emptyset$, since $N \neq \emptyset, K \neq \emptyset$.

1- $\forall a, b \in N \cap K \Rightarrow a, b \in N$ and $a, b \in K$ by define of \cap .

$\Rightarrow a - b \in N$ and $a - b \in K$ since N, K are submodules $\Rightarrow a - b \in N \cap K$

2- $\forall r \in R, a \in N \cap K \Rightarrow a \in N$ and $a \in K$, by define \cap .

$\forall r \in R \Rightarrow r \cdot a \in N$ and $r \cdot a \in K$ since N, K are submodules $\Rightarrow r \cdot a \in N \cap K. \therefore N \cap K$ is a submodule of M .

OR

We will prove that $N \cap K$ is a submodules of M . Since N and K are subgroups of an abelian group M it follows that N and K contain 0 and hence $N \cap K$ is a nonempty subset of M .

Let $a, b \in N \cap K$ and let $r \in R$. Thus $a, b \in N$ and $a, b \in K$. Since $N \hookrightarrow M$ and $K \hookrightarrow M$ it follows from Proposition (1.2.10), that $a - b, r \cdot a \in N$ and $a - b, r \cdot a \in K$ and this implies that $a - b, r \cdot a \in N \cap K$. By Proposition 1.2.10, $N \cap K$ is a left submodule of M .

PROPOSITION 1.2.21.

Let M be a left R -module and let $\{N_i \mid i \in I\}$ be a family of left submodules of M . Define

$\bigcap_{i \in I} N_i = \{x \in M \mid x \in N_i \text{ for all } i \in I\}$. Then $\bigcap_{i \in I} N_i$ is a left submodule of M .

Proof:-

Let $N_1, N_2, \dots, N_n, \dots$ be any collection of a submodule of M

$N_1 \subseteq M_1, N_2 \subseteq M_2, \dots, N_n \subseteq M_n, \dots$

1- $\forall a, b \in \bigcap_{\lambda \in \Lambda} N_\lambda \Rightarrow a, b \in N_1, a, b \in N_2, \dots, a, b \in N_n, \dots$

$\Rightarrow a - b \in N_1, a - b \in N_2, \dots, a - b \in N_n, \dots \Rightarrow a - b \in \bigcap_{i \in I} N_i$

2- $\forall r \in R, \forall a \in \bigcap_{\lambda \in \Lambda} N_\lambda \Rightarrow a \in N_1, a \in N_2, \dots, a \in N_n, \dots$

$\Rightarrow r \cdot a \in N_1, r \cdot a \in N_2, \dots, r \cdot a \in N_n, \dots \Rightarrow r \cdot a \in \bigcap_{i \in I} N_i$.

$\therefore \bigcap_{i \in I} N_i$ is a submodule of M .

REMARK 1.2.22.

The union of two submodules of a R-module is not necessary a submodule of M.

EXAMPLE 1.2.23.

Let $M=Z_{12}$ is a Z-module and let $N = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}, \bar{4}, \bar{6}, \bar{8}, \bar{10}\}$ and $K= \{\bar{0}, \bar{3}, \bar{6}, \bar{9}\}$. Then N and K are submodules of M.

\oplus_{12}	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$
$\bar{0}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$
$\bar{2}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$
$\bar{4}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$
$\bar{6}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$
$\bar{8}$	$\bar{8}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$
$\bar{10}$	$\bar{10}$	$\bar{0}$	$\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}$	$\bar{6}$	$\bar{8}$

$a - b \in N, \forall a, b \in N$ and $ra \in N, \forall a \in N$ and $r \in R$.

$NUK = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}, \bar{3}, \bar{4}, \bar{6}, \bar{8}, \bar{9}, \bar{10}\}$, $\bar{2}, \bar{3} \in NUK$, but $\bar{2} \oplus_{12} \bar{3} = \bar{5} \notin NUK$.

REMARK 1.2.24.

If N and K are submodules of M , then NUK is a submodules of M $\Leftrightarrow N \subseteq K$ or $K \subseteq N$.

Proof. H.W.

PROPOSITION 1.2.25.

Let M be a left Z-module. Then the left submodules of a left Z-module M are exactly the subgroups of an abelian group M.

Proof.

Let N be a subgroup of an abelian group M, thus N is an abelian group with the same addition of a group M. By Remark 1.1.24, N is a Z-module with the same module multiplication on M and hence by Proposition (1.2.11), we have that N is a left submodules of a left Z-module M. Thus every subgroups of an abelian group M is a left submodules of a left Z-module M.

Let K be a left submodule of a left Z-module M. By Proposition (1.2.11), K is a left Z-module and hence $(K, +)$ is a group. Since K is a subset of M it follows that K is a subgroup of M. Hence the left submodules of a left Z-module M are exactly the subgroups of an abelian group M.

THEOREM 1.2.26. (Modular Law)

If M is a left R-module and if A,B,C are left submodules of M with $B \hookrightarrow C$, then

$$(A + B) \cap C = (A \cap C) + (B \cap C) = (A \cap C) + B.$$

Proof.

(1) We will prove that $(A + B) \cap C = (A \cap C) + B$. Let $x \in (A + B) \cap C$, thus $x \in A + B$ and $x \in C$ and hence $x = a + b$, where $a \in A$ and $b \in B$. Since $B \hookrightarrow C$ it follows that $x, b \in C$ and hence $x - b \in C$. Since $a \in A$ and $a = x - b$ it follows that $a \in A \cap C$ and hence $a + b \in (A \cap C) + B$. Thus $x \in (A \cap C) + B$ and this implies that $(A + B) \cap C \subseteq (A \cap C) + B$.

Since $A \cap C \subseteq C$ it follows that $(A \cap C) + B \subseteq C + B$. Since $A \cap C \subseteq A$ it follows that $(A \cap C) + B \subseteq A + B$ and hence $(A \cap C) + B \subseteq (A + B) \cap (C + B) = (A + B) \cap C$.

Therefore, $(A + B) \cap C = (A \cap C) + B$.

(2) We will prove that $(A \cap C) + (B \cap C) = (A \cap C) + B$. Since $B \subseteq C$ it follows that $B \cap C = B$ and hence $(A \cap C) + (B \cap C) = (A \cap C) + B$.

From (1) and (2) we get that $(A + B) \cap C = (A \cap C) + (B \cap C) = (A \cap C) + B$.

REMARK 1.2.27.

In Theorem (1.2.26), if we remove the condition $B \subseteq C$, then we already have $(A \cap C) + (B \cap C) \subseteq (A + B) \cap C$.

Proof.

Since $A \subseteq A + B$ it follows that $A \cap C \subseteq (A + B) \cap C$. Also, since $B \subseteq A + B$ it follows that $B \cap C \subseteq (A + B) \cap C$ and hence $(A \cap C) + (B \cap C) \subseteq (A + B) \cap C$.

PROPOSITION 1.2.28.

The reverse inclusion in remark(1.2.27) above does not necessarily hold, for example: let $M = R^2$ as a left R -module. Let $A = \{(0, y) \in R^2 \mid y \in R\}$, $B = \{(x, 0) \in R^2 \mid x \in R\}$ and let $C = \{(x, x) \in R^2 \mid x \in R\}$. Then $(A \cap C) + (B \cap C) \neq (A + B) \cap C$.

PROPOSITION 1.2.29.

Let M be a left R -module and let A, B, C are left submodules of M such that $A \subseteq B$, $A + C = B + C$, $A \cap C = B \cap C$. By using **Modular Law**, prove that $A = B$.

Proof. (H.W.) see [Plyth, 2.11, p. 16] or [p.11, Passman: A Course in Ring Theory].

FINITELY GENERATED MODULES

DEFINITION 1.3.1.

If X is a subset of a left R -module M then $\langle X \rangle$ will denote the intersection of all the submodules of M that contain X . This is called the submodule of M generated by X , while the elements of X are called generators of $\langle X \rangle$.

REMARK 1.3.2.

- 1- A right R -modules can be defined analogously as follows.
- 2- If the ring R is commutative, then a module M is left R -module if and only if it is a right R -module.

DEFINITION 1.3.3.

Let X be any subset of an R -module M the submodule of M generated by X denoted by $\langle X \rangle$ or (X) it is the intersection of all submodules of M containing X , i.e. $(X) = \bigcap \{N : N \text{ is a submodule of } M \text{ such that } X \subseteq N\}$

REMARK 1.3.4.

- 1- $\langle X \rangle$ is the smallest submodules of M containing X .
- 2- The set X is called a generating set of the submodules (X) .

PROPOSITION 1.3.5.

Let X be a subset of a left R -module M . Then $\langle X \rangle$ is the smallest left submodule of M that contains a subset X .

Proof.

By Proposition 1.2.25, $\langle X \rangle$ is a submodule of M . Let N be a submodule of M contains X . By definition of $\langle X \rangle$ we have that $\langle X \rangle = \bigcap_{X \subseteq A} A$. Since $N \subseteq M$ and $X \subseteq N$, it follows that

$\langle X \rangle \subseteq N$. Thus $\langle X \rangle$ is the smallest submodule of M that contains a subset X .

PROPOSITION 1.3.6.

Let M be a R -module and $X \subseteq M$. Then (X) is the smallest submodules of M containing X .

Proof :-

Suppose that N is a submodules of M and $X \subseteq N$, we have to show that $(X) \subseteq N$. Let $\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i \in (X)$, $\therefore x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X \subseteq N$. $\therefore r_1 x_1, r_2 x_2, \dots, r_n x_n \in N$ and $r_1 x_1 + r_2 x_2 + \dots + r_n x_n \in N$, since N is submodule of M . $\Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i \in N \Rightarrow (X) \subseteq N$.

PROPOSITION 1.3.7.

Let X be a nonempty subset of a left R -module M and let $N = \{ \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i \mid r_i \in R, x_i \in X, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \}$. Then $N \subseteq M$.

Proof.

Since $X \neq \emptyset$, thus there is an element $a \in X$ and hence $r \cdot a \in N$, for all $r \in R$. Let $r = 0$, thus $0_M = 0_R \cdot a = r \cdot a \in N$ and hence $N \neq \emptyset$. Since $N \subseteq M \Rightarrow N$ is a nonempty subset of M .

Let $a, b \in N$, $r \in R$. Thus $a = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i$ and $b = \sum_{j=1}^m s_j y_j$ with $r_i, s_j \in R, x_i, y_j \in X$, for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, m$ with $n, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Hence $a - b = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i - \sum_{j=1}^m s_j y_j = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i + \sum_{j=1}^m (-s_j) y_j = \sum_{k=1}^{n+m} r_k x_k$, where $r_{n+j} = -s_j$ and

$x_{n+j} = y_j$ for all $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Since $\sum_{k=1}^{n+m} r_k x_k \in N$ (by the definition of N), thus $a - b \in N$.

Also, $r \cdot a = r \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n (r \cdot r_i) x_i$. Since $\sum_{i=1}^n (r \cdot r_i) x_i \in N$ (by the definition of N), thus $r \cdot a \in N$. Therefore, $N \hookrightarrow M$.

PROPOSITION 1.3.8.

Let X be a subset of a left R -module M . Then $\langle X \rangle = \begin{cases} \{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i \mid r_i \in R, x_i \in X, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\} & \text{if } X \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{if } X = \emptyset \end{cases}$

Proof.

Suppose that $X = \emptyset$. Since $\{0\} \hookrightarrow M$ and $X = \emptyset \subseteq \{0\}$, thus $\bigcap_{\emptyset \subseteq A} A = 0$. Since $\langle \emptyset \rangle = \bigcap_{\emptyset \subseteq A} A$,

$\Rightarrow \langle X \rangle = \langle \emptyset \rangle = 0$.

Suppose that $X \neq \emptyset$ and let $N = \{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i \mid r_i \in R, x_i \in X, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$. We will prove that $\langle X \rangle = N$.

Let $a \in N \Rightarrow a = \sum_{i=1}^m s_i y_i$ with $s_i \in R, y_i \in X, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Let A be any submodule of M contains X . Since $y_i \in X$ and $s_i \in R \Rightarrow s_i \cdot y_i \in A$, for all

$i = 1, 2, \dots, m \Rightarrow a = \sum_{i=1}^m s_i y_i \in A \Rightarrow N \subseteq A$, for all submodule A of M contains X

$\Rightarrow N \subseteq \bigcap_{\substack{X \subseteq A \\ A \hookrightarrow M}} A$

Since $\langle X \rangle = \bigcap_{\substack{X \subseteq A \\ A \hookrightarrow M}} A \Rightarrow N \subseteq \langle X \rangle$.

By Proposition 1.3.5, $\langle X \rangle$ is the smallest left submodule of M contains X . Since N is a left submodule of M (by Proposition 1.3.6) and $X \subseteq N$ (**Why?**), it follows that $\langle X \rangle \subseteq N$.

Thus $\langle X \rangle = N = \{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i \mid r_i \in R, x_i \in X, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$.

DEFINITION 1.3.9.

(1) If M is a finitely generated left R -module generated by a subset $X = F\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, then we will write $M = \langle a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \rangle$.

Also, from Proposition 1.3.7, we get that $M = \langle a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \rangle = N = \{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i a_i \mid r_i \in R, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$.

(2) A left R -module M is said to be finitely generated if it generated by a finite subset X , that is $M = \langle X \rangle$.

(3) If M is a cyclic left R -module generated by a subset $X = \{a\}$, then we will write $M = \langle a \rangle$. Also, from Proposition 1.3.7, we get that $M = \langle a \rangle = \{r \cdot a \mid r \in R\} = Ra$.

(4) A left R -module M is said to be cyclic if it generated by a subset $X = \{a\}$ contains one element only, that is $M = \langle \{a\} \rangle$.

(6) Let M be a R -module and $X \subseteq M$. If $X = \{x\}$, the set submodule $X = \{r \cdot x \mid r \in R\} = R_x$, In this case we say that R_x is the cyclic submodule of M generated by X and we write (X) instead of (X) .

(7) A R -module M is called **cyclic R -module M** if there exists $x \in M$ such that $M = (x)$.

EXAMPLE 1.3.10.

- (1) Every left R-module M has a generated set M.
- (2) Every ring R with identity 1 is a cyclic left R-module, since ${}_R R = \langle 1 \rangle$.
- (3) Let $M = \mathbb{Z}_{24}$ as \mathbb{Z}_{24} -module. Then $\langle 6, 12 \rangle = \mathbb{Z}_{24} \cap \langle 2 \rangle \cap \langle 3 \rangle \cap \langle 6 \rangle = \{0, 6, 12, 18\} = \langle 6 \rangle$.
Also, $\mathbb{Z}_{24} = \langle 1 \rangle = \langle 5 \rangle = \langle 7 \rangle$ as \mathbb{Z}_{24} -module.

PROPOSITION 1.3.11.

Let $\{N_i \mid i \in I\}$ be a family of submodules of a left R-module M. Then

$$\langle \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle = \begin{cases} \{\sum_{i \in I'} a_i \mid a_i \in N_i, I' \subseteq I \text{ with } I' \text{ is finite}\} & \text{if } I \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{if } I = \emptyset \end{cases}$$

That is, in the case $I \neq \emptyset$, $\langle \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle$ is the set of all finite sums $\sum a_i$ with $a_i \in N_i$.

Proof.

If $I = \emptyset$, then $\bigcup_{i \in I} N_i = \emptyset$. By Proposition 1.3.7, $\langle \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle = 0$.

If $I \neq \emptyset$, then $\bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \neq \emptyset$. By Proposition (1.3.7), $\langle \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle = \{\sum_{j=1}^n r_j x_j \mid r_j \in R, x_j \in \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$.

Let $x \in \langle \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle$, thus $x = \sum_{j=1}^n r_j \cdot x_j$, for some $r_j \in R$, $x_j \in \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. If we bring together all summands $r_j \cdot x_j$ which lie in a fixed N_i to form a sum x'_i and if we treat with the remaining summands similarly then it follows that $x = \sum_{i \in I'} r_i x'_i = \sum_{i \in I'} x'_i$.

Thus $\langle \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle \subseteq \{\sum_{i \in I'} a_i \mid a_i \in N_i, I' \subseteq I \text{ with } I' \text{ is finite}\}$.

Conversely, let $x \in \{\sum_{i \in I'} a_i \mid a_i \in N_i, I' \subseteq I \text{ with } I' \text{ is finite}\}$, thus $x = \sum_{j \in I'} b_j$, with $b_j \in N_j, I' \subseteq I$ with I' is finite. We can write $I' = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Thus $x = \sum_{j=1}^n b_j$ with $b_j \in \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \Rightarrow x \in \langle \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle$ and hence $\{\sum_{i \in I'} a_i \mid a_i \in N_i, I' \subseteq I \text{ with } I' \text{ is finite}\} \subseteq \langle \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle$. Thus $\langle \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle = \{\sum_{i \in I'} a_i \mid a_i \in N_i, I' \subseteq I \text{ with } I' \text{ is finite}\}$.

PROPOSITION 1.3.12.

If $\{N_i; i \in I\}$ is any collection of submodules of a R-module M, the sum of this collection denoted by: $\sum_{i \in I} N_i$ it is defined to be the submodule of M generated by: $\bigcup_{i \in I} N_i$. That is

$\sum_{i \in I} N_i = (\bigcup_{i \in I} N_i)$. Show that :-

- 1) $\sum_{i \in I} N_i = \{0\} \Leftrightarrow I=Q \Leftrightarrow M = \{0\}$
- 2) $\sum_{i \in I} N_i = \{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i \cdot x_i \mid r_i \in R, x_i \in N_i, \forall i=1,2,\dots,n\}$

In particular :- $N_1 + N_2 = (N_1 \cup N_2) = \{a + b : a \in N_1 \cap b \in N_2\}$ is submodules of M.

Proof:-

- 1) (\Rightarrow) Suppose $\sum_{i \in I} N_i = \{0\}$, since $\sum_{i \in I} N_i = (\bigcup_{i \in I} N_i) = \{0\}$.
 $\{0\} = (\bigcup_{i \in I} N_i) = \cap \{K \mid K \text{ is a submodule of } M \text{ and } \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \subseteq K\} \Rightarrow K_i = \{0\} \Rightarrow \bigcup_{i \in I} N_i \subseteq \{0\} \Rightarrow N_i = \{0\}, \forall i \in I \Rightarrow I=Q \Rightarrow M = \{0\}$.

(\Leftarrow) $M = \{0\} \Rightarrow \therefore N_i \subseteq M \Rightarrow N_i = \{0\} \Rightarrow I=Q \Rightarrow \sum_{i \in I} N_i = \{0\}$.

- 2) $\sum_{i \in I} N_i = (\bigcup_{i \in I} N_i) = \{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i \cdot x_i : r_i \in R \ \& \ x_i \in N_i, \forall i=1,2,\dots,n\}$. If $i=1$ and $i=2$,

1- Let $a_1 + b_1, a_2 + b_2 \in N_1 + N_2 \Rightarrow (a_1 + b_1) + (a_2 + b_2) = (a_1 + a_2 + b_1 + b_2) \in N_1 + N_2$.

2- $\forall r \in R$ and $a + b \in N_1 + N_2 \Rightarrow r \cdot (a + b) = r \cdot a + r \cdot b \in N_1 + N_2 \Rightarrow r \cdot (a + b) \in N_1 + N_2$.

$\therefore N_1 + N_2$ is a submodule of M. (S) = $\sum_{i \in I} N_i$, let $r_1 \cdot x_1, r_2 \cdot x_2 \in (S)$

- 1) $r_1.s_1 + r_2.s_2 \in (S)$ since $S \subseteq M$ (M module)
 2) $k.(r_1.s_1) = (k.r_1).s_1 \in (S) \Rightarrow (S)$ is submodules of M.

PROPOSITION 1.3.13.

Let M be a R-module and $X \subseteq M$. Prove that if $X=Q$, then $(X) = \{0\}$.

Proof:-

Since $(X) = \cap \{N: N \text{ is a submodules of } M ; X \subseteq N\}$. $\therefore (Q) = \cap \{N: N \text{ is a submodule of } M ; Q \subseteq N\}$.
 Since $\{0\}$ is a trivial submodules of M and $Q \subseteq \{0\}$. $\therefore (Q) = \{0\} \cap \{N: N \text{ is a submodules of } M; Q \subseteq N\} = \{0\}$.

PROPOSITION 1.3.14.

if $X \neq Q$, then $(X) = \{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i = r_i \in R \text{ n } x_i \in X \forall i=1,2,\dots,n\}$
 = the set of an finite linear combinations of elements of X

Proof :-

$X \neq Q \Rightarrow X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$. And since $(X) = \cap \{N: N_i \text{ is a submodules of } M \text{ such that } X \subseteq N_i\}$
 $\Rightarrow \forall r_i \in X \Rightarrow x_i \in N_i$ (since $x \subseteq N_i$). $\therefore \forall r_i \in R \quad \forall x_i \in X \Rightarrow r_i x_i \in N_i$ (since N is submodules) $\sum r_i x_i \in N_i$.
 Since $(X) = \cap \{N_i : N_i \text{ submodule}\} \Rightarrow (X) = \{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i : r_i \in R, x_i \in X\}$.

PROPOSITION 1.3.15.

Let M be a R-module and $X \subseteq M$. Prove that if $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, then $(X) = \{\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i : r_i \in R, \forall i=1,2,\dots,n\}$.

Proof:-

$R_x = \{r.X : r \in R\}$ is a cyclic submodule since $x \in X$ is submodule.

- 1) Let $r_1.x, r_2.x \in R_x \Rightarrow r_1.x_1 + r_2.x = (r_1+r_2).x \in R_x$
 2) Let $k \in R$ and $r.x \in R_x \Rightarrow k.(r.x) = k.r.x \in R_x$
 $\therefore R_x$ submodule of m R_x cyclic since $\exists x \in X=M$ such that $m = \{r x, x \in X\} = (X)$.

REMARK 1.3.16.

Every simple module is cyclic module.

Proof :-

Let M be a simple R-module $\Rightarrow m$ has no proper submodules (by define of simple R-module).

The only submodules of M are modules $\{0\}$.

Since $\forall x \in M, M = \{r.x, r \in R\}$ by define of submodule $= (X)$. $\therefore \exists x \in M$ such that $M = (X)$.

$\therefore M$ is cyclic module.

Or

Let M be a simple R-module and let X be any subset of M $\Rightarrow (X) = \cap \{N: N \text{ is submodule of } M, X \subseteq N\}$. $\therefore M$ is simple $\Rightarrow \{0\}, M$ are only submodules of M. $\therefore X \neq Q \Rightarrow (X) \neq \{0\}$.

$(X) = \cap \{M: M \text{ is submodule of itself, } X \subseteq M\}$. $\therefore (X) = M$.

If $X = \{x\} \Rightarrow M = (X) \Rightarrow M$ is cyclic module.

EXAMPLES 1.3.17.

- 1) Z as a Z-module is cyclic module, since $Z = (1)$, $Z = \{n . 1 : n \in Z\} = Z . 1$

2) Z_n as a Z -module (n is a positive integer) is a cyclic Z -module . Since $Z_n = Z \cdot \bar{1} = \{n \cdot \bar{1} : n \in Z\}$.
As Z_8 as a Z -module since $Z \times Z_8 \rightarrow Z_8 \supset 4Z$.

$4Z = \{0, 4\}$ is submodule of Z_8 since : $\bar{0} +_8 \bar{4} \in 4Z$, $\bar{4} \cdot_8 \bar{8} = \bar{32} = \bar{0} \in 4Z$

3) $n \cdot Z$ as a Z -module of Z is cyclic generated by n since $n \cdot Z = \{k \cdot n : k \in Z\} = (n)$

$E = 2 \cdot Z = (2) = \{2k : k \in Z\}$ is cyclic submodule of Z generated by 2.

4) $N = (\bar{4}) = \{\bar{0}, \bar{4}\}$ is a submodules of Z_8 . 1- $\bar{0} +_8 \bar{4} = \bar{4} \in (\bar{4})$. 2- $\forall r \in Z_8 \Rightarrow r \cdot_8 \bar{4} \in (\bar{4})$.

i. e. $\bar{0} \cdot \bar{4} = \bar{0} \in \bar{4}$, $\bar{1} \cdot \bar{4} = \bar{4} \in \bar{4}$, $\bar{2} \cdot \bar{4} = \bar{8} = \bar{0} \in \bar{4}$, $\bar{3} \cdot \bar{4} = \bar{12} = \bar{4} \in \bar{4}$, $\therefore (\bar{4})$ is sub module Z_8 generated by 4. Since $\forall r \in Z_8 \Rightarrow N = \{r \cdot \bar{4} , r \in Z_8\} = (\bar{4})$ cyclic but not prime submodule of Z_8 .

PROPOSITION 1.3.18.

If finitely many elements are omitted from any generating set of Q_Z (Q as a Z -module), then the set after these elements omitted is also a generating set for Q_Z .

Proof :-

Let $X \subseteq Q$ be a generating set of Q (i. e) $Q = (X)$. Let $x_0 \in X$; we have to show that $Q = (X - \{x_0\})$.

$x_0/2 \in Q \Rightarrow x_0/2 = \sum_{i=0}^n r_i \cdot x_i = r_0 x_0 + \sum_{x_0 \neq x_i}^n r_i \cdot x_i$, (since $Q = (X)$).

$x_0 = 2r_0 x_0 + \sum_{x_0 \neq x_i}^n 2 \cdot r_i \cdot x_i \Rightarrow (1-2r_0)x_0 = \sum_{x_0 \neq x_i}^n r'_i \cdot x_i$

$n \cdot x_0 = \sum_{x_0 \neq x_i}^n r'_i \cdot x_i \dots \dots (1)$ where $n = 1-2r_0$, $n \neq 0$, since $r_0 \in Z$. Since $n \neq 0 \Rightarrow x_0/2 \in Q$

$x_0/2 = r'_0 x_0 + \sum_{x_0 \neq x_i}^n r''_i \cdot x_i$, since $Q = (X)$.

$x_0 = n \cdot r'_0 x_0 + \sum_{x_0 \neq x_i}^n r''_i \cdot x_i = \sum_{x_0 \neq x_i}^n r'_{i0} r'_i \cdot x_i + \sum_{x_0 \neq x_i}^n n \cdot r''_i \cdot x_i = \sum_{x_0 \neq x_i}^n r'''_i x_i$

$\therefore x_0 \in (X - \{x_0\}) \Rightarrow Q \subseteq (X - \{x_0\})$. But $(X - \{x_0\}) \subseteq Q$. $\therefore Q = (X - \{x_0\})$

COROLLARY 1.3.19.

Q as a Z -module is not finitely generated.

Proof :-

Suppose that Q_Z is finite generated . $\therefore \exists$ a finite set $X \subseteq Q$ such that $Q = (X)$.

$\therefore Q = (Q)$ by the proposition(1.3.18). $\therefore Q = \{0\}$ which is a contradiction (C!).

$\therefore Q_Z$ is not finitely generated.

Chapter Two

HOMOMORPHISMS OF MODULES

DEFINITION 2.1.1.

Let M, M' be to two left R -modules, then mapping $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +', \cdot')$ is called Left R -module homomorphism (R -homomorphism) if for all $x, y \in M, r \in R$, then

$$1- f(x + y) = f(x) +' f(y), \forall x, y \in M,$$

$$2- f(r \cdot y) = r \cdot' f(y), \forall r \in R, \forall y \in M.$$

i.e., f preserves addition and scalar multiplication between the two modules.

EXAMPLES 2.1.2.

Let M, M' be any two R -modules and $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +', \cdot')$ be a mapping. f is called **constant mapping zero**. i.e., $f(m) = {}_{M'}0, \forall m \in M$, then f is a R -homomorphism.

Note that:- This homomorphism is called the trivial homomorphism.

Proof:- $\forall m_1, m_2 \in M, \forall r \in R$,

$$1- f(m_1 + m_2) = {}_{M'}0 = {}_{M'}0 + {}_{M'}0 = f(m_1) +' f(m_2),$$

$$2- f(r \cdot m_1) = r \cdot {}_{M'}0 = r \cdot' f(m_1).$$

EXAMPLES 2.1.3.

Let M be any R -module, the identity map ${}_M I$ on M is a R -homomorphism on M .

${}_M I$ is called **the identity homomorphism on M** , ${}_M I: M \rightarrow M$ such that ${}_M I(m) = m, \forall m \in M$.

Proof:-

Let $m, m_1, m_2 \in M, r \in R$,

$${}_M I(m_1 + m_2) = m_1 + m_2 = {}_M I(m_1) + {}_M I(m_2),$$

$${}_M I(r \cdot m) = r \cdot m = r \cdot {}_M I(m) \Rightarrow {}_M I \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}$$

EXAMPLES 2.1.4.

If M is any R -module and N is a submodule of M the inclusion map $I_N: N \rightarrow M$ such that $I_N(m) = m, \forall m \in N$. I_N is a R -homomorphism. This homomorphism is called **the inclusion homomorphism**.

Proof:- Let $m, m_1, m_2 \in M, r \in R$,

$$I_N(m_1 + m_2) = m_1 + m_2 = I_N(m_1) + I_N(m_2), \text{ and } I_N(r \cdot m) = r \cdot m = r \cdot I_N(m).$$

I_N is a R -homomorphism.

EXAMPLES 2.1.5.

If N is a submodule of a R -module M , the natural map $\pi : M \rightarrow M/N$ defined by $\pi(m) = m+N$, $\forall m \in M$ is a R -homomorphism. π is called **the natural homomorphism from M on to M/N** .

Proof:- Let $m, m_1, m_2 \in M, r \in R$,

$$1- \pi(m_1 + m_2) = (m_1 + m_2) + N, \quad \forall m_1, m_2 \in M. = (m_1 + N) \oplus (m_2 + N), \quad \text{by define of } \oplus \\ = \pi(m_1) + \pi(m_2), \quad \text{by define of natural map}$$

$$2- \pi(rm) = r.m + N, \quad \forall m \in M. = r.(m + N) = r.\pi(m). \quad \therefore \pi \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism.}$$

DEFINITION 2.1.6.

Let M, N be two R -modules. Let $H = \text{Hom}_R(M, N) = \{f \mid f: M \rightarrow N \text{ is a homomorphism}\}$ = the set of all homomorphism from M into N . Define $(+)$ and (\cdot) on H such that $(f+g)(m) = f(m) + g(m)$ and $(r.f)(m) = r.f(m), \forall f, g \in H, \forall r \in R, m \in M$. Then It is called **the module of all homomorphism of M to N** and $(H, +, \cdot)$ is an until M -module.

Proof:-

Closure, let $f, g \in H$, since $f: M \rightarrow N$ is homomorphism and $g: M \rightarrow N$ is homomorphism, $f + g: M \rightarrow N$ homomorphism, where

$$(f + g)(a+b) = f(a+b) + g(a+b) = f(a) + f(b) + g(a) + g(b) = f(a) + g(a) + f(b) + g(b) \\ = (f + g)(a) + (f + g)(b). \quad \therefore f + g \text{ is homomorphism.}$$

Well-defined, $f = f_1$ and $g = g_1, (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = f_1(m) + g_1(m) = (f_1 + g_1)(m)$.

Assuasive, $[(f + g) + h](m) = (f + g)(m) + h(m) = (f(m) + g(m)) + h(m) = f(m) + (g(m) + h(m)) \\ = f(m) + (g+h)(m) = [f + (g+h)](m).$

Identity, $f(m) = e_N, (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = e_N + g(m) = g(m)$

$$(g + f)(m) = g(m) + f(m) = g(m) + e_N = g(m).$$

Inverse, $f(m) + f(m^{-1}) = f(m + m^{-1}) = f(e_M) = e_N. f(m^{-1}) + f(m) = f(m^{-1} + m) = f(e_M) = e_N.$

$$\therefore (f(m))^{-1} = f(m^{-1}).$$

Commutative, $(f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) = g(m) + f(m)$, since $(M, +)$ is commutative group $= (g + f)(m)$. $\therefore f + g$ is commutative.

$(H, +)$ is commutative group.

Define $\alpha : M \times H \rightarrow H$ such that $(f, m) \mapsto f(m). \quad \forall f, g \in H, \quad \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M.$

i- Let $f, g \in H$ and $m \in M$,

$$(f + g, m) = (f + g)(m) = f(m) + g(m) \text{ by define of } + \text{ on } H = (f, m) + (g, m) \text{ by define of } \alpha.$$

ii- Let $f, g \in H$ and $m \in M$,

$$(r.f, m) = (r.f)(m) \text{ by define } \alpha = r.f(m) \text{ by define of } \cdot \text{ on } H = (r, (f, m)).$$

iii- Let $f \in H$ and $m_1 + m_2 \in M$

$$(f, m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) + f(m_2) = (f, m_1) + (f, m_2).$$

iv- mI is the identity mapping of H and $(mI, m) = mI(m) = m, \quad \forall m \in N.$

$\therefore (H, +, \cdot)$ is an until M -module.

PROPOSITION 2.1.7.

Let M, N be two R -modules. Let $K = \text{End}_R(M) = \{f \mid f: M \rightarrow M \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}\} =$ the set of all homomorphism from M into M . Define $(+)$ and (\circ) on H . $K = \text{End}_R(M)$ is called **the endomorphism ring of M over R** .

Proof:-

By examples (1.1.15), $(K = \text{End}_R(M), +)$ is **commutative group**.

Define $\alpha : M \times K \rightarrow K$ such that $(f, m) \rightarrow f(m)$. $\forall f, g \in K, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M$.

i- Let $f, g \in K$ and $m \in M$,

$$(f+g, m) = (f+g)(m) = f(m)+g(m) \text{ by define of } + \text{ on } K = (f, m)+(g, m) \text{ by define of } \alpha.$$

ii- Let $f, g \in K$ and $m \in M$,

$$(f \circ g, m) = (f \circ g)(m) \text{ by define } \alpha = f(g(m)) \text{ by define of } + \text{ on } K = (f, g(m)) = (f, (g, m)).$$

iii- Let $f \in K$ and $m_1+m_2 \in M$ $(f, m_1+m_2) = f(m_1+m_2) = f(m_1)+f(m_2) = (f, m_1) + (f, m_2)$.

iv- I_m is the identity mapping of K and $(I_m, m) = I_m(m) = m, \forall m \in M$.

$\therefore (K = \text{End}_R(M), +, \cdot)$ is an until M -module .

REMARK 2.1.8.

Let M, N be two R -modules. $\text{Hom}_R(M, N) = \{f \mid f: M \rightarrow N \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}\} =$ the set of all R -homomorphism from M into N .

In case $N = R$, then $\text{Hom}_R(M, R) = M^*$. It is a ring with respect to the operation $+$ and \circ .

$\text{End}_R(M)$ is called **the dual module of M** . A R -module M is called **the dualizable** if $M^* \neq 0$.

EXAMPLES 2.1.9.

Let M, N be two R -modules. $M^* = \text{Hom}_R(M, R) = \{f \mid f: M \rightarrow R \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}\}$. It is a ring with respect to the operation $+$ and \circ . Prove that $M^* = (\text{Hom}_R(M, R), +, \cdot)$ is a R -module

Proof:-

By examples (1.1.14), $(M^* = \text{Hom}_R(M, R), +)$ is **commutative group**.

Define $\alpha : M \times M^* \rightarrow M^*$ such that $(f, m) \rightarrow f(m)$. $\forall f, g \in M^*, \forall m, m_1, m_2 \in M$.

i- $(f+g, m) = (f+g)(m) = f(m)+g(m)$ by define of $+$ on $M^* = (f, m)+(g, m)$ by define of α .

ii- $(f \circ g, m) = (f \circ g)(m)$ by define $\alpha = f(g(m))$ by define of $+$ on $M^* = (f, g(m)) = (f, (g, m))$.

iii- $(f, m_1+m_2) = f(m_1+m_2) = f(m_1)+f(m_2) = (f, m_1) + (f, m_2)$

iv- mI is the identity mapping of R and $(mI, m) = mI(m) = m$.

$\therefore (M^*, +, \cdot)$ is an until M -module .

THEOREM 2.1.10.

1. 1- For any R -module M , $\text{Hom}_R(R, M) \cong M$.

2. if \exists a R -homomorphism $Q: M \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(R, M)$ such that $Q \circ \beta = I_{\text{Hom}(R, M)}$ any $\beta \circ Q = I_M$.

Proof:-

1- Defined $\beta: \text{Hom}_R(R, M) \rightarrow M$ such that $\beta(f) = f(1), \forall f \in \text{Hom}_R(R, M)$, where 1 is ideal element of R . $f(1) \in M$, closed, since $f: R \rightarrow M, 1 \in R \Rightarrow f(1) \in M$.

And if $f=g \in \text{Hom}_R(R, M) \Rightarrow f(1)=g(1)$. $\therefore \beta(f)=\beta(g) \Rightarrow \beta$ is well-defined $\Rightarrow \beta$ is a mapping.

$$\text{Let } f, g \in \text{Hom}_R(R, M), \beta(f+g) = (f+g)(1) = f(1)+g(1) = \beta(f) + \beta(g).$$

$$\text{Let } r \in R, \beta(r.f) = (r.f)(1) = r.(f(1)) = r.\beta(f) \Rightarrow \beta \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}$$

Let $\beta(f) \in M$, there exist $f \in \text{Hom}_R(R, M)$ such that $\beta(f) = f(1) \Rightarrow \beta$ is onto.

And if $\beta(f) = \beta(g) \Rightarrow f(1) = g(1) \therefore f = g \in \text{Hom}_R(R, M) \Rightarrow \beta$ is 1-1.

2- Define $\beta^1 = Q: M \rightarrow \text{Hom}_R(R, M)$ such that $(Q(m))(r) = r.m, \forall m \in M, \forall r \in R$.

$\therefore M$ is a R -module $\Rightarrow r.m \in M, \forall r \in R, \forall m \in M. \Rightarrow (Q(m))(r) \in M$ is closed.

$Q(m) \in \text{Hom}_R(R, M)$ such that $Q(m): R \rightarrow M, \exists Q(m)(r) = r.m$.

If $r_1 = r_2$ in $R \Rightarrow r_1.m = r_2.m \Rightarrow (Q(m)(r_1)) = (Q(m)(r_2)) \Rightarrow Q(m)$ is well-defined. $\therefore Q(m)$ is a mapping.

To prove Q is homomorphism.

$(Q(m))(r_1 + r_2) = (r_1 + r_2)(m) = r_1.m + r_2.m$, since M is a R -module $= (Q(m))(r_1) + (Q(m))(r_2)$.

$(Q(m))(r_1 \cdot r_2) = r_1 \cdot r_2(m) = r_1(r_2 \cdot m) = r_1(Q(m))(r_2)$

$\therefore Q(m)$ is a R -homomorphism $\Rightarrow Q(m) \in \text{Hom}_R(R, M) \Rightarrow Q(m)$ is closed.

1- $(Q(m_1 + m_2))(r) = r(m_1 + m_2) = r.m_1 + r.m_2 = (Q(m_1) + (Q(m_2)))(r) = (Q(m_1) + Q(m_2))(r), \forall r \in R$.

$\therefore Q(m_1 + m_2) = Q(m_1) + Q(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M$.

2- $(Q(s.m))(r) = r.(s.m) = (r.s).m = (s.r).m$, since R is commutative

$= s.(r.m) = s.(Q(m))(r), \forall r, s \in R, \forall m \in M. \therefore Q(sm) = s Q(m)$

$\therefore Q$ is a R -homomorphism

To proof $Q \circ \beta = I_{\text{Hom}(R, M)}$ any $\beta \circ Q = I_{\text{Hom}(R, M)}$?

Let $f \in \text{Hom}_R(R, M), (Q \circ \beta)(f) = Q(\beta(f)) = Q(f(1))$ and $(Q(f(1)))(r) = r.f(1) = f(r.1) = f(r), \forall r \in R$.

$\therefore (Q \circ \beta)(f) = f, \forall f \in \text{Hom}_R(R, M). \therefore Q \circ \beta = I_{\text{Hom}(R, M)}$.

Let $m \in M, (\beta \circ Q)(m) = \beta(Q(m)) = (Q(m))(1) = 1.m = m = I_{\text{Hom}(R, M)}(m), \forall m \in M. \therefore \beta \circ Q = I_{\text{Hom}(R, M)}$.

THEOREM 2.1.11.

Let M, M' be to two R -modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +, \cdot)$ be a R -homomorphism, then

1- $f(0_M) = 0_{M'} \wedge f(-a) = -f(a), \forall a \in M$.

2- $f(a - b) = f(a) - f(b), \forall a, b \in M$

Proof:- H.W.

DEFINITION 2.1.12.

Let M, N be to two R -modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +, \cdot)$ be a R -homomorphism.

1- The kernel of f denoted by $(\ker(f))$, it is the set $\{x : x \in M, f(x) = 0_M\} \subseteq M$.

2- The image of f denoted by $(\text{Im}(f))$, it is the set $\{f(m) : m \in M\} \subseteq N$.

3- The cokernel of f denoted by $(\text{Coker}(f))$, it is the set $\text{Coker}(f) = \text{CoDom}(f)/\text{Im}(f) = N/\text{Im}(f)$.

4- The coimage of f denoted by $(\text{Coim}(f))$, it is the set $\text{Coim}(f) = \text{Dom}(f)/\ker(f) = M/\ker(f)$.

REMARK 2.1.13.

1- If f is an injection (1-1) and homomorphism, then f is called a monomorphism.

2- If f is a surjection (onto) and homomorphism, then f is called an epimorphism.

3- If f is a bijection (1-1 and onto) and homomorphism, then f is called an isomorphism.

4- Two R-modules M and N are said to be isomorphic ($M \cong N$) if and only if, \exists an isomorphism from M into N or (from N into M).

5- If $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +', \cdot')$ is a R-homomorphism, then

a- $f(0) = 0'$.

b- $f(-x) = -f(x)$, for all $x \in M$.

THEOREM 2.1.14.

Let M, N be two R-modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +', \cdot')$ be a R-homomorphism. Then:

1. $\ker f$ is a submodule of M .
2. $\text{Im}(f)$ is a submodule of N .
3. $\ker f = \{0\} \Leftrightarrow f$ is 1-1.
4. $\text{Im} f = N \Leftrightarrow f$ is a R-epimorphism.
5. f is a R-isomorphism if and only if \exists a R-homomorphism $g: N \rightarrow M$ such that $g \circ f = I_M$ and $f \circ g = I_N$.

Proof:-

1- $\ker f = \{m \in M : f(m) = 0_M\} \subseteq M$, $\ker f \neq \emptyset$ since $0 \in M \Rightarrow f(0) = 0 \in \ker f$.

Let $m_1, m_2 \in \ker f \Rightarrow f(m_1) = 0_M, f(m_2) = 0_M$.

$f(m_1 + m_2) = f(m_1) + f(m_2) = 0_M + 0_M = 0_M \Rightarrow m_1 + m_2 \in \ker f, \forall r \in R, m \in \ker f \Rightarrow f(m) = 0_M$

$f(r.m) = r.f(m) = r.0_M = 0_M \Rightarrow r.m \in \ker f$. Hence, $\ker f$ is a submodule of M.

2- $\text{Im} f = \{f(m); m \in M\} \subseteq N$, $\text{Im} f \neq \emptyset$, since $0 \in M \Rightarrow f(0) = 0 \in \text{Im} f$.

Let $x_1, x_2 \in \text{Im} f \Rightarrow x_1 = f(m_1), x_2 = f(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M$.

$x_1 + x_2 = f(m_1) + f(m_2) = f(m_1 + m_2) \in \text{Im} f$, since $(M, +)$ is group $m_1 + m_2 \in M, \forall r \in R, x \in \text{Im} f$

$\Rightarrow x = f(m)$.

$r.x = r.f(m) = f(r.m) \in \text{Im} f$, since $r.m \in M$ (M is a module). $\therefore \text{Im} f$ is a submodule of M.

3- $\ker f = \{m_0\} \Leftrightarrow f$ is a R-monomorphism.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\ker f = \{m_0\}, f(m) = m_0, \forall m \in M$. Let $m_1, m_2 \in M, f(m_1) = f(m_2) \Rightarrow m_0 = m_0 \Rightarrow m_1 = m_2$, by hyp. $\therefore f$ is 1-1. $\Rightarrow f$ is a R-monomorphism

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that f is a R-monomorphism \Rightarrow If $f(m_1) = f(m_2), \forall m_1, m_2 \in M \Rightarrow m_1 = m_2$. $\ker f = \{m \in M, f(m) = m_0\}, m \in \ker f \Rightarrow f(m) = m_0, f(0) = m_0$, since f is a R-homomorphism $\Rightarrow f(m) = f(0) = m_0 \Rightarrow m = m_0$, since f is 1-1 $\Rightarrow \ker f = \{m_0\}, \forall m \in M$.

4- $\text{Im} f = N \Leftrightarrow f$ is a R-epimorphism

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\text{Im} f = N \Rightarrow \text{Im} f = \{f(m) : m \in M\} = N, \forall y \in N \Rightarrow \exists m \in M \ni f(m) = y \Rightarrow f$ is onto $\Rightarrow f$ is R-epimorphism.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that f is a R-epimorphism $\Rightarrow f$ is onto. To proof $\text{Im} f \subseteq N$, by define of $\text{Im} f$. Since f is onto. Let $y \in N \Rightarrow \exists m \in M \ni f(m) = y \Rightarrow y \in \text{Im} f \Rightarrow N \subseteq \text{Im} f \Rightarrow \text{Im} f = N$.

5- (\Rightarrow) Suppose that f is R -isomorphism, to proof $g:N \rightarrow M$ is R -homomorphism

$\Rightarrow \exists f^{-1}:N \rightarrow M$ such that $f^{-1} \circ g = \text{id}_N$. Since f is a R -isomorphism $\Rightarrow \exists m_1, m_2 \in M$ such that $f(m_1)=y_1$ and $f(m_2)=y_2 \forall y_1, y_2 \in N$ (since f onto)

$$1) g(y_1, y_2) = g(f(m_1)+f(m_2)) = f^{-1}(f(m_1+m_2)) = f^{-1} \circ (f(m_1+m_2)) = m_1+m_2 \\ = f^{-1}(y_1)+f^{-1}(y_2) = g(y_1)+g(y_2).$$

$$2) g(r.y)=g(r.f(m)) = g(f(r.m)) = f^{-1}(f(r.m)) = r.m = r.f^{-1}(y) = r.g(y). \therefore g \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}$$

$$\text{Let } x \in M, g \circ f(x)=g(f(x)) = f^{-1}(f(x)) = x = \text{id}_M, \forall x \in M.$$

$$\text{Let } y \in N, f \circ g(y)=f(g(y)) = f(f^{-1}(y)) = y = \text{id}_N, \forall y \in N.$$

(\Leftarrow) To proof f is a R -isomorphism, to proof f is 1-1 and onto.

Since $f:M \rightarrow N$, $g:N \rightarrow M$, then

$g \circ f(x) = \text{id}_M: M \rightarrow M \Rightarrow f$ is 1-1 & g onto, since id_M is a R -isomorphism.

$f \circ g(x) = \text{id}_N: N \rightarrow N \Rightarrow g(x)$ is 1-1 & f onto, since id_N is a R -isomorphism.

$\therefore f$ is a R -isomorphism.

THEOREM 2.1.15.

Let M, M' be to two R -modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M', +, \cdot)$ be a R -homomorphism, then

1- If N is submodule of M , then $f(N)$ is R -submodule of M' , where f is onto.

2- If W is submodule of M' , then $f^{-1}(W)$ is a R -submodule of M .

Proof:- H.W.

COROLLARY 2.1.16.

Let $f:M \rightarrow N$ be a left R -homomorphism. Then $\ker(f)$ is a left submodule of M and $\text{Im}(f)$ is a left submodule of N .

Proof.

Since $\ker(f) = \{x \in M \mid f(x) = 0\} = f^{-1}(0)$ and since $0 \in N$ it follows from Theorem(2.1.15(2)) that $\ker(f)$ is a left submodule of M .

Also, since $\text{Im}(f) = \{y \in N \mid y = f(x), \text{for some } x \in M\} = f(M)$ and since $M \in M$ it follows Theorem (2.1.15(1)) that $\text{Im}(f)$ is a left submodule of N .

PROPOSITION 2.1.17.

Let M be a left R -module and let N be a left submodule of M . Then the natural mapping $\pi: M \rightarrow M/N$ defined by $\pi(x) = x + N$, for all $x \in M$ is a left R -epimorphism with kernel N .

Proof. [Dummit and Foote, Proposition 3, p. 348]

Let $x, y \in M$ and let $r \in R$, thus $\pi(x+y) = (x+y) + N = (x+N) + (y+N) = \pi(x) + \pi(y)$ and $\pi(r.x) = r.x + N = r.(x+N) = r.\pi(x)$. Thus $\pi: M \rightarrow M/N$ is a left R -homomorphism. Since π is a surjective mapping $\Rightarrow \pi$ is a R -epimorphism.

$$\text{Also, } \ker(\pi) = \{x \in M \mid \pi(x) = 0\} = \{x \in M \mid x + N = N\} = \{x \in M \mid x \in N\} = N.$$

PROPOSITION 2.1.18.

Let $(G_1, *)$ and (G_2, \circ) be abelian groups and let $f: G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be a function. Then f is group homomorphism if and only if, it is left Z -homomorphism.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that $f: (G_1, *) \rightarrow (G_2, \circ)$ is group homomorphism, thus $f(a * b) = f(a) \circ f(b)$, for all $a, b \in G_1$. Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $a \in G_1$, thus $f(n.a) = f(\underbrace{a * a * \dots * a}_{n\text{-time}}) = (\underbrace{f(a) \circ f(a) \circ \dots \circ f(a)}_{n\text{-time}}) = n.f(a)$. Thus f is left \mathbb{Z} -homomorphism.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that $f: (G_1, *) \rightarrow (G_2, \circ)$ is \mathbb{Z} -homomorphism, thus for all $x, y \in G_1$, we have that $f(x * y) = f(x) \circ f(y)$. Hence f is group homomorphism.

PROPOSITION 2.1.19.

Let V_1 and V_2 be vector spaces over a field F and let $f: V_1 \rightarrow V_2$ be a function. Then f is a left F -homomorphism if and only if, it is linear transformation over F .

Proof. (Exercise).

EXAMPLE 2.1.20. [Dummit and Foote, p. 346]

Let $f: (\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ defined by $f(x) = 2x$, for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then f is a left \mathbb{Z} -module homomorphism but it is not ring homomorphism, since $f(1) = 2 \neq 1 = f(1/2)$, $1/2 \notin \mathbb{Z}$.

EXAMPLE 2.1.21.

Let R be a ring. Define $f: R \rightarrow M_{2 \times 2}(R)$ by $f(x) = \begin{pmatrix} x & 0 \\ 0 & x \end{pmatrix}$, for all $x \in R$. Then f is a left R -monomorphism.

Proof. H.W.

PROPOSITION 2.1.22.

Let $\alpha: N \rightarrow M$ be a left R -homomorphism. Then α is R -monomorphism if, $\ker(\alpha) = \{N0\}$.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that α is R -monomorphism. Let $x \in \ker(\alpha)$, thus $\alpha(x) = M0$. Since $\alpha(N0) = M0$, thus $\alpha(N0) = \alpha(x)$. Since α is a R -monomorphism $x = N0 \Rightarrow \ker(\alpha) = \{N0\}$.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that $\ker(\alpha) = \{N0\}$. Let $x, y \in N$ such that $\alpha(x) = \alpha(y) \Rightarrow \alpha(x) - \alpha(y) = M0 \Rightarrow \alpha(x - y) = M0 \Rightarrow x - y \in \ker(\alpha)$. Since $\ker(\alpha) = \{N0\} \Rightarrow x - y = N0 \Rightarrow x = y \Rightarrow \alpha$ is a R -monomorphism.

THEOREM 2.1.23.

Let M, N be to two R -modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +', \cdot')$ be a R -homomorphism. Then:

1. f is a R -monomorphism if and only if, for any R -module A and any two R -homomorphism, $\alpha_1, \alpha_2: A \rightarrow M$ such that $f \circ \alpha_1 = f \circ \alpha_2$ implies $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$.
2. f is a R -epimorphism if and only if, for any R -module B and any R -homomorphism $\beta_1, \beta_2: N \rightarrow B$ such that $\beta_1 \circ f = \beta_2 \circ f$ implies $\beta_1 = \beta_2$.

Proof:-

1-(\Rightarrow) If f is a R -monomorphism, f is a R -homomorphism & 1-1.

Let A be any R -module of N and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2: A \rightarrow M$ be any two homomorphism such that $f \circ \alpha_1 = f \circ \alpha_2$.

To proof $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$. Since $f \circ \alpha_1 = f \circ \alpha_2 \therefore \forall \alpha \in A, (f \circ \alpha_1)(x) = (f \circ \alpha_2)(x) \Rightarrow f(\alpha_1(x)) = f(\alpha_2(x))$.
 $\therefore \alpha_1(x) = \alpha_2(x), \forall x \in A$ (since f is a R -monomorphism) $\Rightarrow \therefore \alpha_1 = \alpha_2$.

(\Leftarrow) To proof f is a R -monomorphism. Let $m_1, m_2 \in M$ such that $f(m_1) = f(m_2)$, we have to show that $m_1 = m_2$? $f(m_1) = f(m_2) \Rightarrow f(m_1 - m_2) = 0$.

Let $A = (m_1 - m_2) = R(m_1 - m_2)$ be the submodule of M generated by $(m_1 - m_2)$.

Let α_1 be the mapping R -homomorphism from A into M

i.e. $\alpha_1: R(m_1 - m_2) \rightarrow M \ni \alpha_1(x) = x, \forall x \in R(m_1 - m_2)$.

Let α_2 be the mapping R -homomorphism from A into M

i.e. $\alpha_2: R(m_1 - m_2) \rightarrow M \ni \alpha_2(x) = 0, \forall x \in R(m_1 - m_2)$.

Let $x \in R(m_1 - m_2) \Rightarrow x = r(m_1 - m_2), r \in R$

$$\begin{aligned} (f \circ \alpha_1)(x) &= (f \circ \alpha_1)(r(m_1 - m_2)) = f(\alpha_1(r(m_1 - m_2))), \text{ since } \alpha_1(x) = x \\ &= f(r(m_1 - m_2)) = r.f(m_1 - m_2) \quad \text{since } f \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism.} \\ &= r.m_0 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

$$(f \circ \alpha_2)(x) = f(\alpha_2(r(m_1 - m_2))) = f(0) = 0 \quad \text{since } f \text{ is a } R\text{-homomorphism}$$

$$\Rightarrow (f \circ \alpha_1)(x) = (f \circ \alpha_2)(x), \forall x \in A. \therefore f \circ \alpha_1 = f \circ \alpha_2, \text{ since } \alpha_1 = \alpha_2 \quad \text{by hyp.}$$

$$\therefore \alpha_1(x) = \alpha_2(x), \forall x \in A. \therefore \alpha_1(r(m_1 - m_2)) = \alpha_2(r(m_1 - m_2)); r \in R. \alpha_1(m_1 - m_2) = \alpha_2(m_1 - m_2).$$

If $r = 1$, since $\forall r \in R, m_1 - m_2 = 0. \therefore m_1 = m_2 \therefore f$ is a R -monomorphism.

2-(\Rightarrow) If f is a R -epimorphism, let B be any R -module of M and $\beta_1, \beta_2: N \rightarrow B$ be any two homomorphism $\ni \beta_1 \circ f = \beta_2 \circ f$. To proof $\beta_1 = \beta_2$,

Suppose that $\beta_1 \neq \beta_2, \therefore \exists x \in N$ such that $\beta_1(x) \neq \beta_2(x) \dots \dots \dots (1)$

Since f is a R -epimorphism and $x \in N \Rightarrow \exists m \in M$ such that $f(m) = x \dots \dots \dots (2)$

From (1) and (2) $\Rightarrow \beta_1(f(m)) \neq \beta_2(f(m)). \therefore \beta_1 \circ f(m) \neq \beta_2 \circ f(m), m \in M. \therefore \beta_1 \circ f \neq \beta_2 \circ f$, for some $m \in M. \therefore \beta_1 = \beta_2$.

(\Leftarrow) To proof f is a R -epimorphism. We have to show that $\text{Im } f = N$.

Let $B = N/\text{Im}(f), f: M \rightarrow N \therefore \text{Im } f \subseteq N$ by define of $\text{Im } f$.

Let $\beta_1: N \rightarrow N/\text{Im}(f)$ to the natural homomorphism. *i.e.* $\beta_1 = \pi_1: N \rightarrow N/\text{Im}(f), \beta_1(x) = x + \text{Im } f, \forall x \in N$.

Let $\beta_2: N \rightarrow N/\text{Im}(f)$ to the zero homomorphism *i.e.* $\beta_2(x) = \bar{0} = \text{Im}(f), \forall x \in N$.

$$(\beta_1 \circ f)(m) = \beta_1(f(m)) = f(m) + \text{Im } f = \text{Im}(f), \forall m \in M, \text{ since } f(m) \subseteq \text{Im } f.$$

$$\text{And } (\beta_2 \circ f)(m) = \beta_2(f(m)) = \bar{0} = \text{Im}(f), \forall m \in M. \therefore (\beta_1 \circ f)(m) = (\beta_2 \circ f)(m), \forall m \in M.$$

$$\beta_1 \circ f = \beta_2 \circ f \Rightarrow \beta_1 = \beta_2 \text{ by hyp. } \therefore \beta_1(x) = \beta_2(x), \forall x \in N. \therefore x + \text{Im } f = \text{Im } f, \forall x \in N.$$

$$\therefore x \in \text{Im } f, \forall x \in N \Rightarrow N \subseteq \text{Im } f. \text{ But } \text{Im } f \subseteq N \Rightarrow N = \text{Im } f \Rightarrow f \text{ is a } R\text{-epimorphism.}$$

QUOTIENT MODULES

PROPOSITION 2.2.1.

Let R be a ring, let M be a left R -module and let N be a left submodule of M . The (additive, abelian) quotient group M/N can be made into a left R -module by defining a module multiplication $\alpha: R \times M/N \rightarrow M/N$ by: $\alpha(r) = r \cdot (x + N) = (r \cdot x) + N$, for all $r \in R, x + N \in M/N$.

Proof. [Dummit and Foote, Proposition 3, p. 348].

Since M is an abelian group under $+$ the quotient group M/N is defined and is an abelian group. To see that the multiplication α is well defined, suppose $x + N = y + N$, i.e., $x - y \in N$. Since N is a left R -submodule, $r \cdot (x - y) \in N$. Thus $r \cdot x - r \cdot y \in N \Rightarrow r \cdot x + N = r \cdot y + N$. Thus α is a well-defined.

Since $\alpha: R \times M/N \rightarrow M/N$ such that $(r, x + N) \mapsto r \cdot x + N, \forall x + N, y + N \in M/N$ and $r, r_1, r_2 \in R$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i- } (r_1 + r_2, x + N) &= (r_1 + r_2) \cdot (x + N) = (r_1 + r_2) \cdot x + N = (r_1 \cdot x + r_2 \cdot x) + N = (r_1 \cdot x + N) \oplus (r_2 \cdot x + N) \\ &= (r_1 \cdot (x + N)) \oplus (r_2 \cdot (x + N)) = (r_1, x + N) \oplus (r_2, x + N). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii- } (r_1 \cdot r_2, x + N) &= (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot (x + N) = (r_1 \cdot r_2) \cdot x + N = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot x) + N = r_1 \cdot (r_2 \cdot x + N) \\ &= r_1 \cdot (r_2, (x + N)) = (r_1, (r_2, x + N)). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{iii- } (r, (x + N) \oplus (y + N)) &= r \cdot ((x + N) \oplus (y + N)) = r \cdot ((x + y) + N) = r \cdot (x + y) + N \\ &= (r \cdot x + r \cdot y) + N = (r \cdot x + N) \oplus (r \cdot y + N) = (r \cdot (x + N)) \oplus (r \cdot (y + N)) \\ &= (r, (x + N)) \oplus (r, (y + N)). \end{aligned}$$

$\therefore M/N$ is a R -module.

DEFINITION 2.2.2.

The left R -module M/N is defined in Proposition (2.2.1) is called **quotient (or factor) module**.

REMARK 2.2.3.

1- A right R -modules can be defined analogously as follows.

2- If the ring R is commutative, then a module M is left R -module if and only if it is a right R -module.

DEFINITION 2.2.4.

Let M be a R -module. Let N be a submodule of M . $(M, +)$ commutative group ($r \cdot x \in M, r \in R, x \in M$). $(N, +)$ is commutative group of $(M, +) \Rightarrow (N, +) \triangleleft (M, +)$. Let

$M/N = \{ a + N : a \in M \}$. Define \oplus, \odot on M/N as $\forall a + N, b + N \in M/N$,
 $(a + N) \oplus (b + N) = (a + b) + N$ and $r \odot (a + N) = r \cdot a + N, \forall r \in R, a + N \in M/N$.

$\therefore (M/N, \oplus, \odot)$ called **the quotient module M by N** .

PROPOSITION 2.2.5.

Let $(M, +, \cdot)$ be a left R -module. N is a submodule of M . Then:

- (1) If M is commutative module $\Rightarrow M/N$ is commutative module.
- (2) If M has unity $1 \Rightarrow M/N$ has unity $1+N$.

Proof :-

1. Let $a+N, b+N \in M/N, (a+N) \odot (b+N) = ((a \cdot b) + N) = (b \cdot a) + N = (b+N) \odot (a+N)$.
2. Let $(a+N) \odot (1+N) = (a \cdot 1) + N = a+N$. $1+N$ is unity of M/N .

PROPOSITION 2.2.6.

Let M be a R -module and N be a submodule of M . $(M/N, \oplus)$ is a commutative group.

Proof:-

Since $(M, +)$ is abelian group and $(N, +)$ is a subgroup of $M \Rightarrow N \leq M \Rightarrow (M/N, +)$ is an abelian group. $\therefore (M/N, \oplus)$ is a commutative group. R -homomorphism. Then M_2/M_1 is a left submodule of M/M_1

REMARK 2.2.8.

Let M be a R -module and N be a submodule of M . In a R -module $(M/N, \oplus, \odot)$, N is the zero element of the module M/N .

EXAMPLES 2.2.9.

1- Let $M=Z$ and $N=Z_e = E$, $M/N = Z/E = \{a + E : a \in Z\} = \{0+E, 1+E\} = \{E, o\} \cong Z_2$

In general, the quotient module, n is a positive integer

$$Z / \langle n \rangle = \begin{cases} Z_p, & \text{if } n \text{ is prime number} \\ Z_n, & \text{if } n \text{ is not prime number} \end{cases}$$

$$\{ \bar{0} \} = 0 + Z, \quad \text{if } n = \bar{1}$$

$$Z \quad \text{if } n = 0$$

2- $Q/Z = \left\{ \left(\frac{a}{b} \right) + Z : a, b \in Z \text{ and } b \neq 0 \right\}$. It is the quotient module of Q by Z . Prove that Q/Z is an unital Z -module.

1- Since $(Q, +)$ is abelian group and $(Z, +)$ is a subgroup of $Q \Rightarrow Z \leq Q \Rightarrow (Q/Z, +)$ is abelian group.

2- $\exists \alpha : Z \times Q/Z \rightarrow Q/Z$ such that $(n, \frac{a}{b} + Z) \rightarrow n \cdot \frac{a}{b} + Z$ and for all $\frac{a}{b}, \frac{a_1}{b_1}, \frac{a_2}{b_2} \in Q/Z$ and $n, n_1, n_2 \in Z$ satisfying :-

$$\text{i) } (n_1 + n_2, \frac{a}{b} + Z) = (n_1 + n_2) \cdot \frac{a}{b} + Z = (n_1 \cdot \frac{a}{b} + n_2 \cdot \frac{a}{b}) + Z = ((n_1 \frac{a}{b}) + Z) \oplus ((n_2 \frac{a}{b}) + Z) = (n_1, (\frac{a}{b}) + Z) \oplus (n_2, (\frac{a}{b}) + Z).$$

$$\text{ii) } (n_1 \cdot n_2, \frac{a}{b} + Z) = (n_1 \cdot n_2) \odot (\frac{a}{b} + Z) = n_1 \cdot (n_2 \cdot \frac{a}{b} + Z) = n_1 \cdot (n_2, \frac{a}{b} + Z) = (n_1, (n_2, \frac{a}{b} + Z))$$

$$\text{iii) } (n, (\frac{a_1}{b_1} + Z) \oplus (\frac{a_2}{b_2} + Z)) = (n, (\frac{a_1}{b_1} + \frac{a_2}{b_2}) + Z) = n \cdot (\frac{a_1}{b_1} + \frac{a_2}{b_2}) + Z = (n \cdot \frac{a_1}{b_1} + n \cdot \frac{a_2}{b_2}) + Z = (n, \frac{a_1}{b_1} + Z) \oplus (n, \frac{a_2}{b_2} + Z) \\ = (n, (\frac{a_1}{b_1} + Z)) \oplus (n, (\frac{a_2}{b_2} + Z)).$$

$$\text{iv) } (1, \frac{a}{b} + Z) = (1) \cdot (\frac{a}{b} + Z) = (1 \cdot \frac{a}{b}) + Z = \frac{a}{b} + Z.$$

Q/Z is an unital Z -module.

(The fundamental theorem of module homomorphisms)

The first fundamental theorem for modules

THREOEM 2.2.10.

Let M, N be to two R -modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +, \cdot)$ be a R -homomorphism. Then $(M/\ker f, \oplus, \odot) \cong (\text{Im}(f), +, \cdot)$.

Proof :-

Define $g: M/\ker f \rightarrow \text{Im}(f) \ni g(m+\ker f) = f(m), \forall m \in M$.

Well-defined: Let $a+\ker f, b+\ker f \in M/\ker f, a+\ker f = b+\ker f \Rightarrow a-b \in \ker f \Rightarrow f(a-b) = 0' \Rightarrow f(a) - f(b) = 0' \Rightarrow f(a) = f(b) \Rightarrow g(a+\ker f) = g(b+\ker f)$.

1-1 $g(a+\ker f) = g(b+\ker f) \Rightarrow f(a) = f(b) \Rightarrow f(a) - f(b) = 0' \Rightarrow f(a-b) = 0' \Rightarrow a-b \in \ker f \Rightarrow (a+\ker f) = (b+\ker f)$.

onto $\forall y \in \text{Im}(f)$ such that $f(a) = y, \exists a+\ker f \in M/\ker f, g(a+\ker f) = f(a)$.

R-homomorphism $\forall r \in R,$

1. $g[(a+\ker f) \oplus (b+\ker f)] = g[(a+b) + \ker f] = g[(a+b) + \ker f] = f(a+b) = f(a) + f(b) = g(a+\ker f) + g(b+\ker f)$

2. $g[r \odot (a+\ker f)] = g[(r \cdot a) + \ker f] = f(r \cdot a) = r \cdot f(a) = r \cdot g(a+\ker f)$.

$\therefore M/\ker f \cong \text{Im}(f)$.

COROLLARY 2.2.11.

Let M, N be to two R -modules such that $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +, \cdot)$ be a R -epimorphism. Then $(M/\ker f, \oplus, \odot) \cong (N, +, \cdot)$.

EXAMPLE 2.2.12.

Consider the ring $(M, +, \cdot)$ where $M = \{0, \pm 3, \pm 6, \dots\}$. let $S = \{0, \pm 6, \pm 12, \dots\}$. Is S an submodule of M , Find M/S ?

Solution:-

$0 \in S \Rightarrow \emptyset \neq S \subseteq M$ let $a, b \in S; a = 6k, b = 6m, k, m \in \mathbb{Z}$

1. $a+b = 6k + 6m = 6(k+m) \in S$

2. Let $r \in M \ni r = 3m; m \in \mathbb{Z}$

$r \cdot a = 3m \cdot 6k = 6(3mk) \in S$, and $a \cdot r = 6k \cdot 3m = 6(3mk) \in S$. $\therefore S$ is submodule of M .

$M/S = \{a: a \in M, f(a) = a+S\}$

$0+S = S, 3+S = \{3, 9, -3, 15, -9, 21, -15, \dots\} = 3+S$. $M/S = \{0+S, 3+S\}$. $\therefore M/S \cong \mathbb{Z}_2$.

EXAMPLE 2.2.13.

Consider the module $(\mathbb{Z}_{12}, +_{12}, \cdot_{12})$. $I = \{0, 4, 8\}$. I is submodule of \mathbb{Z}_{12} . Find

a) All element of \mathbb{Z}_{12}/I ? b) construct the table $(\mathbb{Z}_{12}/I, \oplus)$? c) Is \mathbb{Z}_{12}/I has unity?

Solution:-

a- $0+I = I = \{0, 4, 8\}, 1+I = \{1, 5, 9\}, 2+I = \{2, 6, 10\}, 3+I = \{3, 7, 11\}$

$\mathbb{Z}_{12}/I = \{0+I, 1+I, 2+I, 3+I\}$.

b.

\oplus	0+I	1+I	2+I	3+I	\odot	0+I	1+I	2+I	3+I
----------	-----	-----	-----	-----	---------	-----	-----	-----	-----

0+I	0+I	1+I	2+I	3+I
1+I	1+I	2+I	3+I	0+I
2+I	2+I	3+I	0+I	1+I
3+I	3+I	0+I	1+I	2+I

0+I	0+I	0+I	0+I	0+I
1+I	0+I	1+I	2+I	3+I
2+I	0+I	2+I	0+I	2+I
3+I	0+I	3+I	2+I	1+I

c. unity 1+I

PROPOSITION 2.2.14.

Let M_1, M_2 be two left R -submodules of a left R -module M such that $M_1 \subseteq M_2$, $f: (M_1, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M_2, +, \cdot)$ be a R -homomorphism. Then M_2/M_1 is a left submodule of M/M_1 .

Proof.

For any $x + M_1 \in M_2/M_1 \Rightarrow x + M_1 \in M/M_1$, since $M_2 \subseteq M$. $\therefore M_2/M_1 \subseteq M/M_1$, $0 + M_1 \in M_2/M_1 \Rightarrow M_2/M_1 \neq \emptyset$.

Let $x + M_1, y + M_1 \in M_2/M_1 \Rightarrow (x+y) + M_1 \in M/M_1$, since for all $r \in R, x \in M \Rightarrow r.x + M_1 \in M_2/M_1$. Since M_2 is a left submodule of $M \Rightarrow M_2/M_1$ is a left submodule of M/M_1 .

The second fundamental theorem for modules

THEOREM 2.2.15.

Let M_1, M_2 be two left R -submodules of a left R -module M such that $M_1 \subseteq M_2$, $f: (M_1, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M_2, +, \cdot)$ be a R -homomorphism. Then $(M/M_1)/(M_2/M_1) \cong M/M_2$.

Proof.

Define $\phi: M/M_1 \rightarrow M/M_2$ by $\phi(x + M_1) = x + M_2$, for all $x + M_1 \in M/M_1$.

Well-defined: Suppose that $x + M_1 = y + M_1$, where $x, y \in M$. Thus $x - y \in M_1$. Since $M_1 \subseteq M_2 \Rightarrow x - y \in M_2 \Rightarrow x + M_2 = y + M_2 \Rightarrow \phi(x + M_1) = \phi(y + M_1)$.

onto: Let $x + M_2 \in M/M_2$, thus $x \in M \Rightarrow x + M_1 \in M/M_1$ and $\phi(x + M_1) = x + M_2$.

R-homomorphism: Let $x + M_1, y + M_1 \in M/M_1$ and let $r \in R$. Thus

- 1- $\phi((x + M_1) + (y + M_1)) = \phi((x + y) + M_1) = (x + y) + M_2 = (x + M_2) + (y + M_2) = \phi(x + M_1) + \phi(y + M_1)$.
- 2- $\phi(r \cdot (x + M_1)) = \phi(r \cdot x + M_1) = r \cdot x + M_2 = r \cdot (x + M_2) = r \cdot \phi(x + M_1)$.

By Corollary (2.2.11), $(M/M_1) / \ker(\phi) \cong M/M_2$. Since

$$\ker(\phi) = \{x + M_1 \in M/M_1 \mid \phi(x + M_1) = 0_{(M/M_2)} = M_2\} = \{x + M_1 \in M/M_1 \mid x + M_2 = M_2\} = \{x + M_1 \in M/M_1 \mid x \in M_2\} = M_2/M_1, \text{ Thus } \phi \text{ is 1-1.}$$

Hence $(M/M_1)/(M_2/M_1) \cong M/M_2$.

EXAMPLE 2.2.16.

Since $\langle 4 \rangle \hookrightarrow \langle 2 \rangle \hookrightarrow \mathbb{Z}$, thus theorem (2.2.15) $\Rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/\langle 2 \rangle \cong (\mathbb{Z}/\langle 4 \rangle) / (\langle 2 \rangle / \langle 4 \rangle)$.

The third fundamental theorem for modules

THEOREM 2.2.17.

Let M_1, M_2 be two a left R -submodules of a left R -module M such that $f: (M_1, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M_2, +, \cdot)$ be a R -homomorphism. Then $(M_1 / (M_1 \cap M_2)) \cong (M_1 + M_2) / M_2$.

Proof :-

Define $f: M_1 \rightarrow (M_1+M_2)/M_2$ such that $f(x)=x+M_2, \forall x \in M_1$

Mapping $\forall x \in M_1 \Rightarrow x+0 \in M_1+M_2 \Rightarrow x+M_2 \in (M_1+M_2)/M_2. \therefore f(x) \in (M_1+M_2)/M_2$, since f is closed.

Well-defined If $x_1=x_2 \Rightarrow x_1+M_2 = x_2+M_2 \Rightarrow f(x_1) = f(x_2)$.

R-homomorphism

1- Let $x_1, x_2 \in M_1, f(x_1+x_2) = (x_1+x_2)+M_2 = (x_1+M_2)+(x_2+M_2) = f(x_1)+f(x_2)$.

2- Let $r \in R$ & $x \in M_1, f(r.x) = r.x+M_2 = r.(x+M_2) = r.f(x)$.

onto Let $(x+y)+M_2 \in (M_1+M_2)/M_2$ where $x \in M_1$ and $y \in M_2$

$(x+y)+M_2 = (x+M_2)+(y+M_2) = (x+M_2)+M_2 = x+M_2 = f(x)$.

\therefore By the first fundamental theorem (2.2.10) $\Rightarrow M_1/\ker f \cong (M_1+M_2)/M_2$.

$\ker f = \{x \in M_1 : f(x) = 0\} = \{x \in M_1 : x+M_2 = M_2\} = \{x \in M_1 : x \in M_2\} = M_1 \cap M_2$

$\therefore M_1/(M_1 \cap M_2) \cong (M_1+M_2)/M_2$.

COROLLARY 2.2.18.

Let M_1, M_2 be two a left R -submodules of a left R -module M such that $f: (M_1, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (M_2, +, \cdot)$ be a R -homomorphism. If $M = M_1 \oplus M_2$, then $M/M_2 \cong M_1$.

Proof :-

$M/M_2 = (M_1 \oplus M_2)/M_2 \cong M_1/(M_1 \cap M_2)$, by Theorem (2.2.17). Since $M_1 \cap M_2 = 0$

$\Rightarrow M/M_2 = M_1/0 = M_1$.

Chapter Three

TORSION SUBMODULES

DEFINITION 3.1.1.

A R-module M is called **divisible R-module M** if and only if, $r.M = M, \forall 0 \neq r \in R$.
i.e. M is divisible $\Leftrightarrow \forall m \in M$ and $\forall 0 \neq r \in R, \exists x \in M$ such that $m = r.x$.

EXAMPLES 3.1.2.

2 is not divisible elements in Z as a Z-modules. Since let $r=3$ in Z, then $\nexists x \in Z$ such that $2=3.x$
 The only divisible elements in Z is zero, since $\forall r \in Z, 0=r.0$.

EXAMPLES 3.1.3.

Q is a divisible Z-module. Let $m = \frac{a}{b} \in Q$ and $0 \neq r \in Z, x \in Q \ni m = r.x$??
 Let $x = \frac{a}{rb} \in Q$ and $\frac{a}{b} = r \cdot \frac{a}{rb}$.

DEFINITION 3.1.4.

Let M be a R-module and Let m be element in M. m is called **a torsion element in R-module M** if there exists a non-zero element $r \in R$ such that $r.m=0$.

EXAMPLES 3.1.5.

- (1) $3 \in Z$ is not torsion since $3r \neq 0, \forall 0 \neq r \in R$. Z has no to torsion elements .
- (2) Every non-zero elements in Z_4 as a Z-module is torsion $0.4=0, 1.4=4=0, 2.4=8=0, 3.4=12=0$.

DEFINITION 3.1.6.

Let M be a R-module and let $T(M) = \{m \in M : r.m=0, \text{ for some } 0 \neq r \in R\}$.
 =The set of a torsion elements in M. T(M) is called **the torsion submodule of R-module M** .

REMARK 3.1.7.

- 1- M is called torsion-free, if $T(M) = \{0\}$.
- 2- M is called torsion module, if $T(M) = M$.

EXAMPLES 3.1.8.

- 1- Z is a torsion-free Z -module $T(Z)=0$.
- 2- Z_n is a torsion Z -module since $T(Z_n)=Z_n$.

PROPOSITION 3.1.9.

$T(M)$ is a submodule of M .

Proof:-

- (1) $T(M) \neq \emptyset$, since $0 \in T(M), r.0=0, \forall r \in R$.
- $T(M) \subseteq M$, since $r.m \in T(M), r.m \in M$, by define of $T(M)$. Let $m_1, m_2 \in T(M) \Rightarrow r.m_1=0, r.m_2=0$. Then
 - 1- $r.(m_1 - m_2) = r.m_1 - r.m_2 = 0 - 0 = 0$, for some $r \in R$. $\therefore m_1 - m_2 \in T(M)$.
 - 2- Let $k \in R, m \in T(M) \Rightarrow r.m=0$, for some $r \in R$. $r.(k.m) = (r.k).m = (k.r).m = k.(r.m) = k.0 = 0$. $\Rightarrow k.m \in T(M)$. $\therefore T(M)$ is a submodule of M .

PROPOSITION 3.1.10.

For any R -module M , prove that $M/T(M)$ is torsion-free .

Proof :-

- Let $m+T(M) \in M/T(M)$ and suppose $m+T(M)$ is torsion element of $M/T(M)$.
- $\Rightarrow \exists 0 \neq r \in R$ such that $r.(m+T(M)) = T(M) \Rightarrow r.m+T(M) = T(M)$.
 - $\Rightarrow r.m \in T(M)$ (by $a \times H = H \Leftrightarrow a \in H$).
 - $\Rightarrow \exists 0 \neq s \in R$ such that $s.(r.m) = 0 \Rightarrow (s.r).m = 0$. $\therefore m \in T(M) \Rightarrow m+T(M) = T(M)$.
 - \Rightarrow The element of $T(M)$ is only torsion element of $M/T(M)$.
 - $\therefore T(M/T(M)) = \{0\} = T(M)$. $\Rightarrow M/T(M)$ is torsion free.

PROPOSITION 3.1.11.

Let M and N be two R -modules and Let $f: (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +, \cdot)$ be a R -homomorphism . Prove that

- a) If M is a torsion module, then $T(N) \supseteq \text{Im } f$.
- b) If N is torsion-free, then $T(M) \subseteq \ker f$.
- c) Find $\text{Hom}_Z(Z, Q), \text{Hom}_Z(Z_n, Z), \text{Hom}_Z(Z, Z)$, and $\text{Hom}_Z(Q, Z)$

Proof :-

- a) Let $x \in \text{Im } f \Rightarrow x = f(m), \forall m \in M$. Since M torsion modules $\Rightarrow \forall m \in M, \exists r \in R$ such that $r.m = 0$. $r.x = r.f(m) = f(r.m) = f(0) = 0'$ since f is homomorphism . $\therefore x \in N \Rightarrow \text{Im } f \subseteq T(N)$.
- b) Let $m \in T(M) \Rightarrow \exists 0 \neq r \in R$ such that $r.m = 0$, for some $m \in M$. $r.f(m) = f(r.m) = f(0) = 0'$, since f homomorphism.
- $\therefore f(m) \in T(N)$ and since $T(N) = \{0\}$ is torsion-free, $f(m) = 0 \Rightarrow m \in \ker f \Rightarrow T(M) \subseteq \ker f$.

c)

1- $\text{Hom}_Z(Z, Q)$, Since Q is a Z -module and since $\text{Hom}_R(R, M) \cong M$, for any R -module M , therefore $\text{Hom}(Z, Q) \cong Q$.

2- $\text{Hom}_Z(Z_n, Z)$. $Z_n = \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}, \dots, \overline{n-1}\}$ is a Z -module. Let $f \in \text{Hom}(Z_n, Z) \therefore f: Z_n \rightarrow Z$ is a Z -homomorphism. Let $f(\bar{1}) = x \in Z$. Since f is a homomorphism $\Rightarrow f(0) = 0$.

$\therefore 0 = f(\bar{n}) = f(n.\bar{1}) = n.f(\bar{1}) = n.x$. But Z is an integral domain and $n.x = 0 \Rightarrow x = 0$.

$\therefore f(\bar{1}) = 0$. But $\bar{1}$ is a generator of $Z_n \therefore f(\bar{a}) = (a.\bar{1}) = a.f(\bar{1}) = 0, \forall \bar{a} \in Z_n$. $\therefore f = 0 \therefore \text{Hom}_Z(Z_n, Z) = 0$

3- $\text{Hom}_Z(Z, Z) \cong Z$. and note that $\text{Hom}_Z(Q, Z) = \text{Hom}_Z(M, R) = M^* = Q^*$.

4- Let $f \in \text{Hom}_Z(Q, Z)$. let $0 \neq x \in Q$. Since Q is a divisible Z -module.

$\therefore \forall 0 \neq r \in Z, \exists y \in Q$ such that $x = r.y$. $\therefore f(x) = f(r.y) = r.f(y)$, since f is homomorphism.

$f(x) = r.f(y) \in Z$. $\therefore f(x)$ is a divisible element in Z .

But 0 is the only divisible element in Z . $\therefore f(x) = 0, \forall x \in Q \Rightarrow f = 0 \Rightarrow \text{Hom}(Q, Z) = 0$.

DIRECT SUM DIRECT AND PRODUCT OF MODULES

REMARK 3.2.1.

Let $\{N_1, N_2, \dots, N_n\}$ be a family of submodules of a left R -modules M . Then

$\sum_{i \in I} N_i = \{ \sum_{i \in I}^n a_i \mid a_i \in N_i \}$. **Where** (Let $\{N_i \mid i \in I\}$ be a family of submodules of a left R -module M .)

We will use the notation $\sum_{i \in I} N_i$ to denote **the sum of the submodules** $\{N_i \mid i \in I\}$ and defined by

$\sum_{i \in I} N_i = \langle \cup_{i \in I} N_i \rangle$.

DEFINITION 3.2.2. (Internal direct sum)

Let M be a left R -module and let $\{N_i \mid i \in I\}$ be a family of left submodules of M . We say that M is the **internal direct sum of the submodules** $\{N_i \mid i \in I\}$ and denoted by $M = \bigoplus_{i \in I} N_i$ if the following two conditions are hold:

(1) $M = \sum_{i \in I} N_i$ and

(2) $N_j \cap \sum_{i \neq j} N_i = 0$, for all $j \in I$.

In case I is a finite set (for example $I = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$), then $M = N_1 \oplus N_2 \oplus \dots \oplus N_n$.

EXAMPLES 3.2.3.

Let $M = R^3$ as a left R -module and let $N_1 = \{(x, 0, 0) \mid x \in R\}$, $N_2 = \{(0, y, 0) \mid y \in R\}$ and $N_3 = \{(0, 0, z) \mid z \in R\}$. Prove that:

(1) N_1, N_2 and N_3 are left submodules of M ;

(2) M is the internal direct sum of the submodules N_1, N_2 and N_3 .

Proof.

(1) **Exercise**

(2) Since N_1, N_2 and N_3 are left submodules of $M \Rightarrow N_1 + N_2 + N_3 \subseteq M$. Let $a \in M$, thus $a = (x, y, z)$ with $x, y, z \in R \Rightarrow a = (x, 0, 0) + (0, y, 0) + (0, 0, z) \in N_1 + N_2 + N_3 \Rightarrow M \subseteq N_1 + N_2 + N_3$. Thus $M = N_1 + N_2 + N_3$.

Also, $N_1 + N_2 = \{(x, y, 0) \mid x, y \in R\}$, $N_1 + N_3 = \{(x, 0, z) \mid x, z \in R\}$ and $N_2 + N_3 = \{(0, y, z) \mid y, z \in R\}$. Thus $N_1 \cap (N_2 + N_3) = 0$, $N_2 \cap (N_1 + N_3) = 0$, and $N_3 \cap (N_1 + N_2) = 0$. Hence $M = N_1 \oplus N_2 \oplus N_3$.

EXAMPLES 3.2.4.

- 1- Let M be a left R -module. Then M is the internal direct sum of the trivial submodules $\{0\}$, M .
 2- Let $M = Z_6$ as a left Z_6 -module and let $N_1 = \langle 2 \rangle = \{0, 2, 4\}$ and $N_2 = \langle 3 \rangle = \{0, 3\}$. Then M is the internal direct sum of the submodules N_1 and N_2 .

Proof. Exercise

PROPOSITION 3.2.5.

Let M be a left R -module and let $\{N_i \mid i \in I\}$ be a family of left submodules of M . Then the following two statements are equivalent:

(1) $N_j \cap \sum_{i \in I, i \neq j} N_i = 0$, for all $j \in I$.

(2) For every $x \in M$ the representation $x = \sum_{i \in I'} b_i$ with $b_i \in N_i$, $I' \subseteq I$, I' finite, is unique in the following sense: If $x = \sum_{i \in I'} b_i = \sum_{i \in I'} c_i$ with $b_i, c_i \in N_i$, then $b_i = c_i$, for all $i \in I'$.

Proof.

(1) \Rightarrow (2). Let $x \in M$ such that $x = \sum_{i \in I'} b_i = \sum_{i \in I'} c_i$ with $b_i, c_i \in N_i$, $I' \subseteq I$, I' finite $\Rightarrow \sum_{i \in I'} b_i - \sum_{i \in I'} c_i$.

Thus for all $j \in I'$, we have that $b_j + \sum_{i \in I', i \neq j} b_i - (c_j + \sum_{i \in I', i \neq j} c_i) = 0 \Rightarrow b_j - c_j = \sum_{i \in I', i \neq j} (c_i - b_i)$.

Since $\sum_{i \in I', i \neq j} (c_i - b_i) \in \sum_{i \in I', i \neq j} N_i \Rightarrow b_j - c_j \in \sum_{i \in I', i \neq j} N_i$. Since $b_j - c_j \in N_j \Rightarrow b_j - c_j \in N_j \cap \sum_{i \in I', i \neq j} N_i$

Since $N_j \cap \sum_{i \in I', i \neq j} N_i \subseteq N_j \cap \sum_{i \in I} N_i$ and since $N_j \cap \sum_{i \in I, i \neq j} N_i = 0 \Rightarrow N_j \cap \sum_{i \in I', i \neq j} N_i = 0 \Rightarrow b_j - c_j = 0$

$\Rightarrow b_j = c_j$, for all $j \in I'$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1). Let $b \in N_j \cap \sum_{i \in I, i \neq j} N_i$, thus $b = b_j \in N_j$ and $b \in \sum_{i \in I, i \neq j} N_i \Rightarrow$ there is a finite subset

$I' \subseteq I$ with $j \notin I'$ and $b = b_j = \sum_{i \in I'} b_i$, $b_i \in N_i$.

If we add to the left-hand side the summands $0 \in N_i$, $i \in I'$ and to the right-hand side the summand $0 \in N_j$, then the same finite index set $I' \cup \{j\}$ appears on both sides and from uniqueness in (2) it follows that $b = b_j = 0$. Thus $N_j \cap \sum_{i \in I, i \neq j} N_i = 0$.

DEFINITION 3.2.6. (direct summand)

Let M be a left R -module and let N be a left submodules of M . We say that M is the **direct summand of M** , if there is a submodule K of M such that $M = N \oplus K$.

In other word, there is a submodule K of M such that $M = N + K$ and $N \cap K = 0$.

EXAMPLE 3.2.7.

Let $M = Z_6$ as a left Z_6 -module. Find all direct summands of M .

Solution: M , $\{0\}$, $N_1 = \langle 2 \rangle = \{0, 2, 4\}$ and $N_2 = \langle 3 \rangle = \{0, 3\}$ are all direct summands of M .

EXAMPLE 3.2.8.

Let F be a field. Find all direct summands of ${}_F F$.

Solution: M and $\{0\}$ are all direct summands of ${}_F F$.

EXAMPLE 3.2.9.

Let $M = Z_{30}$ as a left Z_{30} -module. Find all direct summands of M .

Solution: (Exercise).

PROPOSITION 3.2.10.

Let $M = Z$ as a left Z -module. Prove that $\langle 0 \rangle$ and zZ are the only direct summands of M .

Solution: Assume that N is a direct summand of M with $N \neq 0$ and $N \neq zZ$. Thus $N = \langle n \rangle$ with $n \in Z$ and $n \neq 0, n \neq 1, n \neq -1$. Since N is a direct summand of M , there is a submodule $K = \langle m \rangle$ of M for some $m \in Z$ such that $zZ = \langle n \rangle \oplus \langle m \rangle \Rightarrow \langle n \rangle \cap \langle m \rangle = 0$.

Since $n.m \in \langle n \rangle \cap \langle m \rangle \Rightarrow n.m = 0$. Since $n \neq 0$ and Z is an integral domain $\Rightarrow m = 0$.

Since $zZ = \langle n \rangle + \langle m \rangle \Rightarrow zZ = \langle n \rangle$.

Since either $zZ = \langle 1 \rangle$ or $zZ = \langle -1 \rangle \Rightarrow$ either $n = 1$ or $n = -1$ and this is a contradiction.

Thus $\langle 0 \rangle$ and zZ are the only direct summands of $M = zZ$.

DEFINITION 3.2.11.

A R -module M is called **decomposable** or (**directly decomposable**) if M has a non-zero direct summand which is deferent from M

DEFINITION 3.2.12.

A R -module M is called **indecomposable**, if $\langle 0 \rangle$ and M are direct summands of M .

EXAMPLES 3.2.12.

1- Z_6 as a Z -module is decomposable. Let $N = \langle \bar{3} \rangle = \{0, \bar{3}\}$ and $K = \langle \bar{2} \rangle = \{0, \bar{2}, \bar{4}\}$. N and K are submodules of Z_6 and $N+K = \{0, \bar{2}, \bar{4}, \bar{3}, \bar{5}, \bar{1}\} = Z_6$ and $N \cap K = \langle \bar{0} \rangle$

$\therefore Z_6 = N \oplus K$. Hence Z_6 is decomposable.

2- Z as a Z -module is decomposable. The submodules of the module Z on the ring Z are of the form $n.Z$ where n is a positive integer.

Suppose that Z is decomposable $\therefore Z$ has a non-trivial direct summand say $n.Z$ different from Z . $\Rightarrow n \neq 0$ and $n \neq \bar{1}$ $\therefore Z = n.Z \oplus m.Z$, for some positive integer m .

$\therefore n.Z \cap m.Z = \langle 0 \rangle$. $\Rightarrow n.m \in n.Z$ and $n.m \in m.Z$. $\therefore n.m \in n.Z \cap m.Z = \langle 0 \rangle$. $\therefore n.m = 0 \Rightarrow m = 0$, since $n \neq 0$.

$\therefore n.Z$ is not a direct summand $\Rightarrow Z$ is indecomposable.

REMARK 3.2.13.

Every simple R -module is indecomposable, but the converse is not true.

Since every simple R -module containing a submodule which is $\langle 0 \rangle$ and M (by define of simple R -module) $\Rightarrow \langle 0 \rangle, M$ are direct summands of $M \Rightarrow M$ is indecomposable.

DEFINITION 3.2.14.

Let $\{M_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ be a family of left R -modules, we define :-

1) The canonical projection of $\bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ onto M_μ ; $\mu \in \Lambda$ as follows:

$$f_\mu: \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda \rightarrow M_\mu \text{ such that } f_\mu((m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}) = m_\mu.$$

2) The canonical injection of M_μ into $\bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ as follows :-

$$q_\mu: M_\mu \rightarrow \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda \text{ such that } q_\mu(z) = (m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \lambda \neq \mu \forall \lambda \in \Lambda \\ z_\mu & \text{if } \lambda = \mu \end{cases}$$

PROPOSITION 3.2.15.

Let $\{M_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ be a family of R-modules. Let $f_\mu: \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda \rightarrow M_\mu$ is the canonical projection and

$q_\mu: M_\mu \rightarrow \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ is the canonical injection . Then

1- f_μ is an epimorphism .

2- q_μ is a monomorphism .

Proof:- $\forall m_\lambda, m'_\lambda \in \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda, z, z_1, z_2 \in M_\mu$ and $r \in R$,

1- f_μ is an epimorphism .

Homomorphism :- 1) $f_\mu(m_\lambda + m'_\lambda) = (m + m')_\mu = m_\mu + m'_\mu = f_\mu(m_\lambda) + f_\mu(m'_\lambda)$.

$$2) f_\mu(r.m_\lambda) = r.m_\mu = r.(m)_\mu = r.f_\mu(m_\lambda) .$$

onto :- $\text{Im } f_\mu = \{f_\mu((m_\lambda): m_\lambda \in \bigoplus M_\lambda)\} = \{m_\mu: m_\mu \in M_\mu\} = M_\mu$.

2- q_μ is a monomorphism .

Homomorphism :- 1) $q_\mu(z_1 + z_2) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \lambda \neq \mu \\ z_1 + z_2 & \text{if } \lambda = \mu \end{cases}$
 $= (0_1 + 0_2, \dots, z_1 + z_2, \dots) = (0, 0, \dots, z_1, \dots) \oplus (0, 0, \dots, z_2, \dots) = q_\mu(z_1) \oplus q_\mu(z_2)$.

$$2) q_\mu(r.z) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \lambda \neq \mu \\ r.z_\mu & \text{if } \lambda = \mu \end{cases} = r.q_\mu(z) = (0, 0, \dots, r.z, \dots)$$

$$1-1 :- q_\mu(z_1) = q_\mu(z_2) \Rightarrow \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \lambda \neq \mu \\ z_1 & \text{if } \lambda = \mu \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \lambda \neq \mu \\ z_2 & \text{if } \lambda = \mu \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \lambda \neq \mu \\ z_1 = z_2 & \text{if } \lambda = \mu \end{cases}$$

REMARK 3.2.16. As a especial case :- If $M = M_1 \oplus M_2$, then:-

1) $f_1: M_1 \oplus M_2 \rightarrow M_1$ and $f_2: M_1 \oplus M_2 \rightarrow M_2$ such that $f_1(m_1, m_2) = m_1$ and $f_2(m_1, m_2) = m_2$,

$\forall (m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2$. (f_1 and f_2 are epimorphisms, homomorphism + onto).

2) $q_1: M_1 \rightarrow M_1 \oplus M_2$ and $q_2: M_2 \rightarrow M_1 \oplus M_2$ such that $q_1(m_1) = (m_1, 0)$, $\forall m_1 \in M_1$

and $q_2(m_2) = (0, m_2)$, $\forall m_2 \in M_2$. (q_1 and q_2 are monomorphisms, homomorphism + 1-1). i.e.

$f_1 \circ q_1 = I_{M_1}$ and $f_2 \circ q_2 = I_{M_2}$ and i.e. $f_1 \circ q_1 = I_{M_1}$ and $f_2 \circ q_2 = I_{M_2}$.

$f_1 \circ q_1(m_1) = f_1(m_1, 0) = m_1 = I_{M_1}$ and $f_2 \circ q_2(m_2) = f_2(0, m_2) = m_2 = I_{M_2}$.

Solution :-

$\text{Im } f_1 = \{f_1(m_1, m_2): m_1 \in M_1, m_2 \in M_2\} = \{m_1: m_1 \in M_1\} = M_1$. $\therefore f_1$ onto.

$f_1((m_1 + m_2) + (m'_1 + m'_2)) = f_1(m_1 + m'_1, m_2 + m'_2) = m_1 + m'_1 = f_1(m_1, m_2) + f_1(m'_1, m'_2)$, and

$f_1(r.(m_1, m_2)) = r.m_1 = r.f_1(m_1, m_2)$.

$\therefore f_1$ is homomorphism $\Rightarrow f_1$ is epimorphism .

EXAMPLES 3.2.17.

Let $\{M_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ be a family of R-modules. Let $f_\mu: \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda \rightarrow M_\mu$ is the canonical projection and

$q_\mu: M_\mu \rightarrow \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ is the canonical injection . Prove that $f_\mu \circ q_\mu = I_{M_\mu}$ and $q_\mu \circ f_\mu = 0, \forall \mu \neq \lambda$.

Solution :-

$$f_\mu \circ q_\mu(m_\mu) = f_\mu(q(m_\mu)) = f_\mu((m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}) = f_\mu(0, 0, \dots, m_\mu, 0, \dots) = m_\mu .$$

$$q_\mu \circ f_\mu((m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}) = q_\mu(m_\mu) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \lambda \neq \mu \text{ since } \mu \neq \lambda \\ m_\lambda & \text{if } \lambda = \mu \end{cases} \therefore \lambda \neq \mu \forall \lambda \Rightarrow q_\mu(m_\lambda) = 0.$$

DEFINITION 3.2.18. (the direct product)

Let $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a non-empty family of R -modules, the direct product set $\prod_{i \in I} M_i$ is the Cartesian product : $\prod_{i \in I} M_i = \{ (a_i)_{i \in I} \mid a_i \in M_i, \text{ for all } i \in I \}$ in which $(a_i)_{i \in I} = (b_i)_{i \in I}$ if and only if, $a_i = b_i$, for all $i \in I$.

PROPOSITION 3.2.19

Let $\{M_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ be a non-empty family of left R -modules, $\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ be the Cartesian product of a R -module under the component wise operations of addition and multiplication .

i.e. $(M_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} + (M'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} = (M_\lambda + M'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ and $r \cdot (M_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} = (r \cdot M_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$.

$\forall (M_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}, (M'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ and $r \in R$.

i.e., $(a_i)_{i \in I} + (b_i)_{i \in I} = (a_i + b_i)_{i \in I}$, for all $(a_i)_{i \in I}, (b_i)_{i \in I} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$.

Then $(\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda, +)$ is an abelian group. **(H.W.)**

PROPOSITION 3.2.20.

Let $\{M_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ be a non-empty family of left R -modules, $\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ be the Cartesian product.

$(\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda, +, \cdot)$ is a left R -module .

Proof:- Since $(\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda, +)$ is an abelian group, by proposition (3.2.12).

Define $\cdot : R \times \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda \rightarrow \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ such that $r \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I} \rightarrow (r \cdot a_i)_{i \in I}$. $\forall (a_i)_{i \in I} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda, r \in R$. Then (\cdot) is a module multiplication, since for all $r, s \in R$ and $(a_i)_{i \in I}, (b_i)_{i \in I} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda \Rightarrow$

i) $(r, ((a_i)_{i \in I} + (b_i)_{i \in I})) = r \cdot ((a_i + b_i)_{i \in I}) = ((r \cdot a_i + r \cdot b_i)_{i \in I}) = (r \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I}, r \cdot (b_i)_{i \in I})$.

ii) $(r + s, (a_i)_{i \in I}) = (r + s) \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I} = (r \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I} + s \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I}) = (r \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I}, s \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I})$.

iii) $(r s, (a_i)_{i \in I}) = (rs) \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I} = r \cdot (s \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I}) = r \cdot (s \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I}) = (r, (s \cdot (a_i)_{i \in I}))$.

$\therefore \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ is a R -module .

DEFINITION 3.2.21. (the external direct sum)

Let $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a non-empty family of R -modules, the external direct sum set is denoted by $\coprod_{i \in I} M_i$ and defined as follows: $\coprod_{i \in I} M_i = \{ (x_i)_{i \in I} \in \prod_{i \in I} M_i \mid x_i = 0_{M_i}, \text{ for all } i \text{ but finite many } i \in I \}$.

PROPOSITION 3.2.22.

Let $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a non-empty family of left R -modules, then $\coprod_{i \in I} M_i$ is a submodule of a left R -module $\prod_{i \in I} M_i$.

Proof:-

Since $0_{M_i} \in M_i$, for some $i \in I$, thus $\bar{0} = (0_{M_i})_{i \in I} \in \coprod_{i \in I} M_i$ and hence $\coprod_{i \in I} M_i \neq \emptyset$. It is clear that $\coprod_{i \in I} M_i \subseteq \prod_{i \in I} M_i$. Let $(x_i)_{i \in I}, (y_i)_{i \in I} \in \coprod_{i \in I} M_i$ and $r \in R$, thus $x_i = 0_{M_i}$, for all i but finite many $i \in I$ and $y_i = 0_{M_i}$, for all i but finite many $i \in I$ and hence $(z_i)_{i \in I} \in \coprod_{i \in I} M_i$. Thus

$(x_i)_{i \in I} - (y_i)_{i \in I} \in \coprod_{i \in I} M_i$.

Also, $r \cdot (x_i)_{i \in I} = (r \cdot x_i)_{i \in I} = (w_i)_{i \in I}$ with $w_i = 0_{M_i}$, for all i but finite many $i \in I$. Thus $(w_i)_{i \in I} \in \coprod_{i \in I} M_i$ and hence $r \cdot (x_i)_{i \in I} \in \coprod_{i \in I} M_i$. Therefore, $\coprod_{i \in I} M_i$ is a submodule of a left R -module $\prod_{i \in I} M_i$.

COROLLARY 3.2.23.

If $I = \{1,2,\dots,n\}$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. We will prove that $\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda = \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$.

Proof:- (H.W.)

REMARK 3.2.24.

Let I be a non-empty set and M be a left R -module. Then

$M^I = \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ with $M_i = M$ for every $i \in I$. $M^{(I)} = \coprod_{i \in I} M_i$ with $M_i = M$ for every $i \in I$.

We call M^I the direct product of I copies of M and We call $M^{(I)}$ the direct sum of I copies of M .

DEFINITION 3.2.25. (the direct product)

Let $\{M_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ be a non-empty family of R -modules ,the direct product set $\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ is a R -module under the component wise operations of addition and multiplication .

i.e. $(M_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} + (M'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} = (M_\lambda + M'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ and $r \cdot (M_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} = (r \cdot M_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$

$\forall (M_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}, (M'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ and $r \in R$.

The R -module $\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ is called **the direct product** of the family $\{M_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$.

Note that: The submodule of $\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ consisting of an elements $(M_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ such that $M_\lambda = 0$ except for finite number of $\lambda \in \Lambda$ is called the direct sum of the family $\{M_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ which is denoted by $\bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$. (that is $\bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda = \{(m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda : m_\lambda = 0, \text{ except for a finite number of } \lambda \in \Lambda\}$).

Note that: if λ is a finite set, then $\bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda = \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$.

PROPOSITION 3.2.26.

$\bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ is a submodule of $\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$.

Proof:-

To prove $(M_1 \oplus M_2, +)$ is abelian group, $\exists \alpha: R \times (M_1 \oplus M_2) \rightarrow M_1 \oplus M_2$ such that

$(r, (m_1, m_2)) \rightarrow r \cdot (m_1, m_2) = (r \cdot m_1, r \cdot m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2$. $(0, 0) \in M_1 \oplus M_2, 0 \in M_1$ and $0 \in M_2 \Rightarrow M_1 \oplus M_2 \neq \emptyset$.

Closed : Let $(m_1, m_2), (m'_1, m'_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2 \Rightarrow (m_1, m_2) + (m'_1, m'_2) = (m_1 + m'_1, m_2 + m'_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2$.

Associative : $(m_1, m_2) + \{(m'_1, m'_2) + (m''_1, m''_2)\} = (m_1, m_2) + \{(m'_1 + m''_1, m'_2 + m''_2)\}$

$= \{m_1 + (m'_1 + m''_1), m_2 + (m'_2 + m''_2)\} = \{(m_1 + m'_1) + (m''_1), (m_2 + m'_2) + m''_2\}$

$= (m_1 + m'_1, m_2 + m'_2) + (m''_1, m''_2) = \{(m_1, m_2) + (m'_1, m'_2)\} + (m''_1, m''_2)$.

Identity element: $(0, 0)$ is identity element of $M_1 \oplus M_2$, since $\forall (m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2$

$\Rightarrow (m_1, m_2) + (0, 0) = (m_1 + 0, m_2 + 0) = (m_1, m_2) = (0 + m_1, 0 + m_2) = (0, 0) + (m_1, m_2)$.

Inverse : $\forall (m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2, \exists (m'_1, m'_2) + (m'_1, m'_2) = (0, 0)$, then

$(m_1 + m'_1, m_2 + m'_2) = (0, 0) \Rightarrow m_1 + m'_1 = 0 \Rightarrow m'_1 = -m_1$ and $m_2 + m'_2 = 0 \Rightarrow m'_2 = -m_2$

$\therefore (-m_1, -m_2)$ is an inverse of $(m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2$.

Commutative: $(m_1, m_2) + (m'_1, m'_2) = (m_1 + m'_1, m_2 + m'_2) = (m'_1 + m_1, m'_2 + m_2)$

$= (m'_1, m'_2) + (m_1, m_2)$.

$\therefore (M_1 \oplus M_2, +)$ is commutative group

To prove $(M_1 \oplus M_2, +)$ is a submodule, $\exists \alpha: R \times M_1 \oplus M_2 \rightarrow M_1 \oplus M_2$ such that
 $r.(m_1, m_2) \rightarrow (r.m_1, r.m_2)$. $\forall (m_1, m_2), (m'_1, m'_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2, r \in R \Rightarrow$

i) Let $r_1, r_2 \in R, (m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2$,

$$(r_1 + r_2, (m_1, m_2)) = (r_1 + r_2)(m_1, m_2) = ((r_1 + r_2).m_1, (r_1 + r_2).m_2) = (r_1.m_1 + r_2.m_1, r_1.m_2 + r_2.m_2) \\ = (r_1.m_1, r_1.m_2) + (r_2.m_1, r_2.m_2) = r_1.(m_1, m_2) + r_2.(m_1, m_2)$$

ii) $(r, (m_1, m_2) + (m'_1, m'_2)) = r.((m_1, m_2) + (m'_1, m'_2)) = r.(m_1 + m'_1, m_2 + m'_2)$

$$= (r.(m_1 + m'_1), r.(m_2 + m'_2)) = (r.m_1 + r.m'_1, r.m_2 + r.m'_2) = (r.m_1, r.m_2) + (r.m'_1, r.m'_2) \\ = r.(m_1, m_2) + r.(m'_1, m'_2)$$

iii) Let $r_1, r_2 \in R, (m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2$,

$$\{(r_1 r_2), (m_1, m_2)\} = (r_1 r_2).(m_1, m_2) = ((r_1 + r_2).m_1, (r_1 + r_2).m_2) = r_1.(r_2.m_1), r_1.(r_2.m_2) \\ = r_1.(r_2.m_1, r_2.m_2) = r_1.(r_2.(m_1, m_2))$$

vi) Let $1 \in R, (m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2$,

$$(1, (m_1, m_2)) = (1.m_1, 1.m_2) = (m_1, m_2) = (m_1.1, m_2.1) = ((m_1, m_2), 1)$$

$\therefore M_1 \oplus M_2$ is unital R-module.

Note that: $\bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda \neq \phi$, since $0 \in \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda, m = 0$ except for finite $\bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda \subseteq \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ by define of number of $\lambda \in \Lambda$. Let $(m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ and $(m'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$,

$(m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$ and $(m'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda : m, m' = 0$ except for finite number

$(m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} + (m'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} = (m_\lambda + m'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda : (m_\lambda + m'_\lambda) = 0$, since $m = 0$ & $m' = 0$ except for finite number of $\lambda \in \Lambda$. $(m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} + (m'_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$.

Let $r \in R$ and $(m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda \Rightarrow (m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda : m = 0$ except for finite number of $\lambda \in \Lambda$.

$\Rightarrow r.(m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} = (r.m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda : r.m = 0$ except for finite number of $\lambda \in \Lambda$,

$\Rightarrow (r.m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$. $\therefore \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$ is a submodule of $\prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda$, where

$\bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda = \{(m_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \in \prod_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M_\lambda : m = 0 \text{ except for finite number of } \lambda \in \Lambda\}$.

DEFINITION 3.2.27.

Let $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a family of left R-modules and $j \in I$, we define :-

1) The natural projection of $\prod_{i \in I} M_i$ onto M_j is a mapping $\pi_j: \prod_{i \in I} M_i \rightarrow M_j$ defined by

$$\pi_j((a_i)_{i \in I}) = a_j, \text{ for all } (a_i)_{i \in I} \in \prod_{i \in I} M_i.$$

2) The natural injection of M_j into $\prod_{i \in I} M_i$ is a mapping $i_{M_j}: M_j \rightarrow \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ defined by

$$i_{M_j}(a_j) = (0, 0, \dots, 0, a_j, 0, \dots, 0), \text{ for all } a_j \in M_j. \text{ with } M_i = M \text{ for every } i \in I. M^{(I)} = \prod_{i \in I} M_i$$

3) The natural injection of M_j into $\prod_{i \in I} M_i$ is a mapping $i_{M_j}: M_j \rightarrow \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ defined by

$$i_{M_j}(a_j) = (0, 0, \dots, 0, a_j, 0, \dots, 0), \text{ for all } a_j \in M_j.$$

PROPOSITION 3.2.28.

Let $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a family of left R-modules. Then

1) For each $j \in I$, The natural projection $\pi_j: \prod_{i \in I} M_i \rightarrow M_j$ is a left R-epimorphism.

2) For each $j \in I$, The natural projection $\pi_j \rho: \prod_{i \in I} M_i \rightarrow M_j$ is a left R-epimorphism, where

$\rho: \prod_{i \in I} M_i \rightarrow \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ is the inclusion mapping.

3) For each $j \in I$, The natural injections $i_{M_j}: M_j \rightarrow \prod_{i \in I} M_i$, $\bar{i}_{M_j}: M_j \rightarrow \coprod_{i \in I} M_i$ are left R-monomorphisms and $i_{M_j} = \rho \bar{i}_{M_j}$, where $\rho: \prod_{i \in I} M_i \rightarrow \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ is the inclusion mapping.

Proof. (H.W.)

THEOREM 3.2.29.

Let $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a family of left R-modules. Then $\prod_{i \in I} M_i = \bigoplus_{i \in I} M'_i$, where $M'_i = \{(0, 0, \dots, 0, a_i, 0, 0, \dots) \mid a_i \in M_i\}$, for all $i \in I$ and $M'_i \cong M_i$. In other words, the external direct sum of the modules M_i is equal to the internal direct sum of the submodules M'_i of $\prod_{i \in I} M_i$ isomorphic to M_i .

Proof.

Let $i \in I$. Define $\alpha_i: M_i \rightarrow M'_i$ by $\alpha_i(a_i) = (0, 0, \dots, 0, a_i, 0, 0, \dots)$, for all $a_i \in M_i$. Thus α_i is a left R-isomorphism (H.W.) and hence $M'_i \cong M_i$, for all $i \in I$.

Let $M = \sum_{i \in I} M'_i$ and let $x \in M$, thus $x \in \sum_{i \in I} M'_i$ and hence $x \in \langle \bigcup_{i \in I} M'_i \rangle$. Thus $x = \sum_{i \in I'} a_j$ where $a_j \in M'_j$.

For all $j \in I'$, let $a_j = (0, 0, \dots, 0, b_j, 0, 0, \dots)$, for all $b_j \in M_j$. Since I' is finite, thus $x \in \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ and hence $\sum_{i \in I} M'_i \subseteq \prod_{i \in I} M_i$.

Let $0 \neq (a_i)_{i \in I} \in \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ and let $a_{j_1} \neq 0, a_{j_2} \neq 0, \dots, a_{j_n} \neq 0$, where $j_1, j_2, \dots, j_n \in I$. where as $a_i = 0$, for all other $i \in I$, thus it follows that $(a_i)_{i \in I} = (0, 0, \dots, 0, a_{j_1}, 0, 0, \dots) + (0, 0, \dots, 0, a_{j_2}, 0, 0, \dots) + \dots + (0, 0, \dots, 0, a_{j_n}, 0, 0, \dots) \in M'_{j_1} + M'_{j_2} + \dots + M'_{j_n} \subseteq \sum_{i \in I} M'_i$. Thus $\prod_{i \in I} M_i \subseteq \sum_{i \in I} M'_i$. and hence $\sum_{i \in I} M'_i = \prod_{i \in I} M_i$. Since for each $j \in I$, we have that $M'_j \cap \sum_{i \in I} M'_i = 0$ (H.W.) and hence $M = \bigoplus_{i \in I} M'_i$ and hence $\prod_{i \in I} M_i = \bigoplus_{i \in I} M'_i$.

REMARK 3.2.30.

From now we will denote to the external (or internal) direct sum of the family $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ of left R-modules by $\bigoplus_{i \in I} M_i$ and is called the direct sum of the family $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ of left R-modules.

Proof. (H.W.)

PROPOSITION 3.2.31.

Let $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ and $\{N_i\}_{i \in I}$ be two families of left R-modules and $\alpha_i: M_i \rightarrow N_i$ be a left R-homomorphisms, for all $i \in I$. Then

- 1) The mapping $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i: \prod_{i \in I} M_i \rightarrow \prod_{i \in I} N_i$ defined by $(\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i)((a_i)_{i \in I}) = (\alpha_i(a_i)_{i \in I})$, for all $(a_i)_{i \in I} \in \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ is a left R-homomorphism.
- 2) The mapping $\bigoplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i: \bigoplus_{i \in I} M_i \rightarrow \bigoplus_{i \in I} N_i$ defined by $(\bigoplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i)((a_i)_{i \in I}) = (\alpha_i(a_i)_{i \in I})$, for all $(a_i)_{i \in I} \in \bigoplus_{i \in I} M_i$ is a left R-homomorphism.

Proof.

(1) Let $(a_i)_{i \in I}, (b_i)_{i \in I} \in \prod_{i \in I} M_i$ and $r \in R$. Thus $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i((a_i)_{i \in I} + (b_i)_{i \in I}) = \prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i((a_i + b_i)_{i \in I})$
 $= (\alpha_i (a_i + b_i)_{i \in I}) = (\alpha_i (a_i)_{i \in I}) + (\alpha_i (b_i)_{i \in I}) = \prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i((a_i)_{i \in I}) + \prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i (b_i)_{i \in I}$

Also, $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i(r.(a_i)_{i \in I}) = \prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i((r.a_i)_{i \in I}) = (\alpha_i (r.a_i)_{i \in I}) = (r.\alpha_i (a_i)_{i \in I}) = r. \prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i((a_i)_{i \in I})$.
 $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is a left R-homomorphism.

(2) (H.W.) .

PROPOSTION 3.2.32.

Let $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ and $\{N_i\}_{i \in I}$ be two families of left R-modules and $\alpha_i: M_i \rightarrow N_i$ be a left R-homomorphisms, for all $i \in I$. Then

- 1) $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is monomorphism if and only if, for each $i \in I$, α_i is monomorphism.
- 2) $\oplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is monomorphism if and only if, for each $i \in I$, α_i is monomorphism.
- 3) $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is epimorphism if and only if, for each $i \in I$, α_i is epimorphism.
- 4) $\oplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is epimorphism if and only if, for each $i \in I$, α_i is epimorphism.
- 5) $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is isomorphism if and only if, for each $i \in I$, α_i is isomorphism.
- 6) $\oplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is isomorphism if and only if, for each $i \in I$, α_i is isomorphism.

Proof.

(1) (\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is monomorphism, let $j \in I$ and let $a_j, b_j \in M_j$ such that $\alpha_j (a_j) = \alpha_j (b_j)$. Put $a_i = b_i = 0$, for all $i \in I$ and $i \neq j$, thus $\alpha_i (a_i) = \alpha_i (b_i) = 0$, for all $i \in I$ and $i \neq j$, hence $(\alpha_i (a_i)_{i \in I}) = (\alpha_i (b_i)_{i \in I})$. Thus $(\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i (a_i)_{i \in I}) = (\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i (b_i)_{i \in I})$. Since $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is monomorphism, $(a_i)_{i \in I} = (b_i)_{i \in I}$ and hence $a_j = b_j$. Therefore α_j is monomorphism, for each $j \in I$.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that α_i is monomorphism, for each $i \in I$. Let $j \in I$ and let $(a_i)_{i \in I}, (b_i)_{i \in I} \in \prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ such that $(\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i (a_i)_{i \in I}) = (\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i (b_i)_{i \in I})$, hence $(\alpha_i (a_i)_{i \in I}) = (\alpha_i (b_i)_{i \in I})$, thus $\alpha_i (a_i) = \alpha_i (b_i)$, for all $i \in I$. Since α_i is monomorphism, for each $i \in I$, $a_i = b_i$, for all $i \in I$ and hence $(a_i)_{i \in I} = (b_i)_{i \in I}$. Therefore $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is monomorphism.

(2) By similar way of (1) above.

(3) By similar way of (4) above.

(4) (\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\oplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is epimorphism and let $j \in I$. We will prove that $\alpha_j: M_j \rightarrow N_j$ is epimorphism. Let $b_j \in N_j$, thus $(0, 0, \dots, 0, b_j, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \in \oplus_{i \in I} N_j$. Since $\oplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is epimorphism, there is $(a_i)_{i \in I} \in \oplus_{i \in I} M_j$ such that $(\oplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i)((a_i)_{i \in I}) = (0, 0, \dots, 0, b_j, 0, 0, \dots, 0)$. Thus $(\alpha_i)((a_i)_{i \in I}) = (0, 0, \dots, 0, b_j, 0, 0, \dots, 0)$ and hence $\alpha_j (a_j) = b_j$ with $a_j \in M_j$. Thus $\alpha_j: M_j \rightarrow N_j$ is epimorphism, for all $i \in I$.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that $\alpha_i: M_i \rightarrow N_i$ is epimorphism, for each $i \in I$. Let $j \in I$ and let $(b_i)_{i \in I} \in \oplus_{i \in I} N_i$. If $(b_i)_{i \in I} = (0_{N_i})_{i \in I}$. Since $\oplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is a left R-homomorphism, thus $(\oplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i)((0_{M_i})_{i \in I}) = (0_{N_i})_{i \in I}$. If $(b_i)_{i \in I} \neq (0_{N_i})_{i \in I}$, then $(b_i)_{i \in I} = (0, 0, \dots, 0, b_{j_1}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, 0, b_{j_2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, 0, b_{j_n}, 0, 0, \dots, 0)$ with $b_{j_i} \neq 0$ and $b_{j_i} \in N_{j_i}$, $(i=1, 2, \dots, n)$. Since $\alpha_{j_i}: M_{j_i} \rightarrow N_{j_i}$ is epimorphism, thus $a_{j_i} \in M_{j_i}$ such that $\alpha_{j_i}(a_{j_i}) = (b_{j_i})$. Since $(0, 0, \dots, 0, a_{j_1}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, 0, a_{j_2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, 0, a_{j_n}, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \in \oplus_{i \in I} M_{j_i}$ and

$(\bigoplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i)(0, 0, \dots, 0, a_{j1}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, 0, a_{j2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, 0, a_{jn}, 0, 0, \dots, 0) = (0, 0, \dots, 0, \alpha_{j1}(a_{j1}), 0, 0, \dots, 0, \alpha_{j2}(a_{j2}), 0, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, 0, \alpha_{jn}(a_{jn}), 0, 0, \dots, 0) = (b_i)_{i \in I}$, thus $\bigoplus_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is epimorphism.

(5) (\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is isomorphism, thus $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is monomorphism and epimorphism. By (1) and (3) above, we have that α_i is monomorphism and epimorphism, for all $i \in I$. Thus α_i is isomorphism, for all $i \in I$.

(5) (\Leftarrow) (H.W.) .

(6) (H.W.) .

COROLLARY 3.2.33.

Let $\{M_i\}_{i \in I}$ and $\{N_i\}_{i \in I}$ be two families of left R-modules and $\alpha_i: M_i \rightarrow N_i$ be a left R-homomorphisms, for all $i \in I$. Then

- 1) $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is monomorphism if and only if, for each $i \in I$, α_i is monomorphism.
- 2) $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is epimorphism if and only if, for each $i \in I$, α_i is epimorphism.
- 3) $\prod_{i \in I} \alpha_i$ is isomorphism if and only if, for each $i \in I$, α_i is isomorphism.

Proof. (H.W.) .

Chapter Four

EXACT SEQUENCES OF MODULES

DEFINITION 4.1.1.

A sequence $M_1 \xrightarrow{f} M \xrightarrow{g} M_2$ of left R -modules and left R -homomorphism is said to be exact at M if $\text{Im}(f) = \ker(g)$.

DEFINITION 4.1.2.

A sequence of left R -modules and left R -homomorphism of the form

$S : \dots \rightarrow M_{n-1} \xrightarrow{f_{n-1}} M_n \xrightarrow{f_n} M_{n+1} \rightarrow \dots, n \in \mathbb{Z}$, is said to be **an exact sequence** if it is exact at M_n between a pair of R -homomorphisms for each $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

DEFINITION 4.1.3.

Let $\{M_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a nonempty family of R -modules with the corresponding family of R -homomorphism $\{f_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, where $f_n: M_n \rightarrow M_{n+1} \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$ is a R -homomorphism .

The sequences :- $\dots \rightarrow M_{n-2} \xrightarrow{f_{n-2}} M_{n-1} \xrightarrow{f_{n-1}} M_n \xrightarrow{f_n} M_{n+1} \xrightarrow{f_{n+1}} M_{n+2} \xrightarrow{f_{n+2}} \dots$

is called **an exact sequence** if $\text{Im } f_{n-1} = \ker f_n, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$.

If $M_k=0, \forall k > n$, the sequences is in the form $\dots \rightarrow M_{n-2} \xrightarrow{f_{n-2}} M_{n-1} \xrightarrow{f_{n-1}} M_n \rightarrow 0$.

If $M_k=0, \forall k < n$, the sequences is in the form $0 \rightarrow M_n \xrightarrow{f_n} M_{n+1} \xrightarrow{f_{n+1}} M_{n+2} \xrightarrow{f_{n+2}} \dots$

PROPOSITION 4.1.4.

Let A, B and C be left R -modules. Then

(1) The sequence $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B$ is exact (at A) if and only if, f is injective.

(2) The sequence $B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$ is exact (at C) if and only if, g is surjective.

Proof.

(1) (\Rightarrow) Suppose that the sequence $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B$ is exact (at A), thus $\text{Im}(0) = \ker(f) \Rightarrow$

$\ker(f) = 0_A \Rightarrow f$ is injective, by Proposition (2.1.20).

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that f is injective, thus $\ker(f) = 0_A$ (by Proposition (2.1.20)).

Since $\text{Im}(0) = 0_A = \ker(f) \Rightarrow$ the sequence $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B$ is exact (at A).

(2) (H.W.).

PROPOSITION 4.1.5.

1- A sequences $M \xrightarrow{f} N \rightarrow 0$ is exact sequences if and only if, f is an epimorphism .

2- A sequences $0 \rightarrow K \xrightarrow{g} N$ is exact sequences if and only if, g is a monomorphism .

3- A sequences $0 \rightarrow M \xrightarrow{f} N \rightarrow 0$ is exact sequences if and only if, f is an isomorphism.

Proof :-

1-(\Rightarrow) If $M \xrightarrow{f} N \rightarrow 0$ is exact sequences $\therefore \text{Im}f = \ker \alpha = \{x \in N : \alpha(x) = 0\}$.

But $\ker \alpha = N$. $\therefore \text{Im}f = N \Rightarrow f$ is an epimorphism .

(\Leftarrow) If f is an epimorphism. $\therefore \text{Im}f = N$. Since $\alpha : N \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow \ker \alpha = N$. $\therefore \text{Im}f = \ker \alpha$.

\therefore The sequences is exact sequences .

2- (\Rightarrow) If $0 \rightarrow K \xrightarrow{g} N$ is exact sequences. $\therefore \text{Im}\alpha = \ker g = \{x \in K : g(x) = 0\}$.

$\text{Im}\alpha = \alpha(0) = \{0\}$ since α is homomorphism . $\therefore \ker g = \{0\} \Rightarrow g$ is monomorphism .

(\Leftarrow) If g is monomorphism $\Rightarrow \ker g = \{0\}$ and $\text{Im}\alpha = \alpha(0) = \{0\}$, since α is homomorphism $\Rightarrow \text{Im}\alpha = \ker g$. \therefore the sequences is exact sequences .

3- (\Rightarrow) since A sequences is exact sequences $\Rightarrow \text{Im} \alpha_1 = \ker f = \{x \in M : f(x) = 0\}$.

$\text{Im}\alpha_1 = \alpha_1(0) = 0$, since α_1 is homomorphism . $\therefore \ker f = \{0\}$. $\therefore f$ is a monomorphism and since a sequences is exact sequences $\Rightarrow \text{Im}f = \ker \alpha_2$.

$\ker \alpha_2 = \{x \in N : \alpha_2(x) = 0\} = N$, since $\forall x \in N \Rightarrow \alpha_2(x) = 0$. $\therefore \text{Im}f = N \Rightarrow f$ is an epimorphism .

$\therefore f$ is an isomorphism

(\Leftarrow) If f is a monomorphism $\Rightarrow \ker f = \{0\}$. Since $\text{Im}\alpha_1 = 0 \Rightarrow \ker f = \text{Im}\alpha_1$ and since f is epimorphism $\Rightarrow \text{Im}f = N$. But $\ker \alpha_2 = N$. $\therefore \text{Im}f = \ker \alpha_2$. \therefore the sequences by define of exact sequences.

COROLLARY 4.1.6.

The sequence $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$ of left R -modules is exact if and only if, f is injective, g is surjective, and $\text{Im}(f) = \ker(g)$.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that the sequence $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$ of left R -modules is exact,

thus the sequences $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B$, $A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C$ and $B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$ are exact. By proposition 4.1.3, f is injective, g is surjective and $\text{Im}(f) = \ker(g)$.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that f is injective, g is surjective, and $\text{Im}(f) = \ker(g)$. By proposition 4.1.3,

the sequences $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B$, $A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C$ and $B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$ are exact. Thus the sequence

$0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$ of left R-modules is exact.

DEFINITION 4.1.7.

The exact sequence of the form $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$ is called a **short exact sequence**.

Note that: That is $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequences, if $\text{Im} f = \ker g$, f is a monomorphism and g is an epimorphism

PROPOSITION 4.1.8.

Let N be a submodule of a left R-module M . Then the sequence $0 \rightarrow N \xrightarrow{i} M \xrightarrow{\pi} M/N \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequence, where i is the inclusion mapping and π is the natural mapping.

Proof.

Since $\text{Im}(i) = N$ and $\ker(\pi) = N$ (by Proposition 2.1.15), thus $\text{Im}(i) = \ker(\pi)$. Since π is injective and π is surjective it follows from Corollary (4.1.6), that the sequence $0 \rightarrow N \xrightarrow{i} M \xrightarrow{\pi} M/N \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequence.

PROPOSITION 4.1.9.

If $0 \rightarrow K \xrightarrow{f} M \xrightarrow{g} N \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequences then :

- 1) f is a monomorphism .
- 2) g is an epimorphism .
- 3) $M / \text{Im} f \cong N$.
- 4) $g \circ f = \{0\}$.

Proof :- 1-2 (H.W.)

3- $\because g$ is an epimorphism $\Rightarrow M / \ker g \cong N$, by the first fun. theorem .

$\because 0 \rightarrow K \xrightarrow{f} M \xrightarrow{g} N \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequences $\Rightarrow \text{Im} f = \ker g \Rightarrow M / \text{Im} f \cong N$.

4- $\because g \circ f : K \rightarrow N$ such that $g \circ f(x) = g(f(x))$. $\because f(x) \in \text{Im} f = \ker g \Rightarrow f(x) \in \ker g$
 $g \circ f(x) = g(f(x)) = \{0\}$, by definition of kernel $\Rightarrow g \circ f = \{0\}$.

EXAMPLES 4.1.10. Prove that :-

(1):- $0 \rightarrow 2Z \xrightarrow{\alpha} Z \xrightarrow{\pi} Z / (2Z) \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequences .

$\text{Im} i = 2Z = \ker \pi$, $i(2Z) = 2Z$. $\ker \pi = \{x \in Z : f(x) = 0\} = \{x \in Z : f(x) = 2Z\} = 2Z$. $\therefore \text{Im} i = \ker \pi = 2Z$.

i is a monomorphism, π is an epimorphism $\text{Im} \alpha = 0 = \ker i$, $\text{Im} \pi = \{ \pi(x) : x \in Z \} = \{ x + 2Z : x \in Z \} = Z / 2Z$. $\therefore i$ is monomorphism . π is onto $\Rightarrow \pi$ is epimorphism .

In general if N is a submodule of a R-module M , then the sequences $0 \rightarrow N \xrightarrow{i} M \xrightarrow{\pi} M/N \rightarrow 0$ is an short exact sequences

(2):- Let M_1 and M_2 be two R-modules . Then the sequences $0 \rightarrow M_1 \xrightarrow{q_1} M_1 \oplus M_2 \xrightarrow{f_2} M_2 \rightarrow 0$ is an exact sequences .

q_1 is a monomorphism, $\ker q_1 = \{ m_1 \in M_1 : q_1(m_1) = 0 \} = \{ m_1 \in M_1 : (m_1, 0) = 0 \} = \{ 0 \}$ and f_2 is an epimorphism, $\text{Im } f_2 = \{ f_2(m_1, m_2) : (m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2 \} = \{ (0, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2 \} = M_2$. To proof $\text{Im } q_1 = \ker f_2$. Since q_1 is a monomorphism and f_2 is an epimorphism .
 $\text{Im } q_1 = \{ q_1(m_1) : m_1 \in M_1 \} = \{ (m_1, 0) : m_1 \in M_1 \} = M_1$.
 $\ker f_2 = \{ (m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2 : f_2(m_1, m_2) = 0 \} = \{ (m_1, m_2) \in M_1 \oplus M_2 : m_2 = 0 \} = \{ (m_1, 0) \in M_1 \oplus M_2 \} = M_1$
 $\therefore \text{Im } q_1 = \ker f_2$.

PROPOSITION 4.1.11.

Let $f : M \rightarrow N$ be a left R-homomorphism. Then

- (1) the sequence $0 \rightarrow \ker(f) \xrightarrow{i} M \xrightarrow{\pi} M/\ker(f) \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequence;
- (2) the sequence $0 \rightarrow f(M) \xrightarrow{i} N \xrightarrow{\pi} N/f(M) \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequence;
- (3) the sequence $0 \rightarrow \ker(f) \xrightarrow{i} M \xrightarrow{f} N \xrightarrow{\pi} N/f(M) \rightarrow 0$ is an exact sequence;
- (4) the sequence $0 \rightarrow \ker(f) \xrightarrow{i} M \xrightarrow{f'} f(M) \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequence, where $f' : M \rightarrow f(M)$ is defined by $f'(x) = f(x)$, for all $x \in M$.

Proof.

- (1) By Example 4.1.12.
- (2) Since $f(M)$ is a left R-submodule of N (by Corollary 2.1.22) it follows from Proposition (4.1.8) that the sequence $0 \rightarrow f(M) \xrightarrow{i} N \xrightarrow{\pi} N/f(M) \rightarrow 0$ is a short exact sequence.
- (3) Since i is injective and π is surjective, thus by Proposition (4.1.4), we get that $0 \rightarrow \ker(f) \xrightarrow{i} M$ and $N \xrightarrow{\pi} N/f(M) \rightarrow 0$ are exact sequences. Since $\text{Im}(i) = \ker(f)$ the sequence $\ker(f) \xrightarrow{i} M \xrightarrow{f} N$ is exact. Since $\text{Im}(f) = f(M) = \ker(\pi) \Rightarrow$ the sequence $M \xrightarrow{f} N \xrightarrow{\pi} N/f(M)$ is exact. Hence the sequence $0 \rightarrow \ker(f) \xrightarrow{i} M \xrightarrow{f} N \xrightarrow{\pi} N/f(M) \rightarrow 0$ is an exact sequence.
- (4) (H.W.).

PROPOSITION 4.1.12.

Let $\alpha : M \rightarrow N$ and $\beta : N \rightarrow K$ be left R-homomorphisms. Then

- (1) $\ker(\beta\alpha) = \alpha^{-1}(\ker(\beta))$;
- (2) $\text{Im}(\beta\alpha) = \beta(\text{Im}(\alpha))$.

Proof.

(1) Let $x \in \ker(\beta\alpha) \Rightarrow (\beta\alpha)(x) = 0_K \Rightarrow \alpha(x) \in \ker(\beta) \Rightarrow x \in \alpha^{-1}(\ker(\beta)) \Rightarrow \ker(\beta\alpha) \subseteq \alpha^{-1}(\ker(\beta))$.

Conversely, let $x \in \alpha^{-1}(\ker(\beta)) \Rightarrow \alpha(x) \in \ker(\beta) \Rightarrow \beta(\alpha(x)) = 0_K \Rightarrow (\beta\alpha)(x) = 0_K \Rightarrow x \in \ker(\beta\alpha) \Rightarrow \alpha^{-1}(\ker(\beta)) \subseteq \ker(\beta\alpha)$. Thus $\ker(\beta\alpha) = \alpha^{-1}(\ker(\beta))$.

(2) Let $x \in \text{Im}(\beta\alpha) \Rightarrow \exists a \in M \exists (\beta\alpha)(a) = x \Rightarrow \beta(\alpha(a)) = x$. Since $\alpha(a) \in \text{Im}(\alpha) \Rightarrow$

$x \in \beta (\text{Im}(\alpha)) \Rightarrow \text{Im}(\beta\alpha) \subseteq \beta (\text{Im}(\alpha)).$

Conversely, let $y \in \beta (\text{Im}(\alpha)) \Rightarrow \exists x \in \text{Im}(\alpha) \ni y = \beta (x) \Rightarrow \exists a \in M \ni \alpha (a) = x \Rightarrow y = \beta (\alpha (a)) = (\beta\alpha)(a) \in \text{Im}(\beta\alpha) \Rightarrow \beta (\text{Im}(\alpha)) \subseteq \text{Im}(\beta\alpha).$ Thus $\text{Im}(\beta\alpha) = \beta (\text{Im}(\alpha)).$

COROLLARY 4.1.13.

Let $\alpha :M \rightarrow N$ and $\beta :N \rightarrow K$ be left R-homomorphisms.

- (1) If β is a R-monomorphism, then $\ker(\beta\alpha) = \ker(\alpha).$
- (2) If α is a R-epimorphism, then $\text{Im}(\beta\alpha) = \text{Im}(\beta).$

Proof.

(1) Suppose that β is a R-monomorphism, thus $\ker(\beta) = 0_k$ (by Proposition 2.1.20). By Proposition (4.1.15(1)), $\ker(\beta\alpha) = \alpha^{-1} (\ker(\beta)) = \alpha^{-1} (0_k) = \ker(\alpha).$

(2) Suppose that α is a R-epimorphism, thus $\text{Im}(\alpha) = N$. By Proposition 4.1.15(2), $\text{Im}(\beta\alpha) = \beta (\text{Im}(\alpha)) = \beta (N) = \text{Im}(\beta).$

PROPOSITION 4.1.14.

Let $S_1 : 0 \rightarrow M_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha} M \xrightarrow{f} N \rightarrow 0$ and $S_2 : 0 \rightarrow N \xrightarrow{g} M_2 \xrightarrow{\beta} M_3 \rightarrow 0$ be short exact sequences of left R-modules. Then the sequence $S_3 : 0 \rightarrow M_1 \xrightarrow{\alpha} M \xrightarrow{fg} M_2 \xrightarrow{\beta} M_3 \rightarrow 0$ is exact.

Proof. (H.W.)

DEFINITION 4.1.15.

Let the diagram in (4.1.15) of left R- modules and left R-homomorphism is said to be commutative if, $gf = \beta\alpha$.

THEOREM 4.1.16. (The four lemma)

Suppose that the diagram in (4.1.16) of left R- modules and left R-homomorphisms is said to

be commutative and has exact rows. Then we have

- (1) If α_1 is an R-epimorphism and α_2, α_4 are monomorphisms, then α_3 is a monomorphism;
- (2) If α_1 and α_3 are epimorphisms and α_4 is a monomorphism, then α_2 is an epimorphism.

Proof. (H.W.) see {Plyth, Theorem 3.9 , p.32}.

THEOREM 4.1.17. (The five lemma)

Suppose that the diagram in (4.1.17) of left R- modules and left R-homomorphisms is said to

$$\begin{array}{ccccccccc}
 A & \xrightarrow{f} & B & \xrightarrow{g} & C & \xrightarrow{h} & D & \xrightarrow{i} & E \\
 \alpha_1 \downarrow & & \alpha_2 \downarrow & & \alpha_3 \downarrow & & \alpha_4 \downarrow & & \alpha_5 \downarrow \\
 A' & \xrightarrow{f'} & B' & \xrightarrow{g'} & C' & \xrightarrow{h'} & D' & \xrightarrow{i'} & E'
 \end{array}$$

be commutative and has exact rows. Then we have

- (1) If α_1 is an R-epimorphism and α_2, α_4 are monomorphisms, then α_3 is a monomorphism;
- (2) If α_5 is a monomorphism and α_2, α_4 are epimorphisms, then α_3 is an epimorphism.
- (3) If $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_4$ and α_5 are isomorphisms, then α_3 is an isomorphism.

Proof.

- (1) Suppose that α_1 is an epimorphism and α_2, α_4 are monomorphisms. By applying Theorem (4.1.16) to the left – hand three squares , we see that α_3 is a monomorphism.
- (2) Suppose that α_5 is a monomorphism and α_2, α_4 are epimorphisms. By applying Theorem (4.1.16) to the right – hand three squares , we see that α_3 is an epimorphism.
- (3) Suppose that $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_4$ and α_5 are isomorphisms. By (1) above , α_3 is a monomorphism. By (2) above , α_3 is epimorphism . Hence α_3 is an isomorphism.

COROLLARY 4.1.18. (The short five lemma)

Suppose that the diagram in (4.1.18) of left R- modules and left R-homomorphisms is said to

$$\begin{array}{ccccccccc}
 0 & \longrightarrow & B & \xrightarrow{f} & C & \xrightarrow{g} & D & \longrightarrow & 0 \\
 & & \alpha \downarrow & & \beta \downarrow & & \gamma \downarrow & & \\
 0 & \longrightarrow & B' & \xrightarrow{f'} & C' & \xrightarrow{g'} & D' & \longrightarrow & 0
 \end{array}$$

be commutative and has exact rows. Then we have

- (1) If α and γ are monomorphisms, then β is a monomorphism;
- (2) If α and γ are epimorphisms, then β is a epimorphism.
- (3) If α and γ are isomorphisms, then β is a isomorphism.

Proof.

Take $A = A' = E = E' = 0$ in Theorem (4.1.17) .

PROPOSITION 4.1.19.

Suppose that the diagram in (4.1.19) of left R- modules and left R-homomorphisms is said to

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 A & \xrightarrow{f} & B & \xrightarrow{g} & C \\
 \alpha \downarrow & & \beta \downarrow & & \gamma \downarrow \\
 A' & \xrightarrow{f'} & B' & \xrightarrow{g'} & C'
 \end{array}$$

be commutative and α, β and γ be isomorphisms. Then the sequence $A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C$ is exact if and only if the sequence $A' \xrightarrow{f'} B' \xrightarrow{g'} C'$ is exact .

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that the sequence $A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C$ is exact, thus $\text{Im}(f) = \ker(g)$. Since α is an epimorphism it follows from corollary (4.1.18), that $\text{Im}(f') = \text{Im}(f'\alpha)$.

Since $\text{Im}(f'\alpha) = \text{Im}(\beta f) = \beta(\text{Im}(f)) = \beta(\ker(g)) = \ker(g\beta^{-1}) = \ker(\gamma^{-1}g') = (g')^{-1}(\ker(\gamma^{-1}))$

$= (g')^{-1}(0) = \ker(g')$, thus $\text{Im}(f') = \ker(g')$ and hence the sequence $A' \xrightarrow{f'} B' \xrightarrow{g'} C'$ is exact.

(\Leftarrow)(H.W.)

SPLIT SEQUENCES OF MODULES

DEFINITION 4.2.1.

1- A left R -monomorphism Let $\alpha : (M, +, \cdot) \rightarrow (N, +', \cdot')$ is called **splits monomorphism** if, $\text{Im } \alpha$ is a direct summand of N .

2- A left R -epimorphism Let $\beta : (N, +', \cdot') \rightarrow (K, +'', \cdot'')$ is called **splits epimorphism** if, $\ker \beta$ is a direct summand of N .

EXAMPLE 4.2. 2.

1) Let $I: \langle 2 \rangle \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_6$ be the inclusion \mathbb{Z} -homomorphism . Then I is a split monomorphism .

2) Let $\pi: \mathbb{Z}_6 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_6 / \langle 2 \rangle$ be the natural \mathbb{Z} -epimorphism . Then π is a split epimorphism

LEMMA 4.2. 3.

Let $\alpha : M \rightarrow N$ be left R-homomorphisms. Then we have :

- (1) If A is a left R-submodules of M , then $\alpha^{-1}(\alpha(A)) = A + \ker(\alpha)$.
- (2) If B is a left R-submodules of N , then $\alpha(\alpha^{-1}(B)) = B \cap \text{Im}(\alpha)$.

THEOREM 4.2. 4.

Let the diagram in (4.2. 4) be commutative (in other word $\lambda = \beta\alpha$). Then

- (1) $\text{Im}(\alpha) + \ker(\beta) = \beta^{-1}(\text{Im}(\lambda))$; (2) $\text{Im}(\alpha) \cap \ker(\beta) = \alpha(\ker(\lambda))$.

Proof.

- (1) Since $\lambda = \beta\alpha$, thus $\text{Im}(\lambda) = \text{Im}(\beta\alpha) = \beta(\text{Im}(\alpha)) \Rightarrow \beta^{-1}(\text{Im}(\lambda)) = \beta^{-1}(\beta(\text{Im}(\alpha))) = \text{Im}(\alpha) + \ker(\beta)$, by lemma (4.2. 3(1)).
- (2) $\ker(\lambda) = \ker(\beta\alpha) = \alpha^{-1}(\ker(\beta))$, thus $\alpha(\ker(\lambda)) = \alpha(\alpha^{-1}(\ker(\beta))) = \text{Im}(\alpha) \cap \ker(\beta)$, by lemma (4.2. 3(1)).

COROLLARY 4.2. 5.

Let the diagram in (4.2. 5) be commutative (in other word $\lambda = \beta\alpha$). Then

be commutative (in other word $\lambda = \beta\alpha$). Then

- (1) If λ is an epimorphism, then $\text{Im}(\alpha) + \ker(\beta) = B$.
- (2) If λ is a monomorphism, then $\text{Im}(\alpha) \cap \ker(\beta) = 0_B$.
- (3) If λ is an isomorphism, then $\text{Im}(\alpha) \oplus \ker(\beta) = B$.

Proof.

- (1) Suppose that λ is an epimorphism, thus $\text{Im}(\lambda) = C$. By theorem (4.2.4(1)), $\text{Im}(\alpha) + \ker(\beta) = \beta^{-1}(\text{Im}(\lambda)) = \beta^{-1}(C) = B$.
- (2) Suppose that λ is a monomorphism, thus $\ker(\lambda) = 0_A$. By theorem (4.2.4(2)), $\text{Im}(\alpha) \cap \ker(\beta) = \alpha(\ker(\lambda)) = \alpha(0_A) = 0_B$. By Proposition 4.1.15(1), $\ker(\beta\alpha) = \alpha^{-1}(\ker(\beta)) = \alpha^{-1}(0_C) = \ker(\alpha)$.
- (3) By (1) and (2) above.

PROPOSITION 4.2.6.

Let $\alpha :M \rightarrow N$ be left R-homomorphism. Then α is a split monomorphism if and only if there exists a homomorphism $\beta :N \rightarrow M$ with $\beta\alpha = I_M$.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\alpha :M \rightarrow N$ is split monomorphism thus $\text{Im}(\alpha)$ is a direct summand of $N \Rightarrow$ there is a submodule B of N such that $N = \text{Im}(\alpha) \oplus B$.

Let $\pi :N \rightarrow \text{Im}(\alpha)$ be the projection of N onto $\text{Im}(\alpha)$ defined by $\pi(\alpha(a)+b) = \alpha(a)$, for all $\alpha(a) \in \text{Im}(\alpha)$ and $b \in B$. It is clear that π is an epimorphism (H.W.)?

Define $\alpha_0 :M \rightarrow \alpha(M)$ by $\alpha_0(a) = \alpha(a)$, for all $a \in M$. Thus α_0 is an isomorphism (H.W.)?

Put $\beta = \alpha_0^{-1} \circ \pi :N \rightarrow M$. Since α_0^{-1} and π are left R-homomorphism, thus β is a left R-homomorphism. For all $a \in M$, we have that $(\beta\alpha)(a) = \beta(\alpha(a)) = \beta(\alpha_0(a)) = \alpha_0^{-1}(\pi(\alpha(a))) = \alpha_0^{-1}(\alpha(a)) = a = I_M \alpha(a)$. Thus $\beta\alpha = I_M$ and hence there is a left-homomorphism $\beta :N \rightarrow M$ such that $\beta\alpha = I_M$.

(\Leftarrow)(H.W.)

PROPOSITION 4.2.7.

Let $\alpha :M \rightarrow N$ be left R-homomorphism. Then α is a split epimorphism if and only if there exists a homomorphism $\beta :N \rightarrow M$ with $\beta\alpha = I_N$.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\alpha :M \rightarrow N$ is split epimorphism thus $\ker(\alpha)$ is a direct summand of $M \Rightarrow$ there is a submodule A of M such that $M = \ker(\alpha) \oplus A$.

Let $i :A \rightarrow M$ be the inclusion mapping. Define $\alpha_0 :A \rightarrow N$ by $\alpha_0(a) = \alpha(a)$, for all $a \in A$. Thus α_0 is left R-homomorphism (H.W.)?

Let $a, b \in A$ such that $\alpha_0(a) = \alpha_0(b) \Rightarrow \alpha(a) = \alpha(b) \Rightarrow \alpha_0(a-b) = 0_N \Rightarrow a-b \in \ker(\alpha)$. Since $a-b \in A \Rightarrow a-b \in A \cap \ker(\alpha)$. Since $A \cap \ker(\alpha) = 0_A \Rightarrow a-b = 0_A \Rightarrow a=b \Rightarrow \alpha_0$ is left R-monomorphism.

Let $b \in N$, since $\alpha :M \rightarrow N$ is epimorphism, thus there is $a \in M$ such that $\alpha(a) = b$. Since $M = \ker(\alpha) \oplus A \Rightarrow a = a_1 + b_1$ with $a_1 \in \ker(\alpha)$, $b_1 \in A$. Thus $b = \alpha(a) = \alpha(a_1 + b_1) = \alpha(a_1) + \alpha(b_1) = \alpha(a_1) + 0_N = \alpha(a_1) = \alpha_0(a_1)$. Hence α_0 is an epimorphism and $\alpha_0 :A \rightarrow N$ is isomorphism.

Put $\beta = I \circ \alpha_0^{-1} :N \rightarrow M$. Since i and α_0^{-1} are left R-homomorphism, thus β is a left R-homomorphism. For all $x \in N$, we have that $(\beta\alpha)(x) = \beta(\alpha(x)) = \beta(i \circ \alpha_0^{-1}(x)) = \alpha_0^{-1}(\alpha(x)) = x = I_N(x)$. Thus $\beta\alpha = I_N$ and hence there is a left-homomorphism $\beta :N \rightarrow M$ such that $\beta\alpha = I_N$.

(\Leftarrow)(H.W.)

DEFINITION 4.2.8.

An exact sequences $A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C$ is called **splits** on whether $\text{Im}f = \ker g$ is a direct summand of B .

DEFINITION 4.2.9.

Let $n \geq 2$. An exact sequences $A_1 \xrightarrow{f_1} A_2 \xrightarrow{f_2} A_3 \xrightarrow{f_3} \dots \xrightarrow{f_n} A_{n+1}$ is called **splits** on whether $\text{Im}(f_i) = \ker(f_{i+1})$ is a direct summand of A_{i+1} , for all $i=1,2,\dots,n-1$.

DEFINITION 4.2.10.

An exact sequences $0 \rightarrow K \xrightarrow{f} M \xrightarrow{g} N \rightarrow 0$ is called **splits** if and only if, $\text{Im}f$ is a direct summand of M (or $\ker g$ is a direct summand of M).

i.e. (an exact sequences $0 \rightarrow K \xrightarrow{f} M \xrightarrow{g} N \rightarrow 0$ splits if and only if, $M = \text{Im}f \oplus A$ or $M = \ker g \oplus A$, for some submodule A of M)

PROPOSITION 4.2.11.

Let $0 \rightarrow K \xrightarrow{f} M \xrightarrow{g} N \rightarrow 0$ be a short exact sequences. Then the following conditions are equivalent :

- (1) The sequences splits
- (2) There exists a R -homomorphism $h: M \rightarrow K$ such that $h \circ f = I_K$.
- (3) There exists a R -homomorphism $K: N \rightarrow M$ such that $g \circ K = I_N$.

Proof :- (1) \Rightarrow (2)

By (1), the sequences splits ,therefore $\text{Im}f$ is direct summand of M . $\therefore M = \text{Im}f \oplus A$, for some submodule A of M . $\therefore M = \text{Im}f + A$ and $\text{Im}f \cap A = \{0\}$, $\therefore \forall m \in M, m = f(x) + a$ where $x \in K$ and $a \in A$

Define $h: M \rightarrow K$ such that $h(f(x) + a) = x, \forall x \in K$ and $\forall a \in A$.

Well-define of h : Let $f(x_1) + a_1 = f(x_2) + a_2$, where $x_1, x_2 \in K$ and $a_1, a_2 \in A$.

$f(x_1 - x_2) = a_2 - a_1 \in \text{Im}f \cap A = \{0\}$. $\therefore f(x_1 - x_2) = 0$. $\therefore x_1 - x_2 \in \ker f$.

But $\ker f = \{0\}$, since f is a monomorphism. $\therefore x_1 - x_2 = 0 \Rightarrow x_1 = x_2$.

Homomorphism :

(1) $h((f(x_1) + a_1) + (f(x_2) + a_2)) = h(f(x_1 + x_2) + (a_1 + a_2)) = x_1 + x_2 = h(f(x_1) + a_1) + h(f(x_2) + a_2)$.

(2) $h(r \cdot (f(x) + a)) = h(f(rx) + a)$, since f is a homomorphism
 $= r \cdot x = r \cdot h(f(x) + a)$, where $x_1, x_2 \in K$, $a_1, a_2 \in A$.

To prove $h \circ f = I_K$:

Let $y \in K$, $h \circ f(y) = h(f(y)) = h(f(y) + 0) = y = I_K(y)$. $\therefore h \circ f = I_K$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) Since $g: M \rightarrow N$ is an epimorphism (exact sequences)

and $\forall x \in M \Rightarrow (f \circ h)(x) \in M$ (since $M \xrightarrow{h} K \xrightarrow{f} M$) $\therefore (x - (f \circ h)(x)) \in M$.

Now, $K: N \rightarrow M$ such that $K(y) = x - (f \circ h)(x), \forall y \in N$ where $y = g(x)$.

Well-define of k : Let $y_1, y_2 \in N$ and $y_1 = y_2$.

$\therefore y_1 = g(x_1)$ and $y_2 = g(x_2)$, for some $x_1, x_2 \in M$.

Since g is onto, $g(x_1) = g(x_2)$, since $y_1 = y_2 \Rightarrow g(x_1 - x_2) = 0$ and since g is homomorphism

$\therefore x_1 - x_2 \in \ker g \cdot x_1 - x_2 \in \text{Im} f$, since the sequences is exact by hyp.

$\therefore f: K \rightarrow M, z \in k$ such that $f(z) = x_1 - x_2$ (by define of $\text{Im} f$)

$$(x_1 - (f \circ h)(x_1)) - (x_2 - (f \circ h)(x_2)) \stackrel{?}{=} 0$$

$(x_1 - (f \circ h)(x_1)) - (x_2 - (f \circ h)(x_2)) = (x_1 - x_2) - (f \circ h)(x_1 - x_2)$, since $f \circ h$ is homomorphism

$$= f(z) - (f \circ h)(f(z)) = f(z) - (f \circ (h \circ f))(z) = f(z) - (f \circ I_K)(z), \text{ by (2), } h \circ f = I_K$$

$$\Rightarrow f(z) - f(z) = 0. \therefore x_1 - (f \circ h)(x_1) = x_2 - (f \circ h)(x_2).$$

Homomorphism :

$$(1): -k(y_1 + y_2) = (x_1 + x_2 - (f \circ h)(x_1 + x_2)) = (x_1 + x_2 - (f \circ h)(x_1) - (f \circ h)(x_2)) \\ = (x_1 - (f \circ h)(x_1)) + (x_2 - (f \circ h)(x_2)) = k(y_1) + k(y_2)$$

$$(2): -k(rx) = (r \cdot x - (f \circ h)(r \cdot x)) = \{r \cdot x - r \cdot (f \circ h)(x)\} = r \cdot (x - (f \circ h)(x)) = r \cdot k(y).$$

To prove $g \circ k = I_N$

Let $y \in N \Rightarrow \exists x \in M$ such that $g(x) = y$

$$(g \circ k)(y) = g(k(y)) = g(x - (f \circ h)(x)) = g(x) - g(f \circ h)(x)$$

$$= g(x) - (g \circ f)h(x), \text{ by (Remark, } f \text{ monomorphism, } g \text{ epimorphism).}$$

$$= g(x), \text{ (since } g \circ f = 0 \text{ since the sequences is exact)}$$

$$= y = I_N(y).$$

$$\therefore g \circ k = I_N.$$

(3) \Rightarrow (1), We have to show that $\ker g$ is a direct summand of M . Since $k: N \rightarrow M$ is a homomorphism by (3) $\Rightarrow \text{Im } k$ is a submodule of M .

To prove $M = \ker g \oplus \text{Im } k$.

$$\text{Let } x \in M, x = x - k(g(x)) + k(g(x)) \Rightarrow x - k(g(x)) = x - k(g(x)) \Rightarrow$$

$$g(x - k(g(x))) = g(x) - g(k(g(x))) = g(x) - (g \circ k \circ g)(x), \text{ by (3) } = g(x) - (I_N \circ g)(x) = g(x) - g(x) = 0.$$

$$\therefore x - k(g(x)) \in \ker g \Rightarrow M = \ker g + \text{Im } k.$$

Let $z \in \ker g \cap \text{Im } k \Rightarrow z \in \ker g$ and $z \in \text{Im } k \Rightarrow g(z) = 0$ by define of $\ker g$

$$\text{And } z = k(t) \text{ for some } t \in N.$$

$$0 = g(z) = g(k(t)) = (g \circ k)(t) = t \text{ by (3), } g \circ k = I_N. \therefore t = 0 \Rightarrow z = k(t) = k(0) = 0, \text{ since } k \text{ is homomorphism.}$$

$$\therefore \ker g \cap \text{Im } k = \{0\}. \therefore M = \ker g \oplus \text{Im } k. \therefore \text{The sequences is splits.}$$

EXAMPLE 4.2.12.

The sequences in example (4.1.10(1)) is not splits since Z is indecomposable with in example (4.1.10(2)) is splits since $M_1 \oplus M_2$ is decomposable.

FREE MODULES

DEFINITION 4.2.1.

Let M be a left R -module. A subset X of M is said to be linear independent if for every $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i = 0$, with $r_i \in R$, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$, then $r_i=0$, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$.

DEFINITION 4.2.2.

Let M be a left R -module. A subset X of M is said to be a basis for M , if

- 1) $M = \langle X \rangle$ (in other words $m \in M$, $m = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i$, with $r_i \in R$, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$.)
- 2) X is linear independent .

PROPOSITION 4.2.3.

Let M be a left R -module and let X be a generating set for M , then X is a basis for M if and only if for each $m \in M$, the representation $m = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i$, with $r_i \in R$, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$, is unique.

Proof:-

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that X is a basis for M . Let $m \in M$, such that $m = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i = \sum_{i=1}^n t_i x_i$, with $r_i, t_i \in R$, and $x_i \in X$ are distinct element, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$. Thus $\sum_{i=1}^n (r_i - t_i)x_i = 0$. Since X is linear independent, thus $r_i - t_i = 0$ and hence $r_i = t_i$, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$. Therefore for each $m \in M$, the representation $m = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i$, with $r_i \in R$, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$, is unique.

(\Leftarrow) We must prove that X is a basis for M . Since X is a generating set for M , thus we need only prove that X is linear independent. Suppose that $\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i = 0$, with $r_i \in R$, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$. Since $\sum_{i=1}^n 0x_i = 0$, thus $\sum_{i=1}^n 0x_i = \sum_{i=1}^n t_i x_i$. Since the representation of each element in M is unique, thus $r_i = 0$, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$, and hence X is linear independent. Thus X is a basis for M .

DEFINITION 4.2.4.

Let M be a left R -module. M is said to be **free left R -module**, if has a basis.

EXAMPLE 4.2.5.

1- Every ring R with identify 1 is free left R -module.

Proof:-

Let $X = \{1\}$. It is clear that ${}_R R = \langle \{1\} \rangle = \langle X \rangle$. Let $r \cdot 1 = 0$ with $r \in R$ and hence $X = \{1\}$, thus $r = 0$ is linear independent. Hence X is a basis for a left R -module R . Thus R is free left R -module.

2- Z is a free Z -module.

3- Z_n is a free Z_n -module, for every $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

4- Let R be a ring with identify 1 . Then R^n is free left R -module, for every $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Proof:-

Let $X = \left\{ \frac{(1,0,0,\dots,0)}{n\text{-time}}, \frac{(0,1,0,\dots,0)}{n\text{-time}}, \dots, \frac{(0,0,0,\dots,1)}{n\text{-time}} \right\}$. We will prove that X is a basis for R^n as left R -module.

Let $\bar{r} \in R^n$, thus $\bar{r} = (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n)$, with $r_i \in R$, for all $i=1,2,\dots,n$. Hence

$$\bar{r} = (r_1, 0, \dots, 0) + (0, r_2, \dots, 0) \dots + (0, 0, \dots, r_n) = r_1(1, 0, \dots, 0) + r_2(0, 1, \dots, 0) \dots + r_n(0, 0, \dots, 1)$$

And this implies that $R^n = \langle X \rangle$.

Let $s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n \in R$ such that $s_1(1, 0, \dots, 0) + s_2(0, 1, \dots, 0) \dots + s_n(0, 0, \dots, 1) = 0$, thus

$X = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n) = (0, 0, \dots, 0)$ and hence $s_i = 0$, for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Thus X is linear independent and

hence X is a basis for left R -module R^n . Therefore R^n is free left R -module, for every $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

5- Let F be a field. Then every left F -module (F -vector space) is free left F -module.

Proof:- (H.W.).

6- Let R be a ring with identify 1 and let $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Then matrix ring $M_n(R)$ is free left R -module.

Proof:- (H.W.).

7- Z_4 is not a free left Z -module.

Proof:-

It is clear that $\{1\}, \{3\}, \{0,1\}, \{0,3\}, \{1,2\}, \{1,3\}, \{2,3\}, \{0,1,2\}, \{0,1,3\}, \{0,2,3\}, \{1,2,3\}$ and $Z_4 = \{0,1,2,3\}$ are all generating sets of Z_4 as left Z -module (**Why?**).

If $X = \{1\}$ is a basis of Z_4 as left Z -module. Since $3 \cdot 1 = 7 \cdot 1 = 3$, thus $3 = 7$, by proposition(4.2.3).

And this is a contradiction . Thus $X=\{1\}$ is not a basis of Z_4 as left Z -module.

If $X=\{3\}$ is a basis of Z_4 as left Z -module. Since $1.3=5.3=3$, thus $1=5$, by proposition(4.2.3).

And this is a contradiction . Thus $X=\{3\}$ is not a basis of Z_4 as left Z -module.

Similarly, we can prove that $\{0,1\}, \{0,3\}, \{1,2\}, \{1,3\}, \{2,3\}, \{0,1,2\}, \{0,1,3\}, \{0,2,3\}, \{1,2,3\}$ and $Z_4=\{0,1,2,3\}$ are not a basis of Z_4 as left Z -module. Hence Z_4 is not a free left Z -module.

$8- Z_n$ is not a free left Z -module, for all $n \geq 2$.

THEOREM 4.2.6.

Let F be a left R -module. Then F is free left R -module if and only if, $F \cong R^{(I)}$ as left R -module, for some index I .

Proof:- (H.W.).

THEOREM 4.2.7.

The following statements are equivalent for a left R -module M :

- 1) M is finitely generated left R -module;
- 2) there is a left R -epimorphism $\alpha: R^n \rightarrow M$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Proof:-

(1 \Rightarrow 2) Suppose that M is finitely generated left R -module, thus $M = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle$ for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Define $\alpha: R^n \rightarrow M$ by $\alpha(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n) = r_1x_1 + r_2x_2 + \dots + r_nx_n$, for all $(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n) \in R^n$. It is clear that α is a left R -epimorphism **(H.W.)**.

Thus there is a left R -epimorphism $\alpha: R^n \rightarrow M$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

(1 \Leftarrow 2) Suppose that there is a left R -epimorphism $\alpha: R^n \rightarrow M$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Since $R^n = \langle (1, 0, \dots, 0) + (0, 1, \dots, 0) \dots + (0, 0, \dots, 1) \rangle$, thus we can prove that $M = \langle \alpha(1, 0, \dots, 0) + \alpha(0, 1, \dots, 0) \dots + \alpha(0, 0, \dots, 1) \rangle$, **(Why?)**.

And hence M is finitely generated left R -module.

PROPOSITION 4.2.8.

Let I be an index set. Then a free left R -module $R^{(I)}$ is finitely generated if and only if, I is a finite set. In other words, a free left R -module $R^{(I)}$ is finitely generated if and only if, $R^{(I)} = R^n$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Proof:- (H.W.).

COROLLARY 4.2.9.

The following statements are equivalent for a left R -module M :

- 1) there is a left R -epimorphism $\alpha: R^n \rightarrow M$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$;
- 2) M is a homomorphic image of a finitely generated free left R -module.

Proof:-

(1 \Rightarrow 2) **(H.W.)**.

(1 \Leftrightarrow 2) Suppose that M is a homomorphic image of a finitely generated free left R -module, thus there is a left R -epimorphism $\alpha: R^n \rightarrow M$, with F is a finitely generated free left R -module. By Theorem (4.2.6) and proposition (4.2.8), $F \cong R^{(I)}$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, and hence there is an isomorphism $\beta: R^n \rightarrow F$. Put $\phi = \beta\alpha: R^n \rightarrow M$. It is clear ϕ is a left R -epimorphism and hence there is a left R -epimorphism $\phi: R^n \rightarrow M$, for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

* Show that whether the quotient module of a free left R -module is free or not and Why?.

DEFINITION 4.2.10.

By a free module over a ring R on a set S , we mean a R -module F together with a function $f: S \rightarrow F$ satisfying for any R -module X and any function $g: S \rightarrow X$, there exists a unique homomorphism $h: F \rightarrow X$ such that $h \circ f = g$.

That is a **free module on S** is a pair (F, f) which makes the following diagram commutes $h \circ f = g$.

THEOREM 4.2.11.

If (F, f) is a free R -module on a set S , then f is 1-1 and $f(S)$ is a generating set of F .

Proof:-

Let $a, b \in S$ and $a \neq b$, to proof $f(a) \neq f(b)$.

Let X be any R -module, and Let $g: S \rightarrow X$ be a function such that $g(a) \neq g(b)$,

Since F is a free module on S . $\therefore \exists$ a unique homomorphism $h: F \rightarrow X$ such that $h \circ f = g$. If $f(a) = f(b) \Rightarrow h(f(a)) = h(f(b))$, since h is well-defined. $\therefore g(a) = g(b)$, which is a contradiction. then f is 1-1.

(2) \Rightarrow (1)

We have to show that $\text{Im} f$ is a direct summand of M . Since $h: M \rightarrow K$ is homomorphism, then $\ker h$ is a submodule of M . To prove $M = \text{Im} f \oplus \ker h$

Let $x \in M$, $x = x - (f(h(x))) + f(h(x))$.

$$h(x - (f(h(x)))) = h(x) - h(f(h(x))) = h(x) - (h \circ f \circ h)(x) = h(x) - (I_K \circ h)(x) = h(x) - h(x) = 0.$$

$\therefore x - f(h(x)) \in \ker h. \Rightarrow M = \text{Im} f + \ker h$. And

Let $z \in \text{Im} f \cap \ker h \Rightarrow z \in \text{Im} f$ and $z \in \ker h$, then $z = f(t)$, for some t in K and $h(z) = 0$.

$$0=h(z)=h(f(t))=h \circ f(t)=t.$$

$$\therefore t=0 \Rightarrow z=f(0)=0. \therefore \text{Im}f \cap \ker h = \{0\} \Rightarrow M=\text{Im}f \oplus \ker h.$$

$$\therefore f(a) \neq f(b) \Rightarrow f \text{ is 1-1 function. To prove } F=(f(S))$$

Let A be the submodule of F generated by $f(S)$, to prove $A=F$.

Since $A=(f(S)) \subseteq F$ and $f:S \rightarrow F$. $\therefore f$ induces a function $g:S \rightarrow A$ such that $i \circ g=f$, where $i:A \rightarrow F$ is the inclusion mapping, that is $g(x)=f(x) \forall x \in S$.

diagram (4.3)

Now, F is a free R-module on S. $\therefore \exists$ a unique homomorphism $h:F \rightarrow A$ such that $h \circ f=g$.

Consider the following diagram (4.4)

$$(i \circ h) \circ f = i \circ (h \circ f) = i \circ g, \text{ since } h \circ f = g.$$

$$= f, \text{ since } i \circ g = f.$$

diagram (4.4)

But $I_F \circ f=f$ (I_F is the ideal homomorphism on F)

$$\therefore i \circ h = I_F \quad (\text{Since } F \text{ is a free module on } S, \exists \text{ unique homomorphism})$$

$$\therefore I \text{ is onto, since } I_F \text{ is an isomorphism} \Rightarrow i(A)=F. \text{ But } i(A)=A \Rightarrow A=F \Rightarrow F=(f(S)).$$

DEFINITION 4.2.12.

Let M be a R-module a nonempty subset X of M is called a base of M if

(1) $M=(X)$ (i.e. X generates M)

(2) X is a linearly independent set. (i.e. every finite subset $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ of X if

$$\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i = 0, \text{ then } r_i = 0, \forall i = 1, \dots, n.$$

A R-module M such that which has a basis is called a free R-module.

THEOREM 4.2.13. (uniqueness theorem)

Let (F, f) and (F', f') be two free R-modules on the same set S. then exists a unique isomorphism $j:F \rightarrow F'$ such that $j \circ f = f'$.

Proof :-

Since F is a free module on S then there exists a unique homomorphism $j:F \rightarrow F'$ such that $j \circ f = f' \dots (*)$.

To proof j is a monomorphism and j is an epimorphism

Since F' is a free module on S. $\therefore \exists$ a unique homomorphism $h:F' \rightarrow F$ such that $j \circ h = f \dots (**)$.

Consider the following diagram (4.5) :-

diagram (4.5)

$$F \xrightarrow{j} F' \xrightarrow{h} F, \quad F \xrightarrow{h \circ j} F$$

$$(h \circ j) \circ f = h \circ (j \circ f) = h \circ f' \text{ by } (*) \\ = f \text{ by } (**).$$

And $I_F \circ f = f$ identity. But F is a free module on $S \Rightarrow h \circ j = I_F$.

$\therefore j$ is a monomorphism since I_F is an isomorphism

Consider the following diagram (4.6) :-

diagram (4.6)

$$F' \xrightarrow{h} F \xrightarrow{j} F', \quad F' \xrightarrow{j \circ h} F'$$

$$(j \circ h) \circ f' = j \circ (h \circ f') \\ = j \circ f \text{ by } (**) \\ = f' \text{ by } (*).$$

And $I_{F'} \circ f' = f'$ identity. But F' is a free module on $S \Rightarrow j \circ h = I_{F'}$.

$\therefore j$ is an epimorphism since $I_{F'}$ is an isomorphism $\Rightarrow j$ is an isomorphism.

THEOREM 4.2.14. (Existence theorem)

On any set S , there is always a free R -module.

Proof :-

Suppose that $S \neq \emptyset$. Let $F = \{ \varphi \mid \varphi: S \rightarrow R \text{ is a function such that } \varphi(x) = 0, \text{ exact for a finite number of elements } x \text{ in } S \}$.

$F \neq \emptyset$ since zero function $\in F$ such that $\varphi(x) = 0$.

Define $+: F \times F \rightarrow F$ by $(\varphi + \psi)(x) = \varphi(x) + \psi(x)$,

Define $\cdot: R \times F \rightarrow F$ by $(r \cdot \varphi)(x) = r \cdot \varphi(x), \forall \varphi, \psi \in F, \forall x \in S \text{ and } \forall r \in R$.

Then F is a R -module (**check**)

Let $f: S \rightarrow F$ be a function such that $(f(x))(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x = y \\ 0 & \text{if } x \neq y \end{cases}, \forall x, y \in S$

To prove (F, f) is a free R -module on S ?

Let X be any R -module and Let $g: S \rightarrow X$ be a function. Define $h: F \rightarrow X$ such that

$$h(\varphi) = \sum_{x \in S} \varphi(x) \cdot g(x) \in X.$$

well-defined :- Let $\varphi, \psi \in F$ and $\varphi = \psi$

$$\therefore \varphi(x) = \psi(x), \forall x \in S \Rightarrow \varphi(x)g(x) = \psi(x)g(x), \forall x \in S \Rightarrow$$

$$\sum_{x \in S} \varphi(x)g(x) = \sum_{x \in S} \psi(x)g(x) \Rightarrow h(\varphi) = h(\psi) \Rightarrow h \text{ is well-defined.}$$

Homomorphism :-

$$\begin{aligned} 1) h(\varphi, \psi) &= \sum_{x \in S} (\varphi + \psi)(x)g(x) \\ &= \sum_{x \in S} (\varphi(x) + \psi(x))g(x) \\ &= \sum_{x \in S} \varphi(x)g(x) + \sum_{x \in S} \psi(x)g(x) \\ &= \sum_{x \in S} \varphi(x)g(x) + \sum_{x \in S} \psi(x)g(x) \\ &= h(\varphi) + h(\psi) \end{aligned}$$

$$2) \text{ Let } r \in R, \varphi \in F, h(r\varphi) = \sum r.\varphi(x)g(x) = r.\sum \varphi(x)g(x) = r.h(\varphi).$$

Associative :- $\forall \varphi, \psi, \sigma \in F, x \in S.$

$$(\varphi + (\psi + \sigma))(x) = \varphi(x) + (\psi(x) + \sigma(x)) = (\varphi(x) + \psi(x)) + \sigma(x) = ((\varphi + \psi) + \sigma)(x).$$

Identity element :- $\forall \psi \in F, x \in S \exists \varphi \in F$, such that $\varphi(x) + \psi(x) = \psi(x) = \psi(x) + \varphi(x)$.

Inverse element :- $\forall \varphi(x) \in F \exists -\varphi(x) \in F$ such that $\varphi(x) + (-\varphi(x)) = 0 = (-\varphi(x)) + \varphi(x)$.

Commutative :- $\forall \varphi, \psi \in F, x \in S.$

$$(\varphi + \psi)(x) = \varphi(x) + \psi(x) = \psi(x) + \varphi(x) = (\psi + \varphi)(x). \therefore (F, +) \text{ is an abelian group.}$$

Let $\varphi, \psi \in F, r \in R \Rightarrow (r.(\varphi + \psi))(x) = r.(\varphi + \psi)(x)$ by define scalme.

$$\begin{aligned} &= r.(\varphi(x) + \psi(x)) && \text{by define of } + \text{ on } F \\ &= r.\varphi(x) + r.\psi(x) && R \text{ is a ring} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Let } r_1, r_2 \in R, \varphi \in F \Rightarrow (r_1.r_2.(\varphi))(x) = r_1.r_2.\varphi(x) = r_1.(r_2.\varphi(x))$$

$\therefore F$ is an R -module

To prove :- $h^{\circ} f = g$?

$$\text{Let } x \in S, (h^{\circ} f)(x) = h(f(x)) = \sum_{y \in S} f(x)(y)g(y) = 1.g(x) = g(x).$$

To proof :- h is unique .

Suppose that there exists a homomorphism $h': F \rightarrow X$ such that $h^{\circ} f = g$.

To proof :- $h' = h$

$$\text{Let } \varphi \in F, h(\varphi) = \sum_{x \in S} \varphi(x).g(x) \text{ since } g = h^{\circ} f$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{x \in S} \varphi(x).h'(f(x)) \\ &= \sum_{x \in S} h'(\varphi(x)f(x)) \text{ since } h' \text{ is homomorphism} \\ &= h'(\sum_{x \in S} \varphi(x)f(x)) \\ &= h'(\varphi) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{since } \varphi(+) = (\sum_{x \in S} \varphi(x)f(x))(t)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \varphi(x_1)f(x_1) + \varphi(x_2)f(x_2) + \dots + \varphi(t)f(t) \\ &= 0 + 0 + \dots + \varphi(t).1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore h(\varphi) = h'(\varphi)$$

$\therefore (F, f)$ is a free R -module on S .

THEOREM 4.2.15.

Every R -module is isomorphic to a quotient of a free R -module.

Proof :-

Let X be any R -module and let S be a subset of X which generates X .
Let F be the free R -module on the set S consider the following diagram .

diagram (4.7)

Where i is the inclusion mapping from S into X . Since F is a free R -module
 $\Rightarrow \exists$ a unique homomorphism $h:F \rightarrow X$ such that $h \circ f = i$.

$$S = i(S) = (h \circ f)(S) = h(f(S)). \text{ But } h(f(S)) \subseteq h(F). \therefore S \subseteq h(F).$$

But $h(F)$ is a submodule of X and X is generated by $S \Rightarrow h(F) = X$.

$\Rightarrow h$ is an epimorphism

$\therefore F/\ker h \cong X$, by the first fund theorem of isomorphism .

Hence, X is isomorphic to a quotient of F .

THEOREM 4.2.16.

A subset S of a R -module X is a basis for X if and only if, the inclusion mapping $i:S \rightarrow X$ extended to an isomorphism $h:F \rightarrow X$, where F is the Free R -module on set S .

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that S is a basis for X consider the following diagram :-

diagram (4.8)

Since F is a free R -module on $S \Rightarrow \exists!$ homomorphism $h:F \rightarrow X$ such that $h \circ f = i$.

That is h is an extension of i .

To proof h is an isomorphism, (h is 1-1, onto and homomorphism).

$$S = i(S) = h(f(S)) \subseteq h(F) .$$

But S is a basis for $X \Rightarrow S$ generates X and since $h(F)$ is a submodule of X contains S

$\therefore h(F) = X \Rightarrow h$ is an epimorphism.

$$F = \{ \varphi: S \rightarrow R \mid \varphi \text{ is a mapping such that } \varphi(x) = 0 \text{ except for a finite number of } x \in S \} .$$

Or $\varphi(x) \neq 0$ for at most finite number of $x \in S$.

$$\text{Let } \varphi \in \ker h \therefore h(\varphi) = 0$$

$$0 = h(\varphi) = \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi(x_i) i(x_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi(x_i) x_i .$$

$$\therefore \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi(x_i) x_i = 0 . \text{ But } S \text{ is linearly indecomposable (since } S \text{ is a basis for } X).$$

$$\therefore \varphi(x_i) = 0, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \Rightarrow \varphi(x) = 0, \forall x \in F, \text{ since } \varphi \in \ker h \Rightarrow 0 \in \ker h .$$

$\therefore \varphi = 0 \Rightarrow h$ is a 1-1 $\Rightarrow h$ is an isomorphism .

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that $i:S \rightarrow X$ extended to on isomorphism $h:F \rightarrow X$ that is the following diagram is commutative. $h \circ f = i$. To proof, S is a basis for X .

diagram (4.9)

Let $\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i = 0$ where $r_i \in R$ and $x_i \in S, \forall i=1, \dots, n$.

Define $\psi: S \rightarrow R$ such that $\psi(x) = \begin{cases} r_i & \text{if } x = x_i \\ 0 & \text{if } x \neq x_i \end{cases} \therefore \psi \in F$. Since F is the free R -module on S .

$h(\psi) = \sum_{i=1}^n \psi(x_i) i(x_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i = 0 \therefore \psi \in \ker h$.

But h is a monomorphism $\Rightarrow \ker h = 0 \therefore \psi = 0 \Rightarrow \psi(x) = 0, \forall x \in S \Rightarrow r_i = 0, \forall i=1, \dots, n$.

$\therefore S$ is linearly indecomposable.

To prove S generates X . Let $x \in X$ since $h: F \rightarrow X$ is an onto.

$\therefore \exists \varphi \in F$ such that $h(\varphi) = x$

$\therefore \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi(x_i) i(x_i) = x \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi(x_i) x_i = x \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n (t_i) x_i = x, t_i \in R, x_i \in S \Rightarrow S$ generates X .

$\therefore S$ is a basis for X .

DEFINITION 4.2.17. (Projective modules)

An R -module P is called projective if for any epimorphism $f: A \rightarrow B$ (where A and B are any two R -modules) and for any homomorphism $g: P \rightarrow B$, there exists a homomorphism $h: P \rightarrow A$ such that $f \circ h = g$. That is the following diagram commutes

diagram (4.10)

Or every diagram (4.10) of the form :-

(1)

can be embedded in following commutes diagram (4.10).

(2)

THEOREM 4.2.18.

Every free R -module is projective and the converse is not true in general

Proof :-

Let F be a free R -module with basis S and Let $f:A \rightarrow B$ be an epimorphism (A and B are any two R -module) and Let $g:F \rightarrow B$ be a homomorphism . Consider the following diagram :-

diagram (4.11)

$\forall x \in S$. Let $j(x) = a_x \in A \dots \dots (*)$.

Since $f:A \rightarrow B$ is an epimorphism $\Rightarrow \exists a_x \in A$ such that $g(x) = f(a_x)$ (since f is an epimorphism)

Since F is the free R -module on S . $\therefore \exists$ unique homomorphism $h:F \rightarrow A$ such that $h \circ i = j \dots \dots (1)$

We have to show that $f \circ h = g$?

Let $x \in F \Rightarrow x = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i$; $r_i \in R$ and $x_i \in S$ since F is a free R -module $(f \circ h)(x) = f(h(\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i)) = f(\sum_{i=1}^n r_i h(x_i))$, since h is a homomorphism

$= f(\sum_{i=1}^n r_i h(i(x_i))) = f(\sum_{i=1}^n r_i j(x_i))$, by (1)

$= f(\sum_{i=1}^n r_i a_{x_i})$ by (*)

$= \sum_{i=1}^n r_i f(a_{x_i})$ since f is a homomorphism

$= \sum_{i=1}^n r_i g(x_i)$ since $g(x) = f(a_x)$

$= g(\sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i)$ since g is homomorphism

$= g(x)$.

$\therefore f \circ h = g$. $\therefore F$ is projective (by define of projective module)

THEOREM 4.2.19.

Let P be an R -module. Then the following statements are equivalent :-

- 1- P is a projective .
- 2- Every $M \rightarrow P \rightarrow 0$ exact (short exact $(0 \rightarrow N \rightarrow M \rightarrow P \rightarrow 0)$) sequences of the form splits.
- 3- P is a direct summand of a free R -module .

Proof :- (1) \Rightarrow (2)

Suppose that P is a projective R -module. Let $M \xrightarrow{f} P \rightarrow 0$ be an exact sequences

$\Rightarrow f:M \rightarrow P$ is an epimorphism. Consider the following diagram :-

diagram (4.12)

Since P is projective by (1). $\therefore \exists$ a homomorphism $h:P \rightarrow M$ such that $f \circ h = I_P$.

$\therefore h$ is a right inverse of f . \therefore The sequences splits (by theorem) .

(2)⇒(3)

Let P be an R -module. $\therefore \exists$ a free R -module F such that $P \cong F/A$, for some submodule A of F . (every R -module is isomorphism to a quotient of a free R -module).

$\therefore \exists$ an epimorphism $\pi: F \rightarrow P$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore F \xrightarrow{\pi} P \rightarrow 0 \text{ is an exact sequences } \ker \pi &= \{x \in F: \pi(x) = 0\} \\ &= \{x \in F: x + A = A\} \\ &= \{x \in F: x \in A\} \\ &= A \end{aligned}$$

\therefore by (2) this sequences splits. $\therefore \ker \pi$ is a direct summand of F (by define of splitness of sequences). But $\ker \pi = A \Rightarrow F = X \oplus A$ since A is a direct summand of F . $\Rightarrow F/A \cong X$, but $F/A \cong P$ by (1) $\Rightarrow X \cong P$.

$$M = A \oplus B = \{(a, b): a \in A \text{ and } b \in B\}$$

$\rho: M \rightarrow A \Rightarrow \rho(a, b) = a$. P is an epimorphism $M/\ker \rho \cong A$.

$$\ker \rho = \{(a, b) \in M: \rho(a, b) = 0\} = \{(a, b) \in M: a = 0\} = \{(0, b): b \in B\} \cong B.$$

$\therefore M/B \cong A$. Similarly $M/A \cong B$.

$\Rightarrow F = P \oplus A$. $\therefore P$ is a direct summand of F .

(3)⇒(1)

Suppose that P is a direct summand of a free R -module. $\therefore \exists$ a free R -module F such that $F \cong P \oplus X$ for some submodule X of F . Let $f: A \rightarrow B$ be an epimorphism and $g: P \rightarrow B$ be a homomorphism. Consider the following diagram :-

diagram (4.13)

Since F is a free $\Rightarrow F$ is projective (every free module is projective by theorem)

$\therefore \exists$ a homomorphism $k: F \rightarrow A$ such that $f \circ k = g \circ \rho$.

Define $h: \rho \rightarrow A$ by $\{h = k \circ j\} \Rightarrow h$ is a homomorphism, where $j: \rho \rightarrow \rho \oplus X$ is the injection homomorphism

To proof :- $f \circ h = g$?

$$f \circ h = f \circ (k \circ j) = (f \circ k) \circ j = (g \circ \rho) \circ j = g \circ (\rho \circ j) = g \circ I_p = g.$$

$\therefore \rho$ is projective

Note that: $f \circ j = I$ but $j \circ \rho \neq I$.

EXAMPLE 4.2.20.

Z_6 as a Z_6 -module is free since $\{1\}$ is a basis for Z_6 over Z_6 and $Z_6 \cong Z_2 \oplus Z_3$.

If n and m are relatively prime $\Leftrightarrow Z_{nm} \cong Z_n \oplus Z_m$.

$\therefore Z_2$ is a projective Z_6 -module (by theorem every direct summand of a free module is projective). But Z_2 is not free over Z_6 in $Z_2: \bar{0} = \bar{2} \cdot \bar{1}$ and $\bar{0} = \bar{4} \cdot \bar{1} \therefore Z_2$ has no basis over Z_6 .

$Z_6 = \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}, \bar{2}, \bar{3}, \bar{4}, \bar{5}\}$ and $N = \{\bar{0}, \bar{2}, \bar{4}\}, K = \{\bar{0}, \bar{3}\}$

$K \cap N = \{\bar{0}\}$ and $K + N = Z_6 \Rightarrow Z_6 = N \oplus K = \{\bar{0}, \bar{3}, \bar{2}, \bar{5}, \bar{4}, \bar{1}\}$, but $N \cong Z_3, K \cong Z_2 \therefore Z_6 \cong Z_2 \oplus Z_3$.

THEOREM 4.2.21. (Dual basis lemma)

An R -module ρ is projective if and only if, there exists sets $\{x_i: i \in I\} \subseteq \rho$ and $\{f_i: i \in I\} \subseteq \rho^* = \text{Hom}(\rho, R)$ such that $\forall x \in \rho, x = \sum_{i \in I} f_i(x) x_i \in R$ and $f_i(x) = 0$ except for a finite number of $i \in I$.

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that ρ is projective. $\therefore \rho$ is isomorphic to direct of a free R -module (by theorem)

$\therefore \exists$ a free R -module F such that $F \cong \rho \oplus A$ for some submodule A of F .

Let $\{s_i: i \in I\}$ be a basis for F and Let $\sigma: F \rightarrow \rho$ be the projection mapping and Let $x_i = \sigma(s_i), \forall i \in I$

$\therefore \{x_i: i \in I\} \subseteq \rho \quad \forall i \in I$, Let $g_i: F \rightarrow R$ such that $g_i(x) = g_i(\sum_{j=1}^n r_j s_j) = \begin{cases} r_i & \text{if } x = s_i \\ 0 & \text{if } x \neq s_i \end{cases}$

Clearly, $g_i(x) \neq 0$ for a finite number of $i \in I$ and $x = \sum_{i=1}^n g_i(x) s_i$, if $x = s_i$ ------(1).

Since ρ is projective, therefore in the following diagram :-

diagram (4.14)

There exists a homomorphism $h: P \rightarrow F$ such that $f \circ h = I_P$.

Consider the following diagram (4.15):-

diagram (4.15)

Where $f_i = g_i \circ h, \forall i \in I \Rightarrow \{f_i : i \in I\} \subseteq \rho^*, f_i(x) = 0$, except for a finite number of $i \in I$.

Let $x \in \rho \Rightarrow x = I_P(x) = (\rho \circ h)(x) = \rho(h(x))$

$= \rho(\sum_{i=1}^n g_i(h(x))s_i)$ by (1) since $h(x) \in F$.

$= \sum_{i=1}^n g_i(h(x)) \rho(s_i)$ since ρ is a homomorphism

$= \sum_{i=1}^n g_i(h(x)) x_i$ since $\rho(s_i) = x_i \forall i \in I$

$= \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(x) x_i$ since $g_i \circ h = f_i \forall i \in I$.

(\Leftarrow) Conversely, to prove ρ is projective since every R -module is a quotient of a free R -module (by theorem). $\therefore \exists$ a free R -module with basis $\{s_i : i \in I\}$ such that $P \cong F/X$ for some sub module X of F .

$\therefore \exists$ an epimorphism $g : F \rightarrow P$ such that $g(s_i) = x_i, \forall i \in I$.

Define $h : P \rightarrow F$ such that $h(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i s_i$ where $r_i = f_i(x), \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ since $x \in P$ written $x = \sum f(x)$

$(g \circ h)(x) = g(h(x)) = g(\sum r_i s_i) = g(\sum_{i=1}^n f_i(x) s_i)$

$= \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(x) g(s_i)$, since g is homomorphism, $f_i(x) \in R$.

$= \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(x) x_i = x = I_P(x)$. $\therefore g \circ h = I_P \Rightarrow g$ has a right inverse.

\therefore the sequences $0 \rightarrow P \xrightarrow{h} F \xrightarrow{g} P \rightarrow 0$ is splits exact.

$\therefore g$ has a right inverse \Rightarrow the sequences is splits.

Since P is a direct summand of a free R -module, $F/\ker g \cong A$, but $F/\ker g \cong P$. P is direct summand of F . $\therefore P$ is projective (since every direct summand of free, projective).

REMARK 4.2.22.

If $\{P_i\}_{i \in I}$ is a family of R -module and $\{h_i : i \in I\}$ is a family of R -homomorphism from $P_i \rightarrow B, \forall i \in I$.

Then there exists a unique homomorphism $h : \bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i \rightarrow B$ such that $h \circ j_i = h_i$ where $j_i : P_i \rightarrow \bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i$ is the injection homomorphism.

Clearly, $P_1 \xrightarrow{h_1} B$ and $P_2 \xrightarrow{h_2} B$, then $P_1 \oplus P_2 \xrightarrow{h} B$ and $h \circ j_1 = h_1, h \circ j_2 = h_2$.

THEOREM 4.2.23.

Let $\{P_i : i \in I\}$ be a family of R -modules then P_i is projective $\forall i \in I$ if and only if, $\bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i$ is projective.

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) If P_i is projective $\forall i \in I$, to proof $\bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i$ is also projective.

Let $f : A \rightarrow B$ be an epimorphism and $g : \bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i \rightarrow B$ any homomorphism where A and B be any R -modules. Consider the following diagram :-

diagram (4.16)

Since P_i is projective $\forall i \in I$. $\therefore \forall i \in I$.

\exists a homomorphism $h_i: P_i \rightarrow A$ such that $f \circ h_i = g \circ j_i$ -----(1)

And by the previous Remark (4.2.13) ,

\exists a unique homomorphism $h: \bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i \rightarrow A$ such that $h \circ j_i = h_i$ -----(2)

From (2) $\Rightarrow f \circ h \circ j_i = f \circ h_i$. $\therefore f \circ h \circ j_i = g \circ j_i$ from (1), $\therefore f \circ h = g$. $\therefore \bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i$ is projective .

(\Leftarrow) If $\bigoplus P_i$ is projective, to prove P_i is projective $\forall i \in I$.

Let $f: A \rightarrow B$ be an epimorphism and $g_i: P_i \rightarrow B$ be a homomorphism, $\forall i \in I$.

Consider the following diagram :-

diagram (4.17)

Since $\bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i$ is projective , $\therefore \exists$ a homomorphism $h: \bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i \rightarrow A$ such that

(1):- $f \circ h = g_i \circ \rho_i$, where $\rho_i: \bigoplus_{i \in I} P_i \rightarrow P_i$ the projective homomorphism .

Define $h_i: P_i \rightarrow A$ such that

(2):- $h_i = h \circ j_i, \forall i \in I$.

h_i is a homomorphism $\forall i \in I$, to prove $f \circ h_i = g_i, \forall i \in I$, from(2)

$\Rightarrow f \circ h_i = f \circ h \circ j_i, \forall i \in I$

$= g_i \circ \rho_i \circ j_i$, from (1).

$= g_i$, since $\rho_i \circ j_i = \text{Id}_{P_i}, \forall i \in I$.

$\therefore f \circ h_i = g_i \forall i \in I \Rightarrow P_i$ is projective $\forall i \in I$.

DEFINITION 4.2.24.

Let $f: A \rightarrow B$ be a R -homomorphism and Let M be any R -module. Then f induces two homomorphism f' and f'' where :

$f': \text{Hom}(B, M) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(A, M)$ and $f'': \text{Hom}(M, A) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, B)$ are defined by:

$f'(g) = g \circ f, \forall g \in \text{Hom}(B, M): A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} M$ and

$f''(g) = f \circ g \quad \forall g \in \text{Hom}(M, A) \quad M \xrightarrow{g} A \xrightarrow{f} B$

REMARK 4.2.25.

If $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$ is an exact sequences, then the sequences

$$(1) 0 \rightarrow \text{Hom}(C, M) \xrightarrow{g'} \text{Hom}(B, M) \xrightarrow{f'} \text{Hom}(A, M)$$

$$(2) 0 \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, A) \xrightarrow{f''} \text{Hom}(M, B) \xrightarrow{g''} \text{Hom}(M, C)$$

are exact where M is any R-module.

EXERCISE 4.2.26.

$$0 \rightarrow Z \xrightarrow{i} Q \xrightarrow{\pi} Q/Z \rightarrow 0$$

$$0 \rightarrow \text{Hom}(Q/Z, Z) \xrightarrow{\pi'} \text{Hom}(Q, Z) \xrightarrow{i'} \text{Hom}(Z, Z)$$

i' is not onto.

Solution :-

(1) We have to show that g' is 1-1, $f' \circ g' = \{0\}$ and $\text{Im } g' = \ker f'$

$\ker \pi' = \{f \in \text{Hom}(Q/Z, Z) / \pi'(f) = 0\} = 0$, since $\text{Hom}(Q, Z) = 0$.

$\therefore \pi'$ is monomorphism $\Rightarrow g'$ is 1-1.

Let $\alpha \in \ker g' \Rightarrow g'(\alpha) = 0$. But $g'(\alpha) = \alpha \circ g$, by define of g' . $\therefore \alpha \circ g = 0$

$$A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C \xrightarrow{\alpha} M \quad \text{and}$$

$$\alpha \circ g \in \text{Hom}(A, M)$$

$$\alpha \circ g \circ f$$

$$\alpha \circ g \circ f$$

But $g \circ f = \{0\}$, since sequences exact

$\therefore \alpha \circ g \circ f = \{0\}$. $\Rightarrow \alpha = 0$. $\therefore \ker g' = \{0\} \Rightarrow g'$ is 1-1.

If sequences (*) splits $\Rightarrow f'$ in sequences (1) is onto and g'' in sequences (2) is onto .

Or if M is projective $\Rightarrow g''$ is onto.

$$(f' \circ g')(h) = f'(g'(h)) = f'(h \circ g \circ f) = h \circ 0 = \{0\}.$$

$$\text{Im } g' = \{g'(k) : k \in \text{Hom}(C, M)\}, g'(k) = k \circ g \in \text{Hom}(B, M) \Rightarrow \text{Im } g' = \text{Hom}(B, M).$$

$$\ker f' = \{h \in \text{Hom}(B, M) / f'(h) = 0\}$$

$$h \circ f = \{0\} \Rightarrow \text{Hom}(A, M) = \{0\} = \text{Hom}(B, M) \Rightarrow \text{Im } g' = \ker f'.$$

DEFINITION 4.2.27. (Injective modules)

A R-module N is called injective if for any two R-modules A and B and any monomorphism $f: A \rightarrow B$ and for any homomorphism $g: A \rightarrow N$, there exists a homomorphism $h: B \rightarrow N$ such that $h \circ f = g$.

That is the following diagram (4.18) commutes:-

REMARK 4.2.28.

Every R-module can be embedded in an injective R-module .

That is for any R-module M, there exists an injective R-module N and there exists a monomorphism $f:M \rightarrow N$.

THEOREM 4.2.29.

Let N be a R-module .Then the following statements are equivalent :-

- (1) N is injective .
- (2) Every exact sequences of the form $0 \rightarrow N \xrightarrow{f} M$ splits .
- (3) N is isomorphic to a direct summand of an injective R-module .

Proof:-

(1) \Rightarrow (2): Let $0 \rightarrow N \xrightarrow{f} M$ be an exact sequences . Consider the following diagram :-

Since N is injective $\Rightarrow \exists$ a homomorphism $h:M \rightarrow N$ such that $h \circ f = I_N$.

h is a left inverse of f . The above sequences splits (by theorem).

(2) \Rightarrow (3): By the remark (every R-module can be embedded in an injection R-module)

$\therefore \exists$ an injection R-module X and \exists a monomorphism $f:N \rightarrow X$. \therefore The sequences $0 \rightarrow N \xrightarrow{f} X$ is exact \Rightarrow By (2), this sequences is splits $\Rightarrow \text{Im } f$ is a direct summand of X. ($X = \text{Im } f \oplus A$).

But $\text{Im } f \cong N$, since $f:N \rightarrow \text{Im } f$ is an isomorphism because f is a monomorphism .

$\therefore N$ is isomorphic to a direct summand of the injective R-module X.

(3)⇒(1): Let $f:A\rightarrow B$ be a monomorphism, where A and B are any two R -modules and let $g:A\rightarrow N$ be any homomorphism . By (3) N isomorphic to a direct summand of an injective R -module $\Rightarrow \therefore \exists$ an injective R -module X such that $X\cong N\oplus Y$ for some submodules Y of X . Consider the following diagram :-

Since X is an injective R -module $\Rightarrow \exists$ a homomorphism $h:B\rightarrow X$ such that $h\circ f=j\circ g$ ---- (*).

Define $h':B\rightarrow N$ by $h'=f\circ h$, -----(**).

$f:X\rightarrow N$ is the projective homomorphism $\Rightarrow h'$ is a R -homomorphism .

To proof $h'\circ f=g$?

$$h'\circ f=(f\circ h)\circ f, \text{ by (**)}$$

$$=f\circ(h\circ f)=f\circ(j\circ g) \quad \text{by (*)}$$

$$=(f\circ j)\circ g=I_N\circ g. \quad \therefore N \text{ is injective .}$$

THEOREM 4.2.30. (Injective test theorem):-

A R -module N is injective if and only if, for each ideal I of R and for each homomorphism $f:I\rightarrow N$, there exists a homomorphism $g:R\rightarrow N$ such that $g\circ i=f$, where $i:I\rightarrow R$ is the inclusion homomorphism . (That is N is injection if f for each ideal I of R , every homomorphism from I to N can be extended to a homomorphism from R to N).

Proof :-

(⇒) Suppose that N is injective since $i:I\rightarrow R$ is monomorphism $f:I\rightarrow N$ is homomorphism $\Rightarrow \exists$ homomorphism $g:P\rightarrow N$ such that $g\circ i=f$ (by definition of injective).

(⇐) To prove N is injective .

Let A and B be two R -module and $f:A\rightarrow B$ be any homomorphism.

Let $S=\{(B_\alpha, g_\alpha):B_\alpha \text{ is a sub module of } B \text{ containing } \text{Im } f \text{ and } g_\alpha: B_\alpha\rightarrow N \text{ such that } g_\alpha\circ f=g\}$

$S\neq\emptyset$, since $(\text{Im } f, g)\in S$.

Define an ordering \subseteq on S such that $(B_\alpha, g_\alpha)\subseteq(B_\beta, g_\beta)\Leftrightarrow B_\alpha\subseteq B_\beta \wedge g_\alpha|_{B_\alpha}=g_\beta|_{B_\alpha}$.

Then (S, \subseteq) is a p.o.s. $\Leftrightarrow B_\alpha\subseteq B_\beta \wedge g_\alpha|_{B_\alpha}=g_\beta|_{B_\alpha} \Leftrightarrow (B_\alpha, g_\alpha)\subseteq(B_\beta, g_\beta) \Leftrightarrow B_\alpha\subseteq B_\beta \wedge g_\alpha|_{B_\alpha}=g_\beta|_{B_\alpha}$

Let C be a chain in S and let $D=\bigcup_{B_\alpha\in C} B_\alpha\Rightarrow D$ is a submodule of B containing $\text{Im } f$ since B_α containing $\text{Im } f$.

Note that:- (S, \subseteq) is a p.o.s.

(1) \subseteq is ref.

(2) \subseteq is anti-sym.

(3) \subseteq is trans

** if (S, \subseteq) is a p.o.s. ,and $C \subseteq S$ such that $\forall a, b \in C$,either $a \subseteq b$ or $b \subseteq a$, then C is called a chain in S or T.o. subset of S

*** If (S, \subseteq) is a p.o.s. and C is a chain in S , then C is called bounded above or (C has an upper bounded) if there exists an element $X \in S$ such that $a \subseteq X \forall a \in C$

Zorn's Lemma :if (S, \subseteq) is a p.o.s. such that every chain in S is bounded above then S has a maximal element **i.e.** $\exists x \in S$ such that $a \subseteq x \forall a \in S$.

Define $g_c: D \rightarrow N$ such that $g_c(x) = g_\alpha(x), \forall x \in B_\alpha \Rightarrow (D, g_c) \in S$ and (D, g_c) is an upper bounded of C since $C \in S$ and is a chain. \therefore By Zorn's Lemma, S has a maximal element say (B_0, g_0) .

B_0 is submodule of B containing $\text{Im} f$. $g_0: B_0 \rightarrow N$ such that $g_0 \circ f = g$.

To prove $B_0 = B$. Suppose that $B_0 \neq B$. $\therefore \exists x \in B$ such that $x \notin B_0$

Let $I = \{r \in R: rx \in B_0\} \neq \emptyset$, since $0 \in B_0$.

I is an ideal of R , since let r_1 and $r_2 \in I, \forall x \in B$, and $r_1, r_2 \in R$

1- $(r_1, r_2)x = r_1x - r_2x$ since B_0 is an R -module $\in B_0 \Rightarrow (r_1, r_2)x \in B_0 \Rightarrow r_1 - r_2 \in I$

2-Let $s \in R$ and $r \in I \Rightarrow rx \in B_0, (sr)x = s(rx) \in B_0 \therefore sr \in I \Rightarrow I$ is an ideal

Define $k: I \rightarrow N$ by $k(r) = g_0(rx) \quad \forall r \in I$ -----(*) .

k is a homomorphism since g_0 is a homomorphism. \therefore By hyp. There exists a homomorphism .

$k': R \rightarrow N$ such that $k \circ i = k'$

Let $n_0 = k'(1)$, (1 is the ideal of R)

Let B' = the submodule of B generated by $B_0 \cup \{x\}$. $\therefore B' = \{y_0 + rx: y_0 \in B_0, n, r \in R\}$

B' is a submodule of B containing B_0 . $\therefore B'$ is a submodule of B containing $\text{Im} f$

Define $g': B' \rightarrow N$ by $g'(y_0 + rx) = g_0(y_0) + r n_0 \forall y_0 \in B_0 \cap \forall r \in R$.

To proof g' is well-defined

Let $y_0 + r_1x, y'_0 + r_2x \in B'$ such that $y_0 + r_1x = y'_0 + r_2x, y_0 - y'_0 = (r_2 - r_1)x \in B_0$.

$g_0(y_0 - y'_0) = g_0((r_2 - r_1)x)$ since g_0 is a homomorphism (well-defined)

$= k(r_2 - r_1)$ ----by (*).

$= k'(r_2 - r_1)$, since $r_2 - r_1 \in I$ and $k \circ i = k'$

$= (r_2 - r_1)k'(1)$, since k' is a homomorphism and $1 \in R$.

$= (r_2 - r_1)n_0$, since $k'(1) = n_0$. $\therefore g_0(y_0) - g_0(y'_0) = r_2n_0 - r_1n_0$.

$g_0(y_0) + r_1n_0 = g_0(y'_0) + r_2n_0$. $\therefore g'$ is well-defined

To proof g' is a homomorphism and $g' \circ f = g$.

Let $y_0 + r_1x, y'_0 + r_2x \in B'$

(1) $g' \{(y_0 + r_1x) + (y'_0 + r_2x)\} = g' \{(y_0 + y'_0) + (r_1 + r_2)x\}$

$= g_0(y_0 + y'_0) + (r_1 + r_2)n_0 = g_0(y_0) + g_0(y'_0) + r_1n_0 + r_2n_0$

$$=g_0(y_0)+r_1n_0+g_0(y'_0)+r_2n_0=g'(y_0+r_1x)+g'(y'_0+r_2x).$$

$$(2)\forall k\in\mathbb{R} \text{ and } y_0+rx\in B'\Rightarrow g'(k(y_0+rx))=g'((ky_0+rkx))$$

$$=g_0(ky_0)+rk n_0=kg_0(y_0)+kr n_0=k(g_0(y_0)+rn_0)=kg'(y_0+rx).$$

$\therefore g'$ is a homomorphism

$$\Rightarrow \therefore (B',g')\in S \quad \text{since } g'|_{B_0}=g_0$$

But (B_0,g_0) is the maximal element of S and $(B',g')\not\subseteq (B_0,g_0)C!$ a contradiction

$\therefore B_0=B\Rightarrow N$ is injective . $(\exists g_0:B\rightarrow N$ homomorphism).

THEOREM 4.2.31.

Every injective R -module is divisible.

Proof :-

Let N be an injective R -module .To prove N is divisible.

Let $x\in N$ and $0\neq a\in R$,

Let $I=(a)$ be the ideal of R generated by a $I\neq\{0\}$, since $a\neq 0$

Define $f:I\rightarrow N$ by $f(ra)=rx\in N, \forall r\in R$. f is closed .

If $r_1a=r_2a$ in $I\Rightarrow(r_1-r_2)a=0\Rightarrow r_1-r_2=0$ (since $a\neq 0$ and R is an integral domain).

$\therefore r_1=r_2\Rightarrow r_1x=r_2x\Rightarrow f$ is well-defined.

f is a homomorphism since

$$(1)f(r_1a+r_2a)=f((r_1+r_2)a)=(r_1+r_2)x=r_1x+r_2x=f(r_1a)+f(r_2a).$$

$$(2)k\in R,ra\in I. f(k(ra))=f((kr)a)=(kr)x = kf(ra).$$

Since N is an injection R -module by hyp.

$\therefore \exists$ a homomorphism $g:R\rightarrow N$ such that $g\circ I=f, g(1)=y\in N$

$$x=1.x=f(1.a)=f(a)=g(a) \quad \text{since } g\circ I=f$$

$=ag(1)$, since g is homomorphism

$$=ax' \quad \text{where } g(1)=x'\in N$$

$\therefore N$ is divisible .

THEOREM 4.2.32.

Let R be an integral domain and N be a torsion-free divisible R -module. Then N is injective.

Proof :-

Let I be a non-zero ideal in R and let $f:I\rightarrow N$ be any homomorphism .

Let $0\neq a\in I\Rightarrow f(a)\in N$. But N is divisible by hyp.

$\therefore \exists x\in N$ such that $f(a)=ax$

Define $g:R\rightarrow N$ such that $g(r)=rx, \forall r\in R$

If $r_1=r_2\Rightarrow r_1-r_2=0\Rightarrow(r_1-r_2)x=0$, since N is torsion free $\Rightarrow r_1x=r_2x$. $\therefore g$ is well-defined.

g is a homomorphism since

$$(1)g(r_1+r_2)=(r_1+r_2)x=r_1x+r_2x=g(r_1)+g(r_2)$$

$$(2)\text{Let } k\in R, r_1\in R\Rightarrow g(kr_1)=kr_1x=kg(r_1)\Rightarrow g \text{ is homomorphism.}$$

To proof $g\circ I=f$.

We have $f(a)=ax \Rightarrow rf(a)=rax \quad \forall r \in R$

$f(ra)=rax \Rightarrow af(r)=arx.$

$a(f(r)-rx)=0$ and $a \neq 0$ and N is torsion free. $\Rightarrow f(r)-rx=0.$

$f(r)=rx, \forall r \in R$

$\therefore g(r)=f(r) \quad \forall r \in I$

$G(i(r))=f(r).$

$(g \circ i)(r)=f(r) \Rightarrow g \circ I = f$

$\therefore N$ is injective by injective test theorem.

EXAMPLES 4.2.33.

(1) Q as a Z -module is injective since Q is divisible and torsion-free.

(2) Q/Z as a Z -module is injective since Q/Z is divisible and torsion-free.

$Q/Z = \{x+Z : x \in Q\} \forall x+Z \in Q/Z$ and $r \neq 0 \in R$

$\exists x' \in Q/Z$ such that $r(x'+Z) = X' \in Q/Z. \therefore Q/Z$ is divisible

THEOREM 4.2.34.

Let R be a principal ideal domain. Then a R -module N is injective if and only if, it is divisible.

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that N is injective, to prove N is divisible.

Let $x \in N$ and $0 \neq r \in R$, let I be an ideal of R and $I=(r)$ for some $r \in R$.

Let $f: I \rightarrow N$ such that $f(r)=rx, r \in I$

$f(ar)=ax, a \in R, r \in I$

$a_1r=a_2r \Rightarrow (a_1-a_2)r=0 \Rightarrow a_1-a_2=0 \Rightarrow a_1=a_2 \Rightarrow a_1x=a_2x$

$\therefore f$ is well-defined

$f(a_1r+a_2r)=(a_1+a_2)x=a_1x+a_2x.$

Since N is injective over $R \therefore \exists$ a homomorphism $g: R \rightarrow N$ such that $g \circ i = f$.

Let $g(1)=a$, claim $x=ra$?

$x=f(r)=(g \circ i)(r)=g(r)=rg(1)=ra. \therefore N$ is divisible.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose N is divisible, to prove N is injective.

Let I be an ideal of R and let $f: I \rightarrow N$ be a homomorphism. $\therefore R$ is a principal ideal

$\Rightarrow I=(n)$ for some $n \in R$ But $f(n)=x \in N$ -----(*)

Since N is divisible by hyp and $x \in N$ and $n \in R \therefore \exists y \in N$ such that $x=ny$ -----(**).

define $g: R \rightarrow N$ such that $g(r)=ry \quad \forall r \in R$

$\therefore g$ is homomorphism since Let $r=0 \Rightarrow g(0)=0. y=0 \Rightarrow g(0)=0$

to prove $g \circ i = f$?

Let $a \in I \Rightarrow a=tn,$ for some $t \in R.$

Since $I=(n)$ $(g \circ i)(a)=(g \circ i)(tn)=g(i(tn))=g(tn)=tg(n)=t(ny)=tx=tf(n)=f(tn)=f(a) \therefore g \circ i = f$

$\Rightarrow N$ is injective by theorem test.

THEOREM 4.2.35.

Let $\{N_a\}_{a \in \Lambda}$ be a family of R -modules, then $\pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injective if and only if, N_a is injective $\forall a \in \Lambda$.

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) Let $\pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injective, to proof N_a is injective $\forall a \in \Lambda$.

Consider the following diagram :-

diagram (4.21)

Let the sequences $0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B$ and f is a monomorphism and $g: A \rightarrow N_a$ homomorphism

Let f is projection homomorphism of $\pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ on to N_a and j is injection homomorphism of N_a into $\pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$. Since $\pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injection $\therefore \exists$ homomorphism $h: B \rightarrow \pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ such that

$$h \circ f = j \circ g \text{ ---(1)}$$

Define $h': B \rightarrow N_a$ such that $f \circ h = h'$ ----(2)

Its homomorphism since f and h are homomorphism.

To proof $h' \circ f = g$?

$$h' \circ f = (f \circ h) \circ f = f \circ (h \circ f) = f \circ (j \circ g) \text{ by (1)}$$

$$= (f \circ j) \circ g = I_{N_a} \circ g = g.$$

$\therefore N_a$ is injective

(\Leftarrow) Let N_a is injective $\forall a \in \Lambda$, to proof $\pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injective.

Since N_a is injective : so $f: A \rightarrow B$ is a monomorphism

since N_a is injective $\Rightarrow \exists$ a homomorphism $h: B \rightarrow N_a$ such that $h \circ f = f \circ N_a$

Consider the following diagram(4.22) :-

diagram (4.22)

Let $j: N_a \rightarrow \pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injection homomorphism . Define $h_\alpha: B \rightarrow \pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ such that $h_\alpha = j \circ h \Rightarrow h_\alpha$ is a homomorphism , since j and h is homomorphism .

To proof $h_\alpha \circ f = g_\alpha$?

$$h_\alpha \circ f = (j \circ h) \circ f = j \circ (h \circ f) = j \circ (f \circ g_\alpha) = (j \circ f) \circ g_\alpha = I_{\pi N_\alpha} \circ g_\alpha = g_\alpha .$$

$\therefore \pi_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injective .

COROLLARY 4.2.36.

Let $\{N_a\}_{a \in \Lambda}$ be a family of R-modules. If $\bigoplus_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injective, then N_a is injective $\forall a \in \Lambda$.

Proof :-

If $\bigoplus_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injective to proof N_a is injective $\forall a \in \Lambda$

Consider the following diagram :-

diagram (4.23)

Let $f: A \rightarrow B$ be a monomorphism mapping and $g: A \rightarrow N_a$ be any homomorphism

Let f is projection homomorphism of $\bigoplus_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ onto N_a and j is injection homomorphism of N_a into $\bigoplus_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$

Since $\bigoplus_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injective $\Rightarrow \exists$ homomorphism $h: B \rightarrow \bigoplus_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ such that $h \circ f = j \circ g$ -----(1)

Define $h': B \rightarrow N_a$ such that $h' = f \circ h$ its homomorphism, since f and h are homomorphism

To proof $h' \circ f = g$?

$$h' \circ f = (f \circ h) \circ f = f \circ (h \circ f) = f \circ (j \circ g) = (f \circ j) \circ g = I_{N_a} \circ g = g .$$

$\therefore N_a$ is injective

COROLLARY 4.2.37.

Let N_a be a family of R-modules. Then N_a is injective if and only if, N_a is divisible.

Proof :-

(\Rightarrow) Suppose that N is injective, to proof N is divisible .

Let $x \in N$ and $0 \neq a \in R$,

Let $I = (a)$ (since R is a principle ideal domain)

Let $f: I \rightarrow N$ such that $f(a \cdot r) = r \cdot x \in N, \forall r \in R$

$$ar_1 = ar_2 \Rightarrow a(r_1 - r_2) = 0 \Rightarrow r_1 - r_2 = 0 \quad \text{since } 0 \neq a \in R \text{ is P.I.d.}$$

$$r_1 = r_2 \Rightarrow r_1 x = r_2 x \Rightarrow f \text{ is well-defined}$$

Let $ar_1, ar_2 \in I \Rightarrow f(a(r_1+r_2)) = (r_1+r_2)x = r_1x+r_2x = f(ar_1)+f(ar_2)$.

Let $k \in R, ar \in I \Rightarrow f(k(ar)) = f((ka)r) = krx = kf(ar) \therefore f$ is a homomorphism .

Since N is injective over $R \Rightarrow \exists$ a homomorphism $g:R \rightarrow N$ such that $g \circ i = f$.

$\therefore x = 1.x = f(a.1) = (g \circ i)(a) = g(a) = ag(1) = ax'$ since $x' \in N$. $\therefore N$ is divisible

EXERCISE 3.3.38.

If $\bigoplus_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is injective, then N_a is injective $\forall_{a \in \Lambda} R$

and $g_\alpha : A \rightarrow \prod_{a \in \Lambda} N_a$ is homomorphism.

PROBLMES

(1) Let M be a Q -module. Show that the given scalar multiplication is the only one that can be used to make M a Q -module.

(2) Let M be a non-trivial finite abelian group. Can M be made into a Q -module?

(3) Let R be a ring and let I be a subset of R . Using the multiplication in R as the scalar multiplication, show that I is a left R -module if and only if I is a left ideal of R .

(4) Let n be a positive integer. Determine $\text{Hom}_Z(Z, Z/(n))$ and $\text{Hom}_Z(Z/(n), Z)$

(5) A module M is called irreducible if $M \neq 0$ and M are the only sub modules of M . Show that a module M is irreducible if and only if, $M \neq 0$ and M is generated by any nonzero element in M

(6) Show that an R -module M is irreducible if and only if, $M \cong R/I$ for some maximal ideal I of R .

(7) Let M be an R -module. Define $\text{ann}_R M = \text{ann} M = \{a \in R : aM = 0\}$.

(8) Let M, M_1, \dots, M_n be R -modules. Suppose given R -linear maps $n_i: M \rightarrow M_i$ for each i . Show that the map $n_1 \oplus \dots \oplus n_n: M \rightarrow M_1 \oplus \dots \oplus M_n$ such that $m \rightarrow (n_1(m), \dots, n_n(m))$ is a R -linear

(9) Let M_1, \dots, M_n be sub modules of an R -module M having the properties:

(a) $M = M_1 + \dots + M_n$, and

(b) for every $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, we have $M_i \cap (M_1 + \dots + M_{i-1} + M_{i+1} + \dots + M_n) = 0$.

Then $M \cong M_1 \oplus \dots \oplus M_n$.

(10) Let M_1, \dots, M_n be sub modules of an R -module M having the properties :

(a) $M = M_1 + \dots + M_n$, and

(b) the "triangular" set of conditions $M_1 \cap M_2 = 0$

$$(M_1 + M_2) \cap M_3 = 0$$

⋮

$$(M_1 + \dots + M_{n-1}) \cap M_n = 0.$$

Then $M \cong M_1 \oplus \dots \oplus M_n$.

(11) Let M_1, M_2 be R -modules and N_1, N_2 be submodules of M_1, M_2 respectively. Show that $N_1 \oplus N_2$ is a submodule of $M_1 \oplus M_2$. Show that $\frac{M_1 \oplus M_2}{N_1 \oplus N_2} \cong \frac{M_1}{N_1} \oplus \frac{M_2}{N_2}$.

(12) If M_1, M_2 are submodules of M such that $M = M_1 \oplus M_2$, then $M/M_1 \cong M_2$ and $M/M_2 \cong M_1$.

(13) Let M and N be R -modules. Let $f: M \rightarrow N$ and $g: N \rightarrow M$ be R -linear maps such that $fg(n) = n$ for all $n \in N$. Show that $M \cong \ker f \oplus \text{Im } g$.

References

- [1] Burton , **Abstract Algebra** , .
- [2] D. S. Dummit and R. M. Foote, **Abstract Algebra**, 2004.
- [3] I. Carl Faith, **Algebra: Rings , Modules and Categories**, .
- [4] Th. W. Hungerford, **Algebra**, 1974.
- [5] H. A. Nielsen, **Elementary Commutative Algebra**, 2005.
- [6] M.F. Atiyah and I.G. Macdonald, **Introduction to commutative algebra**.
- [7] J. Lambek, **Lectures on rings and modules** ..
- [8] T. S. Plyth, **Module theory an approach to linear algebra**, 1977.
- [9] F. Kasch., **Modules and Rings** , Academic Press, London, New York, 1982.
- [10] F. W .Anderson and K .R .Fuller, **Rings and Categories Modules**.
- [11] P. Ribembom, **Rings and modules**.
- [12] P. E. Bland, **Rings and Their Modules**, 2011.